

**BIOFUEL RESEARCH INSTITUTE, NAZE,
OWERRI-NORTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA,
IMO STATE**

BY

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this design project was carried out by **Onwukwe, Chukwuemeka S.O** with registration number **2016 082 024** under the supervision of Arc. C.T.N.M. Madubuko in partial fulfillment for the award of Master of Science degree (M.Sc.) in Architecture.

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DEDICATION

This project is dedicated to God Almighty, my parents and my family.

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ABSTRACT

The policy framework of the Nigerian Bio-fuel Policy and Incentives (2007) clearly gives the Federal Government of Nigeria the legal backing to initiate and develop proactive measures aimed at maximizing the potentials of biofuels. This is only possible through the existence of a facility that is saddled with the responsibility of carrying out cutting-edge research into biofuels and biomasses. With the country's dependence on fossil fuels, its loss of revenue to fuel importation and, most especially, the downward slide of the country's energy and power indices, it has become imperative for the country to key into the biofuel revolution in order to secure its place in the committee of "green" nations. Methodology adopted for the collation of data were through interviews, observations and case studies conducted on six (6) relevant and related facilities of semblance. Independent Assessors Correlation Module involving six (6) professionals from the construction industry was used to analyze variables that were used as final design considerations.

Results showed that the proposed scheme would, among other variables, adopt a three-dimensional laboratory module as planning layout for laboratories, support spaces and offices while restrictive circulation pattern and security of laboratory test procedures are among some of the design tenets adopted in the scheme. The design solution/scheme adopted is in strict compliance to the 2003 United States of America Department of Defense Whole Building Design Guide which ensured that the proposed Biofuel Research Institute is properly planned and equipped to facilitate pristine and informed research into biofuels and biomasses.

Keywords: Biofuels, Biomasses, Fossil fuels, Independent Assessors Correlation Module, Three-dimensional Laboratory Module

CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND TO THE PROJECT

*The Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) disclosed that the Federal Government would invest about \$50 billion to the development of domestic Biofuel Industry which would serve as an alternative energy source for Nigeria. It said the \$50 billion **Biofuel Fund** would be contributed by different government agencies and development banks including the Bank of Industry (BOI), Bank of Agriculture (BOA) and Development Bank of Nigeria (DBN), that are relevant to the development of a vibrant domestic biofuel industry for Nigeria. The Governor of CBN, Mr. Godwin Emefiele, said this at a workshop on biofuel development in Nigeria (Chineme, 2017).*

“I am particularly impressed by the commitments of the organizers of this laudable initiative and the contributions from all stakeholders in developing and adopting the draft Biofuel policy and Initiatives. As the world continues in search of better and cheaper energy through renewable energy resources, one cannot but admit that the advantages of Biofuels utilization are legion. Therefore, this workshop is expected to further enlighten Nigerians on the Economic, Environmental and Agricultural and Social benefits to the country” (Idris, 2017).

Currently, fossil-based energy resources, such as petroleum, coal, and natural gas, are responsible for about three quarters of the world's primary energy consumption, each corresponding to 33%, 24%, and 19%, respectively. Alternatives to fossil-based energy resources are nuclear power (5%), hydropower (6%), and biomass (13%), representing currently about one quarter of the world's primary energy consumption. With decreasing crude-oil reserves, enhanced demand for fuels worldwide, increased climate concerns about the use of fossil-based energy carriers, and political commitment, the focus has recently turned towards improved utilization of renewable energy resources. Biomass is an abundant and carbon-neutral renewable energy resource for the production of biofuels and valuable chemicals. Energy production from biomass has the advantage of forming smaller amounts of greenhouse gases compared to the conversion of fossil fuels, as the carbon dioxide generated during the energy conversion is consumed during subsequent biomass regrowth (Coelho, 2005).

At a time when the focus is on global warming, carbon dioxide emission, secure energy supply, and less consumption of fossil-based fuels, the use of renewable energy resources is essential. With the exception of hydroelectricity and nuclear energy, the majority of the world's energy needs are supplied through petrochemical sources, coal and natural gas. All of these sources are finite and at current usage rates will be consumed by the end of the next century (CONCAWE, 2000). The depletion of world petroleum reserves and increased environmental concerns has stimulated recent interest in alternative sources for petroleum-based fuels.

Biodiesel has arisen as a potential candidate for a diesel substitute due to the similarities it has with petroleum-based diesel.

Initial efforts to produce biofuels date back to the early days of the automobile. However, they were quickly replaced as the fuel of choice by cheap petrol, which continued relatively unchallenged until the oil crisis of the 1970s, inducing governments to explore alternative sources of fuel. In 1975 the Brazilian Government launched the PROALCOOL Programme to replace imported gasoline with Bioethanol produced from locally grown sugarcane. It was then that biofuels started to be seen as a serious alternative to petrol. However, once the oil crisis ended in the late 1970s to early 1980s, interest in biofuels diminished. Renewed interest in biofuels has been reflected in the rapid expansion of global biofuel markets in the last five years or so. Commonly cited driving forces behind the current market development of biofuels include: current high oil prices, opportunities for greater energy security, and currency savings through a reduced oil bill. But what is new about this renewed interest and what makes biofuels a serious option for partially replacing oil as a transport fuel are their alleged reduced greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. This would help countries to combat the global warming problem and would enable them to comply with the commitments under the Kyoto Protocol. In addition, the Brazilian experience shows that biofuels can deliver export opportunities and rural development (Coelho, 2005).

Biofuels are a serious option to compete with oil in the transport system compared to other technologies such as hydrogen, because biofuel technologies are already well developed and available in many countries. Bioethanol and biodiesel can be mixed with the petroleum products (gasoline and diesel) they are substituting for and can be burned in traditional combustion engines with blends containing up to 10 per cent biofuels without the need for engine modifications. Flexi-fuel vehicle (FFV) technology is now sufficiently well developed to allow the gradual introduction of biofuels in any country. **FFV cars can run with any type**

of fuel blend from pure gasoline to up to 85% biofuel blend. In addition, the distribution of liquid biofuels can easily be accommodated by the existing infrastructure for petroleum fuel distribution and retailing. Furthermore, the current level of oil prices makes production from the most efficient producing countries competitive (U.S. energy policy, 2004). The fuel and the energy crises of the late 1970's and early 1980; as well as accompanying concerns about the depletion of the world's non-renewable resources provided the incentive to seek alternatives to conventional, petroleum based fuels (Peterson et al., 1986). Globally at present, the most widely used fuels are gasoline and diesel, both coming from fossil fuel. Besides the fear for depletion of fossil fuel, due largely to its non-renewable status, use of gasoline is associated with environmental problems. Aside from being extremely flammable, it contributes to increase hazardous emissions (Munack, Schroder, Krahl, & Bunger, 2001).

In Nigeria, the Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN) recently reported that Nigeria's fossil led economy is under severe pressure. In decades to come, the sun will slowly but certainly set on crude oil production. Today, large hydropower plants are increasingly threatened by a shrinking River Niger, shaking the security of electricity supplies (ECN, 2005). Unfortunately, Niger Delta region, the centre for oil extraction, with severe environmental impacts has been ignored in the country's haste to develop making successful oil prospecting a nearly impossible task for the multinational companies in Nigeria. Thus there is an urgent need to find alternative renewable forms of energy before mineral oil supplies run dry (ENC, 2005). The objective of this desertation is therefore to look at biofuels research and production from various sources and its place in complementing Nigeria's energy needs; advantages of biofuels over fossil fuels and the future prospects of biofuels.

1.1.1 Nigeria's Energy Needs

Energy is fundamental to all human activities. The existing MDGs cannot be achieved without access to energy. Energy is inevitable for poverty alleviation and the production of goods and

services. Globally, more than 1.6 billion people live without access to electricity and 2.4 billion people are without energy services for cooking and heating. Majority of the world poor live in the Sub-Saharan Africa. Nigeria is the most populous country in Sub-Saharan Africa, nearly one quarter of Sub-Sahara Africa's population and is one of the poorest countries in the world despite the huge resources from crude oil export. A huge development challenge in Nigeria is reaching out to the 60% - 70% of the Nigerian population that do not have access to electricity and modern energy services. Renewable energy technology is a promising solution to the energy crisis in Nigeria. Renewable energy, apart from being sustainable and inexhaustible, they can be set up in small units and is therefore suitable for community management and ownership (Uyigüe, 2007).

Energy is a very vital ingredient for sustainable development and has always been vital and indispensable input to the economic needs of our present civilization. Increasing access to energy, particular in the rural area, is vital in the fight against poverty. The basic needs of the poor, rural inclusive are jobs, food, health service, education, housing, clean water and sanitation. Energy plays an important role in ensuring these services (UNDP, 2003). There are essentially two distinct types of energy resources. The renewable, such as solar radiation, wind, biomass, hydro etc. have the inherent capacity to replace and maintain themselves within a renewable length of time. In contrast, the non-renewable energy resources such as coal, petroleum, natural gas, etc. took very long time to form and when consumed, they are not replaced within our life time. One of the effects of policy implementation failures is that despite the abundance of natural gas and renewable energy resources in the country, Nigeria has become notorious for its epileptic power supply. In fact while most communities do not have access to this basic social infrastructure, those that have it cannot rely on the very poor supply from the Power Holding Company of Nigeria. This lack of access to efficient energy resources has had adverse impacts on manufacturing, commerce, industry, agriculture, etc. Agriculture

has not developed beyond the small holder subsistence level, as farmers cannot increase production without energy, while harvests are mostly lost due to lack of storage. Producers and farmers are left with dwindling options. Artisans, small scale enterprises and larger productive enterprises are collapsing due to lack of accessible electricity. The overall result is the loss of jobs and the impoverishment of many. It has been observed that Nigeria's per capita electricity consumption is very low as the country lags behind other African countries in providing energy access to its citizens. Electricity generation is put at about 20 watts per person. Indeed Nigeria's per capita energy consumption is 4 times less than the African average and about 19 times less than the world average (Sambo, 2009).

The World Conventional Energy Supply in 2004 showed Africa's highest supply in descending order of magnitude as follows: South Africa - 30,020 MW; Egypt -14,250 MW; Algeria - 6,188 MW; Libya - 4,710 MW; Morocco - 3,592 MW and Nigeria - 3,500 MW. But between 2005 and 2009, power generating capacity in Nigeria oscillated between 2,600 MW and 3,000 MW. This means that the 44.3 million members of South Africa's population have electricity 12 times more than the over 140 million Nigerians. Egypt which is second with a 14,250 MW capacity and a population of about 77.5 million is approximately 6 times higher than Nigeria in conventional energy output (Okeh, 2007).

The costliest energy need in Nigeria is lighting - similar to the pattern in other African countries where nearly 10 - 15 percent of the poorest households' income may be spent on kerosene lamps, stoves or candles. The case is not different in Nigeria where the poorest households earn about 1 - 2 US dollars per day and spend about 0.4 dollars per day on energy needs. Kerosene lamps provide poor lighting and are expensive, inefficient, highly polluting and dangerous. Nigeria's demand for energy is estimated to be 7,600 MW. However, the country only has a total installed generating capacity of 6,000 MW, which is far from being optimized as the country is only able to achieve 3,000 MW output. A highly-placed government official

responsible for the Power Ministry has blamed their inability to utilize fully the installed generating capacity on the shortage of gas of which they currently get a supply of 230mmscf/d. An additional supply of 600mmscf/d is needed to be able to utilize the maximum capacity at 6,000 MW. It is ironic that a country where gas is wasted through flaring is blaming lack of gas supply for its power problems (Sambo, 2009).

In order to ensure sustainability in the rural and peri-urban areas of Nigeria, energy access needs to be enhanced through the utilization of different applications. It is also likely that such energy systems, based on decentralized and cleaner energy, are better suited to meet the needs of the rural poor. While promoting renewable energies, energy efficiency should not be forgotten. Efficient use of energy in general and that of the renewable energy in particular, help to generate income and make renewable energies (FME, 2000). In Nigeria, many of its citizens suffer lack of access to clean and affordable energy. According to Uyigüe (2007), about 60% - 70% of the nation's population is excluded from the nation's electricity grid. The survival strategy for the affected population is to resort to unsustainable sources of traditional energy whose usage is linked to a myriad of social and health problems including global warming and cancer.

1.1.2 Biofuels

Biofuels are drawing increasing attention worldwide as substitutes for petroleum-derived

Figure 1. 1: Photosynthesis.

Source:

www.rsc.org/Education/Teachers/Resources/cfb/Photosynthesis.htm.

Downloaded on 1st June 2018 at exactly 3:38pm.

transportation fuels to help address energy cost, energy security and global warming concerns associated with liquid fossil fuels. **The term biofuel is used here to mean any liquid, solid or gaseous fuel made from plant materials, animal residues or biodegradable waste that**

Figure 1. 2: World primary energy demand by source, 2005.

Source: <https://www.iea.org/Textbase/npsum/WEO2005SUM.pdf>. Downloaded on 1st June 2018 at exactly 3:43pm.

can be used as a substitute for petroleum-derived fuel. The CO₂ emission is not larger than the quantity consumed by photosynthesis. Biofuels can include relatively familiar ones, such

as ethanol made from sugar cane or diesel-like fuel made from soybean oil, to less familiar fuels such as dimethyl ether (DME) or Fischer-Tropsch liquids (FTL) made from lingo-cellulosic biomass.

A relatively recently popularized classification for liquid biofuels includes “first-generation” and “second-generation” fuels.

There are no strict technical definitions for these terms. The main distinction between them is the feedstock used.

A first-generation fuel is generally one made from sugars, grains, or seeds, i.e. one that uses only a specific (often edible) portion of the above-ground biomass produced by a plant, and relatively simple processing is required to produce a finished fuel. First-generation fuels are already being produced in significant commercial quantities in a number of countries.

Second-generation fuels are generally those made from non-edible lingo-cellulosic biomass, (WHO, 2006) either non-edible residues of food crop production (e.g. corn stalks or rice husks) or non-edible whole plant biomass (e.g. grasses or trees grown specifically for energy). Second-generation fuels are not yet being produced commercially in any country.

Biofuel are renewable energy produced from organic matter by converting the complex carbohydrates in organic matter into energy. They include biodiesel, ethanol, methanol etc. Renewable in the sense that energy source is naturally replaced, when it is used, rather than being destroyed. Biofuel processes can be designed to produce solid, liquid and gaseous fuels.

The term third generation biofuel has only recently entered the mainstream. It refers to biofuel derived from algae. Previously, algae were lumped in with second generation biofuels. However, when it became apparent that algae are capable of much higher yields with lower resource inputs than other feedstock, many suggested that they be moved to their own category.

When it comes to the potential to produce fuel, no feedstock can match algae in terms of quantity or diversity. The diversity of fuel that algae can produce results from two

characteristics of the microorganism. First, algae produce an oil that can easily be refined into diesel or even certain components of gasoline. More importantly, however, is a second property in it can be genetically manipulated to produce everything from ethanol and butanol to even gasoline and diesel fuel directly.

Butanol is of great interest because the alcohol is exceptionally similar to gasoline. In fact, it has a nearly identical energy density to gasoline and an improved emissions profile. Until the advent of genetically modified algae, scientists had a great deal of difficulty producing butanol. Now, several commercial-scale facilities have been developed and are on the brink of making butanol and more popular biofuel than ethanol because it is not only similar in many ways to gasoline, but also does not cause engine damage or even require engine modification the way ethanol does.

The list of fuels that can be derived from algae includes:

1. Biodiesel
2. Butanol
3. Gasoline
4. Methane
5. Ethanol
6. Vegetable Oil
7. Jet Fuel

Diversity is not the only thing that algae has going for it in terms of fuel potential. It is also capable of producing outstanding yields. In fact, algae have been used to produce up to 9000 gallons of biofuel per acre, which is 10-fold what the best traditional feedstock have been able to generate. People who work closely with algae have suggested that yields as high as 20,000 gallons per acre are attainable. According to the United States of America Department of

Energy, yields that are 10 times higher than second generation biofuels mean that only 0.42% of the United States of America land area would be needed to generate enough biofuel to meet all of the United States of America needs. Given that the United States of America is the largest consumer of fuel in the world, that is saying something about the efficiency of algae-based biofuels (Biofuels: The fuel of the future, 2010).

Fourth-generation technology combines genetically optimized feedstocks, which are designed to capture large amounts of carbon, with genomically synthesized microbes, which are made to efficiently make fuels. Key to the process is the capture and sequestration of CO₂, a process that renders fourth-generation biofuels a *carbon negative* source of fuel (Rubens, 2008).

Fourth generation biofuels are simply a step further from the third generation biofuels. The keywords are “carbon capture and storage (CCS)”, both at the level of the feedstock and/or the processing technology. The feedstock is tailored not only to improve the processing efficiency, but it is also designed to capture more carbon dioxide, as the crop grows in cultivation. The processing methods (mainly thermochemical) are also coupled to “carbon capture and storage” technologies which funnels off the carbon dioxide generated into geological formations (geological storage, for example, in exhausted oil fields) or through mineral storage (as carbonates). In this way, fourth generation biofuels are thought to contribute better to reducing GHG (greenhouse gas) emissions, by being more carbon neutral or even carbon negative compared to the other generation biofuels. Fourth generation biofuels epitomize the concept of “Bioenergy with Carbon Storage (BECS).

Table 1. 1: Biofuel yields for different feedstocks and countries

CROP	GLOBAL/ NATIONAL ESTIMATES	BIOFUEL	CROP YIELD (Tonnes/ha)	CONVERSION EFFICIENCY (Litres/tonne)	BIOFUEL YIELD (Litres/ha)
Sugar beet	Global	Ethanol	46.0	110	5 060
Sugar cane	Global	Ethanol	65.0	70	4 550
Cassava	Global	Ethanol	12.0	180	2 070
Maize	Global	Ethanol	4.9	400	1 960
Rice	Global	Ethanol	4.2	430	1 806
Wheat	Global	Ethanol	2.8	340	952
Sorghum	Global	Ethanol	1.3	380	494
Sugar cane	Brazil	Ethanol	73.5	74.5	5 476
Sugar cane	India	Ethanol	60.7	74.5	4 522
Oil palm	Malaysia	Biodiesel	20.6	230	4 736
Oil palm	Indonesia	Biodiesel	17.8	230	4 092
Maize	USA	Ethanol	9.4	399	3 751
Maize	China	Ethanol	5.0	399	1 995
Cassava	Brazil	Ethanol	13.6	137	1 863
Cassava	Nigeria	Ethanol	10.8	137	1 480
Soybean	USA	Biodiesel	2.7	205	552
Soybean	Brazil	Biodiesel	2.4	205	491

Source: (Food and Agriculture Association, 2008).

1.1.3 Biodiesel Fuel Production

Biodiesel production is based on trans-esterification of vegetable oils and fats through the addition of methanol (or other alcohols) and a catalyst, giving glycerol as a co-product. Feedstock includes rapeseeds, sunflower seeds, soy seeds and palm oil seeds from which the oil is extracted chemically or mechanically. Advanced processes include the replacement of methanol of fossil origin, by Bioethanol to produce fatty acid ethyl ester instead of fatty acid methyl ether (the latter being the traditional biodiesel). In order to expand the relatively small resource base of biodiesel, new processes have been developed to use recycled cooking oils and animal fats though these are limited in volume. Hydrogenation of oils and fats is a new process that is entering the market. It can produce a biodiesel that can be blended with fossil diesel up to 50% without any engine modifications. Synthetic biofuel production via biomass gasification and catalytic conversion to liquid using Fischer-Tropsch process (biomass conversion to liquids BTL) offers a variety of potential biofuel production processes that may be suited to current and future engine technologies. The largest biodiesel producer is Germany, which accounts for 50% of global production. Biodiesel is currently most often used in 5 - 20% blends (B5, B20) with conventional diesel, or even in pure B100 form (International Energy Agency, 2007).

1.1.4 Chemical Reaction (Trans-esterification)

Trans-esterification is a base-catalyzed chemical reaction process. Almost all the biodiesel is produced by using a base-catalyzed trans-esterification process, as it is the most economical process for it only requires low temperatures and pressures. In the reaction, 100 parts of a fat or oil is reacted with 10 parts of methanol in the presence of a base catalyst to produce 10 parts of glycerin and 100 parts of methyl esters (biodiesel). Normally, the methanol is charged in excess to assist in quick conversion and the excess is recovered for reuse. The catalyst is usually sodium or potassium hydroxide that has already been mixed with the methanol. A typical trans-

esterification reaction is shown in equation 1, a triglyceride reacts with methanol through a base catalyst to produce biodiesel methyl ester and glycerin.

Equation 1. 1: Trans-esterification reaction between triglyceride and methanol through a base catalyst to produce biodiesel methyl ester and glycerin.

Source: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405653716302342>. Downloaded on 1st June 2018 at exactly 4:14pm.

1.1.5 Uses of Biofuel

Fuels with small amounts of admixed biofuel (up to 5 vol.%; E5) are permitted in common gasoline or diesel engines, and can be used in common vehicles without any form of adaptation. Fuels with higher levels of biofuel (more than 5 vol.%) are currently available in Brazil (gasoline, up to 25% ethanol, E25), USA (10% ethanol/90% gasoline, E10), and Sweden (85% ethanol/15% gasoline, E85). Diesel containing 5 - 30 vol.% fatty acid methyl ester (B5, B10, and B30) are common, as E95 for diesel engines. However, vehicles using this type of fuel must be adapted. Biodiesel can be used as a heating fuel in domestic and commercial boilers, sometimes known as bio-heat. Older furnaces may contain rubber parts that would be affected by biodiesel's solvent properties, but can otherwise burn biodiesel without any conversion required. Bio-butanol may be a more suitable gasoline-range biofuel than Bioethanol, as it has the same energy density as Bioethanol, but would increase the octane number in the gasoline pool. In addition, Bio-butanol has a lower vapor pressure and a lower water solubility, which simplifies handling procedures and the infrastructure. Bioethanol can be used in petrol engines as a replacement for gasoline; it can be mixed with gasoline to any percentage. Gasoline with ethanol added has higher octane number, which means that the engine can typically burn hotter and more effectively. An advantage of ethanol is that it has a higher octane rating than ethanol-free gasoline available at roadside gas stations and ethanol's higher octane rating allows an

increase of an engine's compression ratio for increased thermal efficiency (Farrel & Sanni, 2006).

1.1.6 Advantages of Biofuel over Fossil Fuel

In comparison to fossil fuels, biofuels present some environmental, energetic, and socioeconomic advantages, especially in the transport sector. From an environmental point of

Equation 1. 2: Equation 1 showing the formation of acid rain

Source:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405653716302342>. Downloaded on 1st June 2018 at exactly 4:18pm.

view, their use helps to reduce the pollutants and greenhouse gas emissions. In detail, biodiesel does not emit sulphur-dioxide which helps to reduce acid rain, and also help to reduce suspension particles concentration on air, heavy metals, carbon monoxide, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon and volatile organic components. Moreover, as biofuels are easily biodegradable, they do not affect soil contamination in a negative way. Besides, they help to eliminate some types of residues, e.g. wasted oil for biodiesel production. Petroleum otherwise referred to as crude oil is a mixture hydrocarbon, organic compounds and other elements associated with hydrocarbon such as sulphur, nickel, lead, vanadium etc. (Udoessien, 1997). The presence of sulphur and nitrogen in fossil fuels causes acid rain which is detrimental to health and welfare of man.

Equations for the formation of acid rain are given below:

Equation 1. 3: Equation 2 showing the formation of acid rain

*Source: scienceprojectideasforkids.com › Earth Science.
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The two reactions above could be catalyzed by sunlight to produce nitric acid and

sulphuric acid respectively in the presence of water droplets. This leads to what is termed “acid rain”. So changing over to biofuel conversion will reduce the cost of air pollution control since the raw material contain less sulphur and ash than many other fuels do. Indeed, some bioenergy systems would have positive environmental impacts such as reductions in greenhouse gas emissions, pollution, deforestation and the rate of biodegradation.

Another advantage is that biodiesel can be described as “carbon neutral”. This means that the fuel produces no net output of carbon in the form of carbon dioxide. This effect occurs because when the oil crop grows it absorbs the same amount of carbon dioxide as it is released when the fuel is combusted. This can be illustrated in a simple process of photosynthesis (Figure 1.1 on page 8) by considering the following equations:

Equation 1. 4: Equation 4 illustrating a simple process of photosynthesis

*Source: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405653716302342>.
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In these equations, there is a balance in the relationship between plants and animals. Plants give off the oxygen needed for animal to breathe; plants absorb the carbon dioxide produced by animal in oxidation. In the oxidation of a carbohydrate, the carbon dioxide produced is exactly balanced by the carbon dioxide consumed by the plant in making the carbohydrate.

Equation 1. 5: Equation 5 illustrating oxidation of a carbohydrate

Source: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2405653716302342>.

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The balance holds no matter how the oxidation takes place. Like the metabolism of glucose in the body, the burning of fermentation alcohol in an engine causes no net increase in carbon dioxide in the atmosphere (Udoessien, 1997).

From the energetic point of view, biofuels are a renewable and clean energy source. Furthermore, their uses help to reduce energy petroleum fuel dependency and they offer a safe global scenery in the global energy market. From the socioeconomic point of view, biofuels are a viable alternative for crop lands in decadence. By this way, population will come back to rural areas keeping reasonable employment and wealth level, and helping new different agrarian factories to be developed.

1.1.7 Future Prospects for Biofuel

While ten years ago there were only a handful of countries producing biofuels, by 2006 many countries around the world are using biofuels on a large scale. Forecasts for the future of this market are very optimistic as all types of countries, industrialized and developing, large and small, are implementing or planning to implement directives to promote greater use of biofuels. Accordingly, production capacity is expected to rise as suggested by the establishment of many new projects around the world.

According to IEA (2004), with the entering into force of the Kyoto Protocol in 2005 and the first target period under the EU Biofuels Initiative coming into effect in December 2005, world biofuel production is expected to quadruple to over 120,000 ML by 2020, accounting for about

6 per cent and 3 per cent of world motor petroleum use and total road energy use, respectively. A more recent estimate from IEA (2004) increased this figure to 10 per cent of world fuel use for transport by 2025 (Licht & F, 2005).

Biofuels are not expected to totally replace oil-based fuel in the transport system; rather they are an alternative or a complement to it. Brazil is expected to continue as the leading Bioethanol producer and exporter. Although the internal market will still account for the largest part of production, exports will rise sharply. According to the São Paulo Sugar and Bioethanol Institute, the value of Brazil's Bioethanol exports are expected to jump from US\$ 1 billion a year to US\$ 8 billion by 2007. The US is expected to continue demanding large quantities of Bioethanol. The stronger demand will be served both by internal production and imports, mainly from Brazil and CBI countries. Other sugar producing countries such as Indonesia and Southern Africa are also predicted to become exporters (Early, Early, & Straub, 2005).

The EU is expected to continue to be the main market and producer of biodiesel, followed by the US and Brazil. Table 2 shows some rough estimates for world production provided by Early et al. (2005), which provide details of the estimated increases in production in the different countries. In terms of feedstock, this production is likely to be composed of 58 per cent of rapeseed oil, 25 per cent soya oil, 16 per cent palm oil and 1 per cent other oils. In order to implement the European Directive 2003/30/EC that sets a target of 5.75 per cent of biofuel within the mix of transport fuel by 2010, 18.6 million tonnes of oil equivalent of biofuels is needed (EC, 2005). This will require imports to sustain the programme (Gain, 2005). Indeed, Malaysia and Indonesia are already expanding palm oil plantations to meet greater demand and are together expected to supply up to 20 per cent of this market. Brazil is also expected to be the main beneficiary of EU imports of soya for biodiesel (Trindade, 2005).

Other promising import markets are likely to be Asian countries like Japan, Korea and Taiwan, which have very little land available for increased production. Japan, for instance, has been highlighted as potentially the world's largest Bioethanol importer (Trindade, 2005). Currently

Japan allows a 3 per cent Bioethanol content in gasoline, which requires 1.8 billion liters of alcohol-based fuel each year. Discussions are taking place on increasing the blend cap to 10 per cent, which would result in a 6 billion liters market. In order to secure this future supply, Japan and Brazil have recently formed a joint venture company that will produce Bioethanol. Japan is also examining the options of palm and coconut oil from the Philippines to make B5 available from April 2006. In China, although supply capacity is increasing fast, growth in demand might well exceed growth in production. Projections show that 22.7 metric tonnes of biofuels will be needed to blend 10 per cent biofuels into all Chinese cars by 2020. The present target is only 11 metric tonnes capacity expansion. The potential for bioenergy development is high. Nigeria has all the vegetational regions of West Africa except that of the desert. Agriculture is the dominant economic activity, which contributes 41% of Nigeria's GDP and employs the highest labour in Nigeria. Roughly 75 percent (74 million hectares) of Nigeria's total land (98 million hectares) is arable and about 40 percent of this is cultivated, leaving the remaining 60% of arable land idle. If Nigeria's farmland is cultivable, it would have medium for good productivity if properly managed. Policy, institutional and technological approach is inevitable to harness bioenergy potential in Nigeria.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In the wake of unending oil drilling catastrophes giving rise to massive destruction of the ecosystem, irresponsible onshore/offshore drilling practices, environmental concerns such as increased Green House Gas emissions (GHG), political instabilities within the oil producing regions, rising concerns over the continual availability of fossil fuels - Nigeria's cardinal source of foreign exchange, fluctuating oil market, politics of oil trading within the Organization of Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), brain drain as a result of underemployment of Nigeria's university and polytechnic graduates and the lingering power generation deficits of

the country (Daily Post, 2017), it has become exigent for Nigeria to join the rest of the world in the search for Renewable Green Energy which is biofuel.

1.3 AIM

The aim of this scheme is to broaden the nation's vista of Architecture on energy sustainability in order to gradually reduce dependence on imported fossil fuels, reduce environmental degradation while at the same time creating a commercially viable industry that contributes positively to the nation's overall Gross Domestic Product.

1.4 OBJECTIVES

Specific objectives include:

- (a). Provide a unique zoning pattern which secludes sensitive circuits of research to low-decibel and ambulatory areas of the site.
- (b). Create a purpose-built structure that proffers four-prong ingenious ways of transforming biomass into biofuel through informed research.
- (c). Ensure synergy and effective communication between wet laboratories, dry laboratories and support offices of all research agencies to be housed in the planning and design of the research and production institute and listed in the Nigerian Bio-fuel Policy and Incentives (2007) (International Association for Energy Economics, 2009).
- (d). Adopt a "racetrack" research corridor plan for the design of the laboratories, support spaces, offices and atrium (National Institute of Building Sciences, 2017).
- (e). Create a restrictive circulation pattern that limits incursion of the public into sensitive parts of the facility that houses the laboratories, test preparation vaults, support offices and sensitive technical sections.

1.5 JUSTIFICATION OF THE PROJECT

Nigeria presently has a policy on biofuels entitled **Nigerian Bio-fuel Policy and Incentives (2007)**. The Policy Document was approved by the Federal Executive Council on June 20th, 2007 and gazetted as a national bio-fuels policy at the same time. The framework of the policy and the incentives is meant to create an enabling environment that is expected to sensitize and catalyze the development of the country's bio-fuels industry. To make the project a realizable objective, the Federal Government through the Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation, (NNPC) created the Renewable Energy Division (RED), to champion the implementation of the programme. The NNPC, by mandate of the former President Olusegun Obasanjo, inaugurated the Renewable Energy Division in August 2005, and charged it with the responsibility of developing the Bio-fuel Industry in Nigeria. A research agency to be known as the Bio-fuels Research Agency shall be established to act as the central coordination body for bio-fuel research in the country. The policy stresses collaborative efforts with local research institutes in feasibility studies namely, *International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA)*, *National Cereal Research Institute (NCRI)*, *National Root Crops Research Institute (NRCRI)*, *Nigerian Institute for Oil Palm Research Council (NIFOR)*, *Forestry Research Institute Nigeria (FRIN)*, *Nigerian Stored Products Research Institute (NSPRI)*, *Institute for Agricultural Research and Extension Services (IARES)*, *Agricultural Research Council of Nigeria (ARCN)*, *National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA)*, *SHEDA Science and Technology Complex (SHESTCO)* *Federal Soil Conservation School (FSCS)*, *National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM)*, *National Agricultural Seeds Council (NASC)*, *Nigerian Automotive Council*, *Raw Materials Research and Development Council (RMRDC)* and *Federal Institute of Industrial Research Oshodi (FIIRO)* and other relevant agencies. There is also collaboration with Government agencies and parastatals in bio-fuels policy development. The Bio-fuels Research Agency shall collaborate with the Ministry of Agriculture and Ministry of Science and Technology to provide direction for research in

crop production, industry technology and processes pertaining to the production of bio-fuels (Peter & Gbenga, 2009). This forms the main justification of this scheme.

When the Minister of State, Petroleum Resources, Dr. Emmanuel Ibe Kachikwu, assumed office in 2015, one of the programmes he highlighted the Muhammadu Buhari Administration would face headlong was biofuels production which he described as the future of combustible energy.

Consequently, he challenged the Petroleum Products Pricing Regulatory Agency (PPPRA) to fast track the development of the National Biofuels Policy and Incentives document to provide an enabling environment for the biofuels industry to thrive.

Since the policy was initiated in 2007, the government has not mustered the necessary political will to properly articulate and implement it.

But the Acting Executive Secretary/Chief Executive of PPPRA, Victor Shidok, on February 3, 2017 held a stakeholders' meeting to outline ways of actualizing planned biofuels production and establish the country's foremost Bio-fuels Research Agency. At the event, he described the project as the country's new economy, while urging stakeholders to support it.

The Biofuel Research Institute, if developed, will offer many benefits. It will open vistas in ways of reducing demand for fossil fuels thereby making energy supply more secure. Their findings would also reduce import bills for our energy-deficient country and offer improved balance of trade and balance of payments. All these developments would unfreeze scarce resources for other pressing needs.

The Biofuel Research Institute will help offer better ways of controlling emissions of greenhouse gases, carbon monoxide and particulates. This will also help proffer better informed ways of improving vehicle performance.

There are potential benefits for agricultural and rural development, including new jobs and income generation, which would undoubtedly help meet the Millennium Development Goals.

These can be fully explored with the Biofuel Research Institute. The Biofuel Research Institute

will help us float informed subsidiary industries which are fully commercialized in order to bring increased economic activity. This commercialization is in the form of having production outlets that manufacture/dispense biofuel products in commercial quantities. This will also help position the country properly towards exploiting opportunities for carbon trading for many African countries.

The Biofuel Research Institute will help in proffering better ways of improving clean-combustion rates of biomasses particular to our clime. Importantly, they may be easier to commercialize than other alternatives because they can be stored and distributed using existing infrastructure as well informed from the institute (Arungu-Olende, 2007).

A lot more benefits accrue from this industry, which offers an alternative to fossil fuel thus providing cleaner and cheaper energy. In fact, it is the new economy of Nigeria. That is where the world is going and Nigeria cannot be left out. It is worthy of mention that the establishment of the Biofuel Research Institute is to be undertaken in conjunction with the Ministry of Petroleum Resources, Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC), State and Federal Governments, ministries and other stakeholders, which include feedstock farmers, blenders, depot owners and potential investors (Uche, 2017).

1.6 STUDY AREA

The intended location of the proposed Biofuel Research Institute is at Naze, along Aba-Owerri road, Owerri-North Local Government Area of Imo State on 5°26'57.5"North and

Figure 1. 3: Satellite imagery of primary study area showing proximal communities and institutions.

Source(s): <https://www.google.com/maps/search/NAZE/@5.4441397,7.0516333,2180m/data=!3m1!1e3>. Downloaded and re-drafted by the author on 1st of June, 2018 at exactly 8:45pm.

7°03'17.9"East.

Imo State consists of twenty-seven (27) Local Government Areas. They include Aboh Mbaize, Ahiazu Mbaize, Ehime Mbanu, Ezinihitte Mbaize, Ideato North, Ideato South, Ihitte/Uboma, Ikeduru, Isiala Mbanu, Isu, Mbaitoli, Ngor Okpala, Njaba, Nkwerre, Nwangele, Obowo, Oguta, Ohaji/Egbema, Okigwe, Onuimo, Orlu, Orsu, Oru East, Oru West, Owerri Municipal, Owerri North, Owerri West and Nwangele. Owerri-North is the secondary study area for this scheme.

Owerri North Local Government Area of Imo State has its headquarters in the town of Orié Uratta. It has an area of 198 square kilometers and a population of 175,395 as at the 2006

census. It encircles Owerri Municipal like a peninsular. Six major roads that lead out of the municipal cuts across Owerri North Communities. In the North, Orlu road leads to Amakaohia and Akwakuma communities. In the East, Okigwe road leads to Orji Community. In the West, Monier Construction Company (MCC) road off Wetheral to Obibi Uratta and Ihiteoha communities. In the South, Mbaise road leads to Egbu and Emekuku communities, while Aba road leads to Agbala, Ulakwo and Naze communities. Naze community is the primary study area for this scheme.

Naze is part of Alaenyi cluster which comprises of five towns: Ihitte-Ogada, Awaka, Egbu, Naze and Owerri-nchi-ise. Naze is made up of six villages: Umuorie, Ezeakiri, Umuosu, Umuezuo, Okpuala, and Umuakali. The resident market is Nkwo Naze, hitherto known as Amara – Isu where traders from hinterlands (Isomas) came to see civil society. Today Naze is regarded for its farmers’ markets, vegetable stands, and large churches. (Wikipedia, 2018)

The proposed site lies within Umuorie and Ezeakiri districts and is accessible from the Aba-Owerri expressway. The southwest part of the site is the Naze Industrial Clusters while on its northwest is a sprawling motorpark which will soon be dismantled in line with the Rescue Mission government of the Owelle Rochas administration.

1.7 SCOPE

The Biofuel Research Institute is expected to house the following facilities:

- a. Four (4) wet laboratories in form of vivarium, fish tanks and algae-culture tanks each of 82m².
- b. One (1) 80 m² Geo-sequestration station.
- c. 82m², 32 nos. each, dry laboratories of including biosynthesis laboratories, transesterification laboratories, photo-biological/electro-fuels laboratories, lignocellulosic laboratories, algae-culture laboratories, anaerobic digestion laboratories, test sampling laboratories, genetics laboratories, support spaces and laboratory offices.

- d. 30-personnel capacity open/general offices for staff of research agencies.
- e. 94m², 4 nos. each expanded conference rooms.
- f. Liaison and supervision offices (supply, investment and industry).
- g. 9m² offices for research residents.
- h. 18m², 4 nos. each Fermentation Tank yards.
- i. 108m², 4 nos. each Biodegradable Municipal Solid Wastes (BMSW) underground reinforced concrete cistern.
- j. Administration Block.
- k. Parking lots for staff and visitors.
- l. 100- capacity restaurant for senior and junior management staff.
- m. 1,128-capacity auditorium.
- n. 60m², 4 nos. each Exhibition and seminar halls.
- o. 54m², 12 nos. each Lecture halls and
- p. 12-prototype unit residency for visiting researchers and technologists.

1.8 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

There are quite a number of challenges this researcher passed through to ensure the fruition of this project. Though most of them were largely avoided, some of them largely influenced the progress of the work and in all justification, need to be listed.

1.8.1 Bureaucratic tendencies of Government Institutions

Sourcing information and carrying out case studies in existing related facilities in the country was a huge task. Even when properly tagged and identified by relevant documents, the staff of most of the institutions visited during case studies were so skeptical in offering you valid information on their modus operandi. Even when assigned a supervisor to keep you in check, one is not allowed to take pictures of some vital areas that may contribute to the overall impact

on data collection. In such cases, the researcher had to improvise by taking sketches as quickly as possible.

1.8.2 Independent Assessors Correlation Module

The Independent Assessors Correlation Module is a tool the researcher devised for the interpretation of data. It is a format that seeks to bridge the gap between the Qualitative Research Study and Quantitative Research study. Over time, case studies are basically the only tool students of Architecture adopt to carry out Qualitative Research studies. Invariably, more time is spent on planning trips and surveys than analyzing data polled. All case studies are tailored only from the researchers' perspective. This is the generally accepted way of carrying out Qualitative Research Studies with case studies. This mode of research procedure was not entirely adopted by the researcher with the introduction of the Independent Assessors Correlation Module where he allowed professionals in various fields of practice in Architecture, Urban and Regional Planning and Quantity Surveying to contribute their quota to help him make informed selection of variables that would impact positively on the validity of design consideration. This adoption is quite new and will take more time to be improved upon and generally accepted in the research domain.

1.8.3 Security Challenges

The teething security challenges in the country seriously affected travel itinerary to places where information were easily accessible. The current herdsmen/farmers clashes and the persistent nature of highway banditry of fleeing boko haram criminals all contributed to the inability of the researcher to travel to the Middle-belt region of the country especially to Benue and Kogi States. These states have veritable case studies which would have broadened survey and viability of results.

1.8.4 Financial Constraints

As with all academic endeavors, there are bound to be financial constraints. These constraints come by way of challenges in securing funds to travel at short notices, compilation of several volumes of documents to be distributed in the course of the research, tariff charges for local and international calls, lodging accommodation in hotels during case studies, and inducements given to get information and data. Others include personal expenses and pay-outs to third parties that are secondary sources of data collection.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 IDENTIFICATION AND HISTORY OF BUILDING TYPE

The building type of the proposed scheme is Educational of Research Laboratory persuasion.

A laboratory is a facility that provides controlled conditions in which scientific or technological research, experiments, and measurement may be performed. Laboratories used for scientific research take many forms because of the differing requirements of specialists in the various fields of science and engineering. A physics laboratory might contain a particle accelerator or vacuum chamber, while a metallurgy laboratory could have apparatus for casting or refining metals or for testing their strength. A chemist or biologist might use a wet laboratory, while a psychologist's laboratory might be a room with one-way mirrors and hidden cameras in which to observe behavior. In some laboratories, such as those commonly used by computer scientists, computers (sometimes supercomputers) are used for either simulations or the analysis of data. Scientists in other fields will use still other types of laboratories. Engineers use laboratories as well to design, build, and test technological devices.

Scientific laboratories can be found as research room and learning spaces in schools and universities, industry, government, or military facilities, and even aboard ships and spacecraft.

Despite the underlying notion of the laboratory as a confined space for experts, the term "laboratory" is also increasingly applied to workshop spaces such as Living Laboratories, Fabrication Laboratories, or Hackerspaces, in which people meet to work on societal problems or make prototypes, working collaboratively or sharing resources. This

development is inspired by new, participatory approaches to science and innovation and relies on user-centered design methods and concepts like Open Innovation or User Innovation. One distinctive feature of work in Open Laboratories is phenomena of translation, driven by the different backgrounds and levels of expertise of the people involved.

Diamond Schmitt Architects states that, “while the technical capabilities of laboratory services are at the highest level, it is in the larger context, how such technical expertise is put to use and this constitutes the greatest effect” (Diamond Schmitt Architects, 2018).

2.1.1 History of Research Laboratories

The earliest laboratory according to the present evidence is a home laboratory of Pythagoras of Samos, the well-known Greek philosopher and scientist. This laboratory was created when Pythagoras conducted an experiment about tones of sound and vibration of string.

In the painting of Louis Pasteur by Albert Edelfelt in 1885, Louis Pasteur is shown comparing a note in his left hand with a bottle filled with a solid in his right hand, and not wearing any personal protective equipment.

Researching in teams started in the 19th century, and many new kinds of equipment were developed in the 20th century.

A 16th century underground alchemical laboratory was accidentally discovered in the year 2002. Rudolf II, Holy Roman Emperor was believed to be the owner. The laboratory is called Speculum Alchemiae and is preserved as a museum in Prague (Wikipedia, 2018).

Laboratory history is inseparable from the history of industrial research. It takes us from scientific instrumentation to teaching, from the discipline's beginnings as the hidden art of alchemy to its modern status as a required course in science. It also takes in the rise of industrial research, the gradual raising of consciousness about safety and the personal impact

of famous chemists. No discipline is immune to fashion, and a luminary — such as Robert Bunsen, who co-discovered spectroscopic analysis, or organic-chemistry pioneer Justus von Liebig — could set the tone for years by building a laboratory to his personal specifications. As Morris shows, over all this stretches culture. Industrial research moved from a broadly French and English occupation during the Enlightenment, an era of experiments on gases and chemical compositions, to a German one in the mid-nineteenth century, with the Americans eventually beginning to take notes and draw up plans of their own in the twentieth century. Each nation had its own style, which blended with the practical aspects of a workplace to create distinctive looks. The most useful features (such as benches with drawers, and dedicated lines for gases and steam) are still to be found today.

Morris deftly keeps all these threads from getting too tangled. The Matter Factory starts in the alchemist's lair of the medieval era, dominated by the largest, hottest furnace available. The book makes clear that many engravings and paintings of alchemists at work must be inaccurate, because they were drawn by people suspicious of the whole enterprise. (Alchemists' own drawings, such as those in the seventeenth-century text *Mutus Liber*, tended toward the wildly allegorical and the willfully obscure.) The German scientist Georgius Agricola's 1556 *De Re Metallica* (On the Nature of Metals) is probably the first reliable guide to early laboratory technique such as the handling of strong acids. In later illustrations, the furnace shrinks, then disappears entirely, and tables and benches appear.

Fume hoods began to take on a modern look by the 1920s, but separate cupboard-like spaces for experimentation (at first unventilated) go back to at least the mid-nineteenth century. Photographs from that time show benches and shelving progressively stretching across the floors and walls, and lines for water, gas, steam and (by the early twentieth century) electricity threading into the picture. Teaching laboratories gradually separate themselves from research laboratories, and industrial laboratories begin to stand on their own.

The nineteenth century saw perhaps the greatest number of changes in laboratory layout, as new instruments such as Bunsen burners and new styles of working, including team research, proliferated. Much of the books focused on this era. The pace speeds up noticeably in the twentieth century, probably because the major features of the modern laboratories were already largely in place, down to the pegboard over the sink for drying glassware.

Today, one industrial laboratory tends to look very much like another. The changes to laboratories of the future will probably come down to variations in the number and capacity of automated instruments. But the space will probably look broadly similar to what we have now, which will no doubt disappoint some industrial designers looking to make a big splash. The Matter Factory, however, is the story of the years (and centuries) during which such splashes could be made, when chemistry was finding out what it could do. It covers a lot of ground, and brings together many old drawings, plans and photographs that are otherwise scattered through a bewildering literature trail. It should remain the definitive history of the industrial laboratory for many years (Lowe, 2018).

2.2 GENERAL PRINCIPLES OF DESIGN ASSOCIATED WITH THE INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH LABORATORIES

Sustainability in the design, construction and operation of an industrial research laboratory involves reducing the overall costs of each segment (design, construction and operation), reducing the resources required by each and the overall waste products generated. The overarching goal of lab managers in their sustainability efforts is to build and operate their labs in the most natural manner possible and in ways that either minimize or negate the research lab's effects on the environment.

Architects, scientists, engineers, laboratory planners and designers investigate all the available aspects of accomplishing these goals when planning and designing a new or renovated

research laboratory. In the design phase, laboratory developers may focus on laboratory aspects such as siting, site layout and planning, floor and space planning, appearance, new concepts, sustainability, innovation, technology, solar orientation, drainage, landscaping, seasonal weather variations, access to transportation resources, flow of researchers through the proposed facility and urban settings. In the construction phase, they may focus on the use or reuse of local materials, minimization of construction-based pollution effects, protection of natural habitats, sensitivity to brownfield areas and reduction of construction waste materials (Studt, Sustainable Laboratory Design and Construction: Sustainability Basics and Design, 2014).

2.2.1 Site Location

There are so many diverse factors affecting the location of any one laboratory that general comment might seem pointless. If it be recognized, however, that a research laboratory is going to be the center of a search for new knowledge, and not just an adjunct of a plant's testing and control laboratory, then some new factors enter the picture, The desirability of research scientists having ready association with other research workers may prove to be more important than their proximity to workers in their own industry. This is well shown by the success of the new "research parks" such as that now developing on the outskirts of Toronto and that at Pointe Claire, outside Montreal (Hutcheon, 1966).

One of the first steps in designing a new sustainable (or other) research laboratory is the site selection for the facility. Site selection and location involves a wide range of criteria that can have a dramatic effect on the sustainability of the completed research laboratory. Site selection and location also can be concerned with not picking the wrong site, such as prime farmland, flood plains, endangered habitats, near wetlands, near bodies of water identified by the Clean Water Act as usable for recreational use and public parklands.

The positive aspects of site selection can include picking sites that are located on previously developed sites; located near public transportation access to reduce pollution from automobile use and picking a site where existing vegetation can reduce the need for creating new stormwater management infrastructures. Of course, each facility and site will have its own particular factors that involve sustainability issues and other non-sustainability-related research laboratory issues as well.

A partial checklist of things to consider and look for in site selection for a sustainable research laboratory can include:

1. Access to academic facilities;
2. Access to locally manufactured/supplied materials;
3. Access to traditional shipping routes/modes;
4. Ecological restoration possibilities;
5. Environmentally sensitive areas;
6. Existing and potential parking characteristics;
7. Historical uses;
8. Mass transit access;
9. Natural drainage patterns;
10. Natural vegetation;
11. Potential building configuration placement choices;
12. Potential employee housing distribution map;
13. Prevailing weather patterns;
14. Soil analysis and contamination concerns;
15. Solar orientation;
16. Stormwater retention capabilities;
17. Surface and subsurface rock strata;

18. Topographical survey;
19. Traditional insect habitat;
20. Utility access for special purpose lab equipment;
21. Zoning and neighborhood characteristics

(Studdt, Sustainable Laboratory Design and Construction: Sustainability Basics and Design, 2014).

2.2.2 Site Layout and Planning

There must be adequate access to the site for large trucks and plenty of parking space for construction workers. There must also be staging space both inside and outside the building. Staging space is used for storing and laying out construction materials like beams. There must also be room for construction trailers; many of the construction contractors place office trailers at the site. Outside space requirements vary, but reserving several times the inside floor space for outside construction needs is not unreasonable.

It is essential to allow for expansion in even the initial phases of planning - by providing enough space around a building, and by planning the building itself so that, if necessary, it can be readily expanded (Hutcheon, 1966).

In the physical layout planning of the building, it is usually possible to arrange the main elements of the plan, by careful off-setting its layout, so that one or other section can be extended if necessary without interfering with the rest of the building. Parking lots for visitors and staff are provided in close proximity to the ingress points in order to discourage unnecessary vehicular traffic within the confines of the site. In initial planning, this sort of arrangement is easy to achieve because once a building is up, it is difficult to achieve. In a structural laboratory, for example, if an extension of its length may conceivably be necessary in the future, the end columns can be designed and installed as regular column", with crane-

rail brackets, etc., in place, and an end wall that can be readily removed if it is so placed that no part of the building lies in the line of possible extension.

Mechanical and electrical services are an essential requirement in all research laboratories. Their provision must therefore be recognized from the very start of building planning. They are not something that can be "fitted in" to the general plans of the architect - as all good architects know (Hutcheon, 1966). Not only must the main provision of services be flexible, but their use in individual laboratories must be similarly adaptable.

Once the units that are to be accommodated in the layout planning of a research laboratory are known, a further important feature of initial planning is the consideration of the interrelation between the various zones. This is most conveniently done by means of a simple flow diagram; blocks representing the various zones and colored lines showing the anticipated flow between respective zones. The pattern of over-all external traffic will probably become clear from even such a simple graphical aid as this. The auditorium/seminar hall will be found, in all probability, to be the focal point for the noisy zone (Hutcheon, 1966).

2.2.3 Floor and Space (Volume) Planning of Industrial Research Laboratories

Over the past 30 years, architects, engineers, facility managers, and researchers have refined the design of typical wet and dry laboratories to a very high level. The following identifies the best solutions in designing a typical laboratory.

2.2.3. a Laboratory Planning Module

The laboratory module is the key unit in any laboratory facility. When designed correctly, a laboratory module will fully coordinate all the architectural and engineering systems. A well-designed modular plan will provide the following benefits:

- 1. Flexibility**—The laboratory module, as Jonas Salk explained, should "encourage change" within the building. Research is changing all the time, and buildings must allow for reasonable change. Many private research companies make physical changes to an average of 25% of their laboratories each year. Most academic institutions annually change the layout of 5 to 10% of their laboratories.
- 2. Expansion**—The use of laboratory planning modules allows the building to adapt easily to needed expansions or contractions without sacrificing facility functionality.

A common laboratory module has a width of approximately 3.2 meters (*10 ft. 6 in.*) but will vary in depth from 6 meters to 9 meters (*20–30 ft.*). The depth is based on the size necessary for the lab and the cost-effectiveness of the structural system. The 3.2 meters (*10 ft. 6 in.*) dimension is based on two rows of casework and equipment (each row 0.762 meter (*2 ft. 6 in.*) deep) on each wall, a 1.524 meters (*5 ft.*) aisle, and 150mm (*6 in.*) for the wall thickness that separates one lab from another. The 1.524 meters (*5 ft.*) aisle width should be considered a minimum because of the requirements of the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA).

The Two-Directional Laboratory Module is another level of flexibility that can be achieved by designing a laboratory module that works in both directions. This allows the casework to be organized in either direction. This concept is more flexible than the basic lab module concept but may require more space. The use of a two-directional grid is beneficial to accommodate different lengths of run for casework. The casework may have to be moved to create a different type or size of workstation.

Three-Dimensional Laboratory Module planning concept combines the basic lab module or a two-directional lab module with any lab corridor arrangement for each floor of a building. This means that a three-dimensional lab module can have a single-corridor arrangement on

one floor, a two-corridor layout on another, and so on. To create a three-dimensional lab module, the following must be considered. They include:

1. A basic or two-directional laboratory module which must be defined,
2. All vertical risers must be fully coordinated (Vertical risers include fire stairs, elevators, restrooms, and shafts for utilities) and
3. The mechanical, electrical, and plumbing systems must be coordinated in the ceiling to work with the multiple corridor arrangements.

2.2.3. b Laboratory Planning Concepts

The relationship of the laboratories, offices, and corridor will have a significant impact on the image and operations of the building. The following must be considered:

1. The users should either want a view of the exterior from their laboratories or the laboratories will be located in the interior, with wall space used for casework and equipment;
2. Some researchers do not want or cannot have natural light in their research spaces;
3. Special instruments and equipment, such as nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) apparatus, electron microscopes, and lasers cannot function properly in natural light. Natural daylight is not desired in *vivarium facilities* or in some support spaces, so these are located in the interior of the building;
4. Zoning the building between laboratory and non-laboratory spaces will reduce costs; Laboratories require 100% outside air while non-laboratory spaces can be designed with re-circulated air, like an office building;
5. Adjacencies with corridors can be organized with a single, two corridor (racetrack), or a three corridor scheme and

Figure 2. 1: Single corridor laboratory design with offices clustered together at the end and in the middle.

Source: <https://www.wbdg.org/building-types/research-facilities/research-laboratory>.
 Downloaded on 4th of June, 2018 at exactly 7:15am.

Figure 2. 2: Single corridor laboratory design with laboratories and offices adjacent to each other..

Source: <https://www.wbdg.org/building-types/research-facilities/research-laboratory>.
 Downloaded on 4th of June, 2018 at exactly 7:05am.

Figure 2. 3: Single corridor lab design with office clusters accessing main labs directly.

Source: <https://www.wbdg.org/building-types/research-facilities/research-laboratory>.
 Downloaded on 4th of June, 2018 at exactly 9:29am.

6. Open laboratories versus closed laboratories. An increasing number of research institutions are creating "open" labs to support team-based work. The open lab concept is significantly different from that of the "closed" lab of the past, which was based on accommodating the individual principle investigator. In open labs, researchers share not only the space itself but also equipment, bench space, and support staff. The open lab format facilitates communication between scientists and makes the lab more easily adaptable for future needs. A wide variety of labs—from wet biology and chemistry labs, to engineering labs, to dry computer science facilities—are now being designed as open labs (National Institute of Building Sciences, 2017).

2.2.3.c Flexibility

In today's laboratories, the ability to expand, reconfigure, and permit multiple uses has become a key concern. The following should be considered to achieve **flexible laboratory interiors**:

1. **Equipment zones**—These should be created in the initial design to accommodate equipment, fixed, or movable casework at a later date.
2. Generic laboratories.
3. **Mobile casework**—This can be comprised of mobile tables and mobile base cabinets. It allows researchers to configure and fit out the lab based on their needs as opposed to adjusting to pre-determined fixed casework.
4. Flexible partitions—These can be taken down and put back up in another location, allowing lab spaces to be configured in a variety of sizes.

5. Overhead service carriers—These are hung from the ceiling. They can have

utilities like piping, electric, data, light fixtures, and snorkel exhausts. They afford maximum flexibility as services are lifted off the floor, allowing free floor space to be configured as needed.

Research Laboratories designed with overhead connects and disconnects allow for flexibility and fast hook up of equipment.

Figure 2. 4: Mobile casework.

Source: <https://www.wbdg.org/building-types/research-facilities/research-laboratory>. Downloaded on 4th of June, 2018 at exactly 9:35am.

6. Research Laboratories should have easy connects/disconnects at walls and ceilings to allow for fast and affordable hook up of equipment.
7. The Engineering systems should be designed such that fume hoods can be added or removed.
8. Space should be allowed in the utility corridors, ceilings, and vertical chases for future HVAC, plumbing, and electric needs.

2.2.3. d Building Systems Distribution Concept

Interstitial spaces

An interstitial space is a separate floor located above each laboratory floor. All services and utilities are located here where they drop down to service the lab below. This system has a high initial cost but it allows the building to accommodate change very easily without interrupting the laboratories.

Figure 2. 5: Conventional design vs. interstitial design.

Source: <https://www.wbdg.org/building-types/research-facilities/research-laboratory>.

Downloaded on 4th of June, 2018 at exactly 9:48am.

Service Corridor

Laboratory spaces adjoin a centrally located corridor where all utility services are located. Maintenance personnel are afforded constant access to main ducts, shutoff valves, and electric panel boxes without having to enter the lab. This service corridor can be doubled up as an equipment/utility corridor where common laboratory equipment like autoclaves, freezer rooms, etc. can be located (National Institute of Building Sciences, 2017).

2.2.4 Appearance (Elevations)

In design, aesthetics refers to the *visual attractiveness* of a product. Studies have proven that creating good aesthetics in a product leads to better usability and user experience.

In designing with the purpose of increasing aesthetic value, one consideration in particular is essential—namely, the notion that beauty is not only objective and universal (as German philosopher of the Enlightenment period Immanuel Kant argued), but that it has a subjective side to it as well. A user’s cultural background, education, or class may influence his or her judgments of aesthetic value. Designers need to understand these aspects in order to match them with the appropriate design. Thus, as aesthetics involves multiple dimensions of a target audience’s makeup, it demands research into diverse areas relevant to a product’s distribution, including foreign market considerations (Interaction Design Foundation, 2018).

Across the four corners of the globe, there are laboratories whose grand exteriors are as progressive and ground-breaking as the research going on inside them. Far from the clinical image of the stereotypical lab, there are many, many research buildings that are examples of both function and form, a testament to both the work contained within and the creative vision of the designers involved in their builds.

From the legendary Holmdel Complex and its campus-style building to the ALBA’s space age, saucer-like appearance, some of these labs take inspiration from their surroundings and local culture, others act as a metaphor, an extension of science’s constant move towards the future. Some even harness their designs for more than just aesthetic reasons, built in a way that’s both visually striking and environmentally friendly. Award-winning and highly regarded in the realms of both architecture and science, these revered research facilities are boundary-pushing examples of the limitless creativity of the mind (Inter Focus, 2018).

2.2.5 Mechanical Systems

The location of main vertical supply/exhaust shafts as well as horizontal ductwork is very crucial in designing a flexible lab. Key issues to consider include: efficiency and flexibility, modular design, initial costs, long-term operational costs, building height and massing, and design image.

The various design options for the mechanical systems are illustrated below:

Figure 2. 7: Shafts in the middle of the building.

Source:

<https://www.wbdg.org/building-types/research-facilities/research-laboratory>. Downloaded on 4th of June, 2018 at exactly 12:06pm.

Figure 2. 6: Shafts at the end of the building.

Source:

<https://www.wbdg.org/building-types/research-facilities/research-laboratory>. Downloaded on 4th of June, 2018 at exactly 12:09pm.

Figure 2. 8: Exhaust at end and supply in the middle.

Source:

<https://www.wbdg.org/building-types/research-facilities/research-laboratory>. Downloaded on 4th of June, 2018 at exactly 12:11pm.

2.2.6 Electrical Systems

Three types of power are generally used for most research laboratory projects:

1. Normal power circuits are connected to the utility supply only, without any backup system. Loads that are typically on normal power include some HVAC equipment, general lighting, and most lab equipment.
2. Emergency power is created with generators that will back up equipment such as refrigerators, freezers, fume hoods, biological safety cabinets, emergency lighting, exhaust fans, animal facilities, and environmental rooms. Examples of safe and efficient emergency power equipment include distributed energy resources (DER), micro-turbines, and fuel cells.

3. An Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) is used for data recording, certain computers, microprocessor-controlled equipment, and possibly the vivarium area. The UPS can be either a central unit or a portable system, such as Distributed Energy Resources (DER), micro-turbines, fuel cells, and Building Integrated Photovoltaics (BIPV).

The following should be considered:

- a. Load estimation;
- b. Site distribution;
- c. Power quality and
- d. Management of electrical cable trays/panel boxes.

For Lighting Design, the following must be considered:

- a. User expectations;
- b. Illumination levels;
- c. Uniformity;
- d. Lighting distribution-indirect, direct, combination;
- e. Luminaire location and orientation-lighting parallel to casework and lighting perpendicular to casework and
- f. Telephone and data systems

(National Institute of Building Sciences, 2017).

2.2.7 Piping Systems

There are several key design goals to strive for in designing laboratory piping systems:

1. Provide a flexible design that allows for easy renovation and modifications;
2. Provide appropriate plumbing systems for each laboratory based on the lab programming;

3. Provide systems that minimize energy usage;
4. Provide equipment arrangements that minimize downtime in the event of a failure;
5. Locate shutoff valves where they are accessible and easily understood and
6. Accomplish all of the preceding goals within the construction budget.

2.2.8 Research Laboratory and Personnel Safety and Security

Protecting human health and life is paramount, and safety must always be the first concern in laboratory building design. Security-protecting a facility from unauthorized access-is also of critical importance. Today, research facility designers must work within the dense regulatory environment in order to create safe and productive lab spaces. The WBDG Resource Page on Security and Safety in Laboratories addresses all these related concerns, including:

1. Laboratory classifications: dependent on the amount and type of chemicals in the laboratory;
2. Containment devices: fume hoods and bio-safety cabinets;
3. Levels of bio-safety containment as a design principle;
4. Radiation safety;
5. Employee safety: showers, eyewashes, other protective measures and
6. Emergency power.

2.2.9 Sustainability Considerations

A typical laboratory currently uses five times as much energy and water per square foot as a typical office building. Research facilities are so energy demanding for a variety of reasons:

1. They contain large numbers of containment and exhaust devices;
2. They house a great deal of heat-generating equipment;
3. Scientists require 24-hour access; and

4. Irreplaceable experiments require fail-safe redundant backup systems and uninterrupted power supply (UPS) or emergency power.

In addition, research facilities have intensive ventilation requirements—including "once through" air—and must meet other health and safety codes, which add to energy use. Examining energy and water requirements from a holistic perspective, however, can identify significant opportunities for improving efficiencies while meeting or exceeding health and safety standards. Sustainable design of lab environments should also improve comfort and worker productivity.

Chilled beams are an excellent opportunity to use new technology to reduce air change rates but not jeopardize safety. NIH conducted a two-year study and determined that chilled beams were the best value for the second phase of their neuroscience facility. The image to the right is from Oklahoma Medical Research Facility (OMRF) with chilled beams installed. The square shaped panel in the ceiling is the chilled beam.

The key aspects of sustainable laboratory design include:

1. Increased energy and water conservation and efficiency;
2. Reduction or elimination of harmful substances and waste;
3. Improvements to the interior and exterior environments, leading to increased productivity;
4. Efficient use of materials and resources and
5. Recycling and increased use of products with recycled content.

Other key factors of sustainability to be considered include:

2.2.9. a Overhangs

Overhangs for shading windows are often designed as part of the wall system to improve the quality of the natural light entering the interior space. The south elevation should have a

horizontal overhang; east and west elevations usually require both horizontal and vertical overhangs.

2.2.9. b Glazing

The glazing material for exterior windows should have a thermal break and an insulating section between the inner and outer sections of the frames. Wood or fiberglass frames will give much better thermal performance than aluminum. Low-E windows with at least an R-3 insulation value should be used. "Super-windows" that incorporate multiple thin plastic films can have an R value as high as 12. The problem is that such windows cost up to four times as much as low-E glass. Operable windows generally will not reduce energy costs; in fact, they may increase energy usage, but they usually enhance the quality of the indoor environment and are therefore preferred by most clients.

2.2.9.c Roofs and Walls

The use of light-colored roofing with a high-albedo coating to reflect light and heat is recommended. The amount of wall and roof insulation needed will vary depending on the climate and the type of lab. For example, equipment-intensive labs will generate a lot of heat and in certain parts of the country will not require as much roof insulation as elsewhere. All electrical outlets and all plumbing and wire penetrations into the building should be sealed, since air leakage can be a significant source of energy waste as well as moisture problems in some parts of the country.

Today, there is quite a bit of discussion about using photovoltaic panels both to enclose a building and to generate electricity. Photovoltaic panels can be integrated into the building envelope as metal roofing, spandrel glazing, or semi-transparent vision glazing (National Institute of Building Sciences, 2017).

2.3 ESTABLISHED STANDARDS, REGULATIONS AND LAWS GUIDING DESIGN

In January 1985 the Laboratories Investigation Unit of the Department of Education and Science commissioned the Unit for Architectural Studies at the Bartlett School of Architecture and Planning, University College London, to carry out a pilot study into current practice in the design and use of research laboratories. In particular, the research team were asked to ascertain how far the standards and recommendations based on the pioneering Nuffield studies of the 1950's still formed an adequate base for design guidance in the present day, and for planning in the future.

This section gives a brief summary of the aims of the pilot study on standards required for the design of research laboratories at the outset, followed by the main findings across the sample as a whole.

The main findings are in two groups:

- a. Those which are to do with space standards in metric terms, and
- b. Those which are more concerned with spatial configuration and layout of benching.

It concludes with a discussion of the areas in which the Nuffield findings and recommendations may now be considered to be out of date, and makes a number of recommendations on both standards of provision and choices of plan layout in research laboratories and the implications for design.

Most importantly, it highlights the urgent need for detailed research in this area across a much larger and more representative sample than was possible at this pilot stage.

This Design Guide is not intended to be project specific. While it does contain the majority of spaces that now are required in Research Laboratory, it is not possible to encompass all possible future requirements. Therefore, it is recommended that the project specific space

program be the starting point for an individual project design. In addition, it is important to note that the guide plates are a generic graphic representation only. Equipment manufacturers should be consulted for actual dimensions and utility requirements. Use of the Design Guide does not diminish the project Architects' and Engineers' responsibilities to develop a complete and accurate design that meets the user's needs and appropriate code requirements.

2.3.1 Space

This section deals with the spaces used for research or teaching activities with a technical or scientific function, in which there is a potential risk or hazard to users are described as 'Laboratories'. Non-hazardous spaces often called 'Dry Laboratories', which may include computer facilities and language laboratories are not covered in this section.

Laboratories may be required in areas such as Biosciences, Medical Research, Physics, or Chemistry and may include teaching, research, quality control, testing or analysis. These activities may require the usage of chemicals, including dangerous goods, hazardous substances, electrical or radiation hazards, pathogens, quarantine materials or work processes which could also be hazardous.

Special Hazard Laboratories are areas within laboratories (or whole laboratories) in which particularly hazardous substances are used or specific hazardous processes are required which necessitate the requirement to conform with specific standards and legislation in their design and operation. The standards relating to these special hazard laboratories will be over and above the regulatory requirements which are listed in the following section. These special hazard laboratories may include microbiological laboratories, vivaria, cytotoxic chemical preparation rooms, clean rooms and radiological laboratories to cite examples (National Research Council: Division of Building Research, 1966).

The designated laboratory area should include, or have access to, all support spaces required, such as; instrument and preparation labs, laboratory stores, sample stores, chemical stores,

wash up, media prep, sterilization facilities, waste storage and waste treatment facilities. Administration and office accommodation should not be within the laboratory boundary but should ideally be in close physical proximity to the laboratories they serve. Write-up areas are permitted within the laboratory boundary however, these should be separated from areas where hazardous materials are stored or processes undertaken and should only be used on a temporary basis to support the scientific activities (James Cook University Australia., 2016).

2.3.2 Health

The laboratory environment can be a hazardous place to work. Laboratory workers are exposed to numerous potential hazards including chemical, biological, physical and radioactive hazards, as well as musculoskeletal stresses. Laboratory safety is governed by numerous local, state and federal regulations. Over the years, Operational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) has promulgated rules and published guidance to make laboratories increasingly safe for personnel.

The document is intended for supervisors, principal investigators and managers who have the primary responsibility for maintaining laboratories under their supervision as safe, healthy places to work and for ensuring that applicable health, safety and environmental regulations are followed.

Section 5(a)(1) of the Occupational Safety and Health Act of 1970 (OSH Act), the General Duty Clause, requires that employers “shall furnish to each of his employees’ employment and a place of employment which are free from recognized hazards that are causing or likely to cause death or serious physical harm to his employees.” Therefore, even if an OSHA standard has not been promulgated that deals with a specific hazard or hazardous operation, protection of workers from all hazards or hazardous operations may be enforceable under section 5(a)(1) of the OSH Act. For example, best practices that are issued by non-regulatory organizations such as the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH), the

Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the National Research Council (NRC), and the National Institutes of Health (NIH), can be enforceable under section 5(a)(1). The principal OSHA standards that apply to all nonproduction laboratories are listed below. Although this is not a comprehensive list, it includes standards that cover the major hazards that workers are most likely to encounter in their daily tasks. Employers must be fully aware of these standards and must implement all aspects of the standards that apply to specific laboratory work conditions in their facilities. The Occupational Exposure to Hazardous Chemicals in Laboratories standard (29 CFR 1910.1450), commonly referred to as the Laboratory standard, requires that the employer designate a Chemical Hygiene Officer and have a written Chemical Hygiene Plan (CHP), and actively verify that it remains effective. The CHP must include provisions for worker training, chemical exposure monitoring where appropriate, medical consultation when exposure occurs, criteria for the use of personal protective equipment (PPE) and engineering controls, special precautions for particularly hazardous substances, and a requirement for a Chemical Hygiene Officer responsible for implementation of the CHP. The CHP must be tailored to reflect the specific chemical hazards present in the laboratory where it is to be used. Laboratory personnel must receive training regarding the Laboratory standard, the CHP, and other laboratory safety practices, including exposure detection, physical and health hazards associated with chemicals, and protective measures.

The Hazard Communication standard (29 CFR 1910.1200), sometimes called the HazCom standard, is a set of requirements first issued in 1983 by OSHA. The standard requires evaluating the potential hazards of chemicals, and communicating information concerning those hazards and appropriate protective measures to employees. The standard includes provisions for: developing and maintaining a written hazard communication program for the workplace, including lists of hazardous chemicals present; labeling of containers of chemicals in the workplace, as well as of containers of chemicals being shipped to other workplaces;

preparation and distribution of material safety data sheets (MSDSs) to workers and downstream employers; and development and implementation of worker training programs regarding hazards of chemicals and protective measures. This OSHA standard requires manufacturers and importers of hazardous chemicals to provide material safety data sheets to users of the chemicals describing potential hazards and other information. They must also attach hazard warning labels to containers of the chemicals. Employers must make MSDSs available to workers. They must also train their workers in the hazards caused by the chemicals workers are exposed to and the appropriate protective measures that must be used when handling the chemicals.

The Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) standard (29 CFR 1910.132) requires that employers provide and pay for PPE and ensure that it is used wherever “hazards of processes or environment, chemical hazards, radiological hazards, or mechanical irritants are encountered in a manner capable of causing injury or impairment in the function of any part of the body through absorption, inhalation or physical contact.” [29 CFR 1910.132(a) and 1910.132(h)]. In order to determine whether and what PPE is needed, the employer must “assess the workplace to determine if hazards are present, or are likely to be present, which necessitate the use of [PPE],” 29 CFR 1910.132(d)(1). Based on that assessment, the employer must select appropriate PPE (for example, protection for eyes, face, head, extremities; protective clothing; respiratory protection; shields and barriers) that will protect the affected worker from the hazard, 29 CFR 1910.132 (d)(1)(i), communicate selection decisions to each affected worker, 29 CFR 1910.132 (d)(1)(ii), and select PPE that properly fits each affected employee, 29 CFR 1910.132(d)(1)(iii). Employers must provide training for workers who are required to use PPE that addresses when and what PPE is necessary, how to wear and care for PPE properly, and the limitations of PPE, 29 CFR 1910.132(f). The Eye and Face Protection standard (29 CFR 1910.133) requires employers to ensure that each affected worker uses appropriate eye or face protection when exposed to eye or face hazards from flying particles,

molten metal, liquid chemicals, acids or caustic liquids, chemical gases or vapors, or potentially injurious light radiation, 29 CFR 1910.133(a).

The Respiratory Protection standard (29 CFR 1910.134) requires that a respirator be provided to each worker when such equipment is necessary to protect the health of such individual. The employer must provide respirators that are appropriate and suitable for the purpose intended, as described in 29 CFR 1910.134(d)(1). The employer is responsible for establishing and maintaining a respiratory protection program, as required by 29 CFR 1910.134(c), that includes, but is not limited to, the following: selection of respirators for use in the workplace; medical evaluations of workers required to use respirators; fit testing for tight-fitting respirators; proper use of respirators during routine and emergency situations; procedures and schedules for cleaning, disinfecting, storing, inspecting, repairing and discarding of respirators; procedures to ensure adequate air quality, quantity, and flow of breathing air for atmosphere-supplying respirators; training of workers in respiratory hazards that they may be exposed to during routine and emergency situations; training of workers in the proper donning and doffing of respirators, and any limitations on their use and maintenance; and regular evaluation of the effectiveness of the program. The Hand Protection standard (29 CFR 1910.138), requires employers to select and ensure that workers use appropriate hand protection when their hands are exposed to hazards such as those from skin absorption of harmful substances; severe cuts or lacerations; severe abrasions; punctures; chemical burns; thermal burns; and harmful temperature extremes, 29 CFR 1910.138(a). Further, employers must base the selection of the appropriate hand protection on an evaluation of the performance characteristics of the hand protection relative to the task(s) to be performed, conditions present, duration of use, and the hazards and potential hazards identified, 29 CFR 1910.138(b). The Control of Hazardous Energy standard (29 CFR 1910.147), often called the “Lockout/Tagout” standard, establishes basic requirements for locking and/or tagging out equipment while installation, maintenance, testing, repair, or construction operations are in

progress. The primary purpose of the standard is to protect workers from the unexpected energization or startup of machines or equipment, or release of stored energy. The procedures apply to the shutdown of all potential energy sources associated with machines or equipment, including pressures, flows of fluids and gases, electrical power, and radiation.

In addition to the standards listed above, other Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) standards that pertain to electrical safety (29 CFR 1910 Subpart S-Electrical); fire safety (Portable Fire Extinguishers standard, 29 CFR 1910.157); and slips, trips and falls (29 CFR 1910 Subpart D – Walking-Working Surfaces, Subpart E - Means of Egress, and Subpart J - General Environmental Controls) are discussed at pages 25- 28. These standards pertain to general industry, as well as laboratories. When laboratory workers are using large analyzers and other equipment, their potential exposure to electrical hazards associated with this equipment must be assessed by employers and appropriate precautions taken. Similarly, worker exposure to wet floors or spills and clutter can lead to slips/trips/falls and other possible injuries and employers must assure that these hazards are minimized. While large laboratory fires are rare, there is the potential for small bench-top fires, especially in laboratories using flammable solvents. It is the responsibility of employers to implement appropriate protective measures to assure the safety of workers (Occupational Safety and Health Act of 1970, 2018).

2.3.3 Acoustics

Understanding basic acoustic space design criteria and strategies that building managers, users, planners, and designers can use to recognize and address the acoustic needs of laboratory spaces is deeply important for collaboration and efficiency in laboratories.

The expectations for the acoustical performance of research laboratories have changed since many of the design standards were created. Older standards were based on assumptions about laboratory use and noise that may no longer be appropriate.

When planning a laboratory space, it is important to clearly state the expected functions of the space and the required acoustical properties; this allows the Heating, Ventilation, and Air-conditioning (HVAC) design professionals to accommodate the acoustic needs.

The following four considerations are critical in laboratory noise control:

1. Understand the communication needs of the space.
2. Reference the appropriate acoustic metrics for the design and intended use.
3. Contain equipment and utility noise.
4. Integrate energy efficiency and acoustics in the HVAC design.

2.3.3. a Communication needs of the space

Research teams need spaces where people can easily communicate detailed information that may affect their safety and the accuracy of the research data. Scientists and laboratory technicians on a single team commonly speak a variety of native languages, with English as a second language. They must be able to communicate in the laboratory environment without confusion or fatigue. Collaboration is one of the keys to research advances, and noise should not prevent easy communication in a laboratory. If scientists have to move to another space to have an effective conversation, the opportunities for conversations that move the science forward are reduced.

In research laboratory, the current level of collaboration, team communication, and cell phone conversation requires a reevaluation of the acoustic requirements.

2.3.3. b Appropriate acoustic metrics for the design and intended use

The most common measures of background noise are decibel A-weighting (dBA)—a measure of sound that de-emphasizes the very low and very high frequency components of the sound in a manner similar to the frequency response of the human ear—and (Noise Criteria) NC—an index of sound pressure levels based on equal loudness curves. The dBA measurement is approximately equivalent to an NC rating of +5, so, for example, a dBA measurement of 35

would roughly correspond to an NC rating of 30. Readers consider laboratory acoustical design criteria based on a more current understanding of the verbal communication and collaboration that occurs in most laboratories.

During the programming phase for a research laboratory facility, the acoustic design criteria are established with reference to the dBA or NC standards noted above to provide a space that works well for its intended use. Mechanical engineers, architects, and acoustical consultants then work together to provide systems that meet the established criteria.

The established acoustic design criterion for a classroom is typically NC 25 to 35, and the criterion for a research laboratory is NC 45 to 55, yet the functions are not very different.

2.3.3.c Equipment and utility noise

Sources of noise that must be managed include the supply air system, supply valves, and general and fume hood exhaust ducts. Equipment such as vacuum pumps, chillers, and other noisy process equipment should be housed either in a lab cabinet lined with acoustical material or in another room away from the open work environment.

Noise-producing refrigerators, freezers, incubators, centrifuges, and environmental chambers should be kept in equipment rooms or alcoves when possible. Computer server racks and their associated cooling systems should also be in enclosed spaces.

High-bay labs, robotics labs, and various types of engineering labs are often designed without ceilings to afford greater overhead clearance and flexibility to accommodate unique structure-mounted apparatuses. In spaces without acoustical ceilings, more attention must be given to additional sound reduction. Placing supply terminal units in acoustical containers or outside the lab above a corridor ceiling helps. Supply air valves for hoods will need additional sound attenuators in a ceiling-free room.

Duct noise due to excessive supply air velocity is another culprit. Maintaining a design airflow rate of 300 to 500 feet per minute (fpm) at a terminal unit is good practice to minimize

unnecessary noise due to air velocity. Individual terminal units for private offices and multiple smaller terminal units in larger spaces will help keep the airflow velocity within the appropriate range for an acoustically comfortable work environment. When possible, low-flow/high-performance hoods with lower-containment airflow velocities of 60 to 80 fpm can help reduce noise when the sash is open. Radiused and/or tapered exhaust transitions and multiple exhaust outlets for hoods more than six feet wide will also help reduce noise generated by the hoods.

Air handlers can be an additional source of unwanted noise. Fan array technology that includes multiple smaller fans inside the air handler unit instead of a single, large fan helps reduce low-frequency noise and provides greater flexibility to serve changing/dynamic loads.

Supply and exhaust ductwork for labs cannot include internal acoustical lining. However, insulated, nonmetallic flexible duct often can reduce noise at the final run to a ceiling diffuser or can be used for the first few feet of a small general exhaust duct. Axial-type exhaust fans characteristically generate the least low-frequency noise of any of the fan types, given good aerodynamic flow conditions.

2.3.3. d Energy efficiency and acoustics in the HVAC design

Chilled beams and Venturi wedges are becoming more prevalent in laboratories with equipment-driven cooling loads and lower air-change rates. When radiant ceilings or chilled beams are used in an open office environment, they temper noise levels in the space with much less airflow than a typical Variable Air Volume (VAV) system. Because of the higher chilled water temperature and elimination of the reheat typical for a VAV system, the chilled beam system is much more energy efficient. It is not unusual for a radiant ceiling or chilled beam system to have a background noise level of NC 20. Some believe this is a problem insofar as it limits speech privacy. Others suggest it contributes to a sense of community and collaboration.

The trend toward lower air-change rates in laboratories helps to reduce energy use and improve overall acoustical quality in lab spaces. Systems that monitor lab air quality and deliver fresh air on an as-needed basis also help to reduce air noise and energy use.

Perhaps one day it will be common to consider the acoustical properties of a laboratory as part of the typical building commissioning process. Until then, designers, planners, and building managers need to bear in mind the four considerations discussed herein when planning laboratories of all types. A consensus approach to reducing laboratory noise will lead to greater assurance that the desired acoustical performance will be achieved (McNay, 2011).

2.3.4 Lighting

The goal of any laboratory planner is to make laboratories as safe, functional and comfortable as possible. And one of the larger issues in regards to researchers' comfort is lighting. However, not only is lighting a comfort issue in laboratories, but it's also a sustainability issue.

Today, energy codes and energy-efficiency programs, such as Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design (LEED), are driving laboratory planners and architects to pursue energy-conscious design. And while Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems consume about 70% of a laboratory's energy, electrical and lighting loads consume around 30%.

2.3.4. a Laboratory lighting/fixture trends

Light-Emitting Diode (LED) lighting has increased in usage over the past three years for both overhead and task lighting, as labs are becoming more humanistic. And, although LED lighting is more expensive than a T5 fluorescent fixture, the long-term cost savings due to the LED's efficiency outweighs the initial first costs.

Technical advances in LED technology and their fixtures have opened new lab applications. Color rendering of the technology has improved over the past three years. And with more lighting vendors providing viable options, LED technologies have become more competitive. As part of an overall trend toward energy use reduction in labs, LED fixtures help reduce the lighting power density (LPD) and direct electricity use for lighting, but also help reduce heat rejection from lighting sources indirectly assisting the cooling demand reduction. These technology advances also contribute to the growing trend in task/ambient lighting strategies. Small LED task lighting has become a significant factor in providing user-controlled lighting at the bench, while allowing for lower general lighting.

LED technology emits visible light in a narrow spectral band, and can produce “white light” through a red-blue-green array or phosphor-coated blue LED lamp. The benefits of the technology include: compact size, long life, ease of maintenance, resistance to breakage and vibration and lack of infrared or ultraviolet emissions, as well as the ability to be dimmed and

Figure 2. 9: A prototypical lighting design was incorporated which featured a custom designed LED task light which is integral to the top shelf of the casework. Each bench had its own task light with a motion sensor maximizing the potential for energy savings. *Source: <https://www.labdesignnews.com/article/2015/06/lighting-path-efficient-lab-design>. Downloaded on 5th of June, 2018 at exactly 3:08am.*

to provide color control. The lamps usually last 40,000 to 100,000 hours, depending on color and can currently achieve efficiencies of 80 mean lumens per Watt (LPW) or higher.

However, in terms of LPW, or the measure of light source efficacy, traditional fluorescent lamp and ballast design is not behind us. By pairing energy-saving fluorescent lamps with extra high-efficiency electronic program-start ballasts, efficacies as high as 95 to 110 mean LPW can be achieved.

Applying high-efficiency linear fluorescent technologies helps reduce the LPD throughout entire lab spaces, cutting the total connected electric lighting load. These high-efficiency technologies also increase lamp life from 20,000 hours to 36,000 hours, reducing replacement and disposal costs.

2.3.4. b Task/Ambient approach

Gone are the days of 100 foot-candles (fc) at the bench level throughout laboratories. These days were driven by the bad color quality of previous fluorescent lamp lighting available. However, through the years, the quality of fluorescent lamps and LEDs have improved. With this, most researchers are satisfied with around 50 to 65 fc at the bench.

Task/ambient lighting solutions are now commonplace in laboratories, and are typically carried out in laboratories that require different lighting requirements. However, many laboratories still have higher than needed levels of ambient lighting. And, at times, these ambient light sources aren't integrated with daylighting via full-range automatic dimming.

To increase building performance and sustainability, high-efficiency electric lighting with low power density (or Watts per square foot) provides modest amounts of ambient lighting. In conjunction with well-designed task lighting, this can reduce LPD below code allowance. The allowance for laboratories is currently 1.4 W/sf according to IESNA Standard 90.1 (the energy code referenced by LEED). Other technologies and techniques, such as LED lamps, linear

fluorescent T5 lamps, chilled beam-integrated luminaires, universal dimmers and daylighting can get LPD at or below 1.0 W/sf.

Glare control is critical for effective daylighting. There are many strategies available for solar control, each requiring attention to detail and particular attention to control systems. Today, many motorized shade manufacturers offer sophisticated control systems that combine predictive algorithms for the position of the sun in the sky and the effect of adjoining buildings and terrain with active adaptation to actual sun and sky conditions.

One of the easiest ways to properly implement a daylighting strategy is to specify a photosensor directly into laboratory lighting fixtures. One sensor can be daisy chained to other ballasts in the same zone through low-voltage wiring.

A second option is to provide a photosensor that's connected to a lighting control system and then programming which zones of luminaires to dim (Hock, 2015).

2.3.4. c Understanding occupancy

The greatest potential for lighting energy savings is to turn off the lights completely when not needed. Occupancy sensors are now mandated by energy code in most laboratories. These sensors serve three basic functions: automatically turn lights on when a laboratory becomes occupied; keep the lights on without interruption while the laboratory is occupied; and turn the lights off within a preset time period after the laboratory is vacated. Overall, the use of occupancy sensors within a laboratory setting can reduce lighting energy by 10 to 30%, if they are implemented correctly. Payback on the technology can be seen one to two years after implementation.

Two popular technologies are currently used for occupancy sensors: passive infrared (PIR) and ultrasonic. PIR sensors are triggered by the movement of a heat-emitting body through their field of view. PIR sensors can't see through opaque walls or partitions and can't see around corners. Occupants must be in direct line-of-site of the sensor for optimal use. Ultrasonic

sensors, on the other hand, emit an inaudible sound pattern that's disrupted by any moving object altering the signal returning to the sensor (Doppler principle). These sensors are suited for spaces where line-of-sight view to the occupant isn't always available, as the sensor detects even minor motion better than PIR sensors.

These controls can be used in conjunction with dimming or daylight controls to keep the lights in a lab from turning off completely when unoccupied, or to keep the lights off when daylight is plentiful and the lab is occupied (Hock, 2015).

2.3.5 Circulation

Arrangement of fixed and movable furnishings needs to allow teachers and students to circulate easily through the space. Good circulation makes for a safer and more accessible laboratory.

All laboratories should have two doors leading to a corridor or other egress; this does not include doors to prep rooms or other support spaces. The doors should not be crowded next to laboratory stations, which could hinder a quick exit.

Care should be taken not to nest rooms inside one another: no one should have to travel through more than one adjoining space to get to an egress corridor.

Within the laboratory space, schematic design layouts should show all seating, even movable chairs, so the circulation space can be evaluated. There should be a minimum of 1 meter clear around three sides of the perimeter of the seating area, and 1.5 meters around the fourth side.

Consider the movement of equipment and materials in laying out spaces. Users should be able to move from one activity to another with accompanying materials. The location of preparation and storage rooms should consider both access and security.

Public institutions must provide access for users with disabilities to all research/educational programs in the least restrictive manner. They also may not discriminate against individuals with disabilities in matters of employment and public services. Consequently, research/science facilities must be fully accessible to students, teachers, and public users.

Minimum scope and technical requirements are identified in Americans with Disabilities Act Accessibility Guidelines (ADAAG). In addition to those guidelines, the following should be considered when designing for accessibility:

1. In order to integrate accessible laboratory stations fully into the classroom, design them to be part of the laboratory configuration as a whole, rather than isolating these stations away from the predominant student groupings. Integrating accessible features into the prototypical laboratory station and allowing students with disabilities to fully participate in group activities is advisable. Since both accessibility and computer use at the laboratory station require lower work station-height than a traditional 914mm high work surface, variations in counter height will be the norm anyway.
2. The clearances between fixed equipment must meet circulation and access requirements. Movable equipment can be effectively used and easily shifted to meet individual needs.
3. Standard furniture and equipment often has to be modified to meet the needs of a particular individual. Wood furniture is desirable because it is more easily modified than metal or plastic.
4. Adjustable seat, table and display surface heights are desirable.
5. Handrails or handgrips may be of assistance to some individuals at work surfaces or when using tools.

6. Custom made shop coats or aprons for individuals with adaptive or assistive devices should be considered.
7. Emergency eyewashes and showers, if required for the program, should be accessible to persons with disabilities (School Improvement in Maryland, 2016).

2.3.6 Building Materials

As global populations increase, so too will the need for accommodation. However, current mainstream building methods are unsustainable, producing large amounts of CO² both during construction and throughout a building's life. Thankfully, sustainability is becoming a priority for developers, and with many exciting innovations happening in the construction industry, sustainably addressing global accommodation needs seems possible.

These five materials, apart from conventional materials, will surely improve sustainability of this scheme:

1. Wool Bricks:

Developed by Spanish and Scottish researchers with an aim to obtain a composite that was more sustainable, non-toxic, using abundant local materials that would mechanically improve the bricks' strength', these wool bricks are exactly what the name suggests. Simply by adding wool and a natural polymer found in seaweed to the clay of the brick, the brick is 37% stronger than other bricks, and more resistant to the cold wet climate often found in Britain. They also dry hard, reducing the embodied energy as they don't need to be fired like traditional bricks.

2. Solar Tiles:

Traditional roof tiles are either mined from the ground or set from concrete or clay - all energy intensive methods. Once installed, they exist to simply protect a building from the elements despite the fact that they spend a large portion of the day absorbing energy from

the sun. With this in mind, many companies are now developing solar tiles. Unlike most solar units which are fixed on top of existing roofing, solar tiles are fully integrated into the building, protecting it from the weather and generating power for use by the facility.

3. Sustainable Concrete:

Whilst 95% of a building's CO² emissions are a result of the energy consumed during its life, there is much that can be done to reduce that 5% associated with construction. Concrete is an ideal place to start, partly because almost every building uses it, but mostly due to the fact that concrete is responsible for a staggering 7-10% of global CO² emissions. More sustainable forms of concrete exist that use recycled materials in the mix. Crushed glass can be added, as can wood chips or slag - a byproduct of steel manufacturing. Whilst these changes aren't radically transforming concrete, by simply using a material that would have otherwise gone to waste, the CO² emissions associated with concrete are reduced.

4. Paper Insulation:

Made from recycled newspapers and cardboard, paper-based insulation is a superior alternative to chemical foams. Both insect resistant and fire-retardant thanks to the inclusion of borax, boric acid, and calcium carbonate (all completely natural materials that have no associations with health problems), paper insulation can be blown into cavity walls, filling every crack and creating an almost draft-free space.

5. Triple-Glazed Windows:

In fact, super-efficient windows would better describe this particular building material. The three layers of glass do a better job of stopping heat from leaving the building, with fully insulated window frames further contributing. In most double-glazed windows, the gas argon is injected between each layer of glass to aid insulation, but in these super-efficient windows, krypton - a better, but more expensive insulator - is used. In addition

to this, low-emissivity coatings are applied to the glass, further preventing heat from escaping.

A building that combined all five of these methods would be an admirably sustainable option for housing. Whilst the construction industry tends to progress at a slow pace, the importance of sustainability is a high profile issue, and one which is only likely to increase. With sustainable building materials already fully developed, it is now up to consumers to actively demand their use and building developers to respond promptly (Peach, 2018).

2.3.6. a Finishes

Code requirements shall be met with regard to selected finishes; Factors which may be applicable include slip resistance, ease of cleaning (smoothness, sealed joints, provision of coves, avoidance of construction joints), resistance to chemicals and / or cleaning / decontamination agents, flammability. Impervious materials shall be used on walls, floors and benches.

In wet laboratories where there is the potential for water spills and flooding, the optimal flood containment and minimal risk of leakage to lower floors is required. Appropriate detailing and construction sequence of these spaces is vital.

2.3.6. b Floors

Generally sheet vinyl is to be used as floor finishes in laboratories unless specifically required for other purpose (such as epoxy coated floors for hose down areas). Thick rubber flooring may also be considered appropriate if available. Electrical exclusion zones, including at safety shower and eyewash locations, should be marked in contrasting colors on floor.

2.3.6. c Walls

Generally painted (heavy duty, washable acrylic) plasterboard is suitable unless other requirements for impervious finish, washability and airtightness are paramount. E.g. clean rooms, animal holding facilities, surgical areas etc. In such cases sandwich paneling, sheet vinyl or epoxy coatings may be required.

2.3.6. d Ceilings

Vinyl faced removable ceiling tiles are appropriate for use in laboratories unless special requirements for containment are an issue. Ceilings may be omitted in some situations, however accumulation of dust on exposed surfaces must be addressed. Provide color coded identification tags on suspended ceilings to locate access points to service pipes.

2.3.6. e Color Selection

Color selection within the laboratories shall generally be neutral. Feature colors shall be used on paintable surfaces only, and not for example in joinery finishes such as laminates. Color selection shall also take into account the anticipated laboratory activities, including risks of staining, scratching and burning and the texture / pattern of the material.

2.3.7 Materials Testing

All selected finishes and colors to be used within the laboratory environment on floors, bench tops, fume cupboard work surfaces, shelving and splashbacks shall be fully evaluated by the users with respect to their performance and suitability with all specific types and concentrations of chemicals which are likely to be encountered in each laboratory. This will enable the final selections of color and material type to be determined. A test of how each material performs with respect to its chemical and stain resistance shall be performed over a period of up to 24 hours. The primary purpose of this is to assess the chemical resistance to staining and damage of the proposed finishes against the specific chemicals that will be used

in the particular spaces in question. While the proposed finishes should be selected for their known general high level of chemical resistance, particular chemicals can have different effects on otherwise seemingly similar finishes and colors.

For each finish type and color, material samples from 4 sets of alternative suppliers should be distributed to the user groups of each building / laboratory. Provide plans showing allocation of finishes types to the various spaces, to assist in deciding which chemicals need to be tested on which finishes. The codes for each finish should also be marked on the matching samples for ease of identification. User groups should undertake testing along the following lines:

1. Users should set up a grid on each of the samples, and record the chemicals on a matching grid drawn up on a sheet of paper.
2. Testing for all chemicals for periods of time similar to how long a spill might be left for, but also up to 24 hours to simulate repeated staining over time (James Cook University Australia., 2016).

2.4 APPLICABLE STRUCTURAL CONSIDERATIONS

The structural grid for a laboratory is ideally determined by the internal space planning module, which can typically lead to grids of 6.8meters - 7.2meters. This is influenced by the type of research, space sharing and safety criteria, all of which are translated into the depth of benching, equipment and circulation space. Offices, however, might work to a different planning module for efficiency of design, such as 1.5 meters.

Thus, if the most efficient grid for both the laboratory and office components of the building is maintained this results in complexities in the design and construction of the frame and cladding.

Alternatively, a consistent structural grid can be adopted throughout the building with internal planning of the laboratories and offices being adjusted to a potentially less efficient layout.

2.4.1 Structural Systems

Once the basic lab module is determined, the structural grid should be evaluated. In most cases, the structural grid equals 2 basic lab modules. If the typical module is 10 ft. 6 in. x 30

ft., the structural grid would be 21 ft. x 30 ft. A good rule of thumb is to add the two dimensions of the structural grid; if the sum equals a number in the low 50's, then the structural grid would be efficient and cost-effective.

Figure 2. 10: Typical lab structural grid of a research laboratory.

Source: <https://www.wbdg.org/building-types/research-facilities/research-laboratory>.
Downloaded on 4th of June, 2018 at exactly 11:57am.

Key design issues to consider in evaluating a structural system

include:

1. Framing depth and effect on floor-to-floor height;
2. Ability to coordinate framing with lab modules;
3. Ability to create penetrations for lab services in the initial design as well as over the life of the building;
4. Potential for vertical or horizontal expansion;
5. Vibration criteria, and
6. Cost.

2.4.2 Storey heights

Laboratory storey heights would typically be 4.5 meters -5 meters, compared with a typical office of 3.5 meters -4 meters. This can result in the whole building being constructed to the

greater storey height, which increases costs of frame, cladding and vertical services distribution.

Alternatively, the laboratory and office components of the building may be separated and constructed to their own standards, depending upon the site and footprint opportunities.

2.4.3 Internal and External Loading Considerations

Loads are a primary consideration in any building design because they define the nature and magnitude of hazards or external forces that a building must resist to provide reasonable performance (i.e., safety and serviceability) throughout the structure's useful life. The anticipated loads are influenced by a building's intended use (occupancy and function), configuration (size and shape), and location (climate and site conditions). Ultimately, the type and magnitude of design loads affect critical decisions such as material selection, construction details, and architectural configuration. Thus, to optimize the value (i.e., performance versus economy) of the finished product, it is essential to apply design loads realistically.

2.4.3. a Wind Loads:

Wind produces non-static loads on a structure at highly variable magnitudes. The variation in pressures at different locations on a building is complex to the point that pressures may become too analytically intensive for precise consideration in design. Therefore, wind load specifications attempt to simplify the design problem by considering basic static pressure zones on a building representative of peak loads that are likely to be experienced. The peak pressures in one zone for a given wind direction may not, however, occur simultaneously with peak pressures in other zones. For some pressure zones, the peak pressure depends on a narrow range of wind direction. Therefore, the wind directionality effect must also be factored into determining risk-consistent wind loads on buildings. In fact, most modern wind load specifications take account of wind directionality and other effects in determining nominal design loads in some simplified form (SBCCI, 1999; ASCE, 1999). This further simplifies

wind load design specifications to provide an easy yet effective approach for designing typical residential buildings. Because they vary substantially over the surface of a building, wind loads are considered at two different scales.

On a large scale, the loads produced on the overall building, or on major structural systems that sustain wind loads from more than one surface of the building, are considered the Main Wind Force-Resisting System (MWFRS). The MWFRS of a public building includes the shear walls and diaphragms that create the lateral force-resisting system (LFRS) as well as the structural systems such as trusses that experience loads from two surfaces (or pressure regimes) of the building. The wind loads applied to the MWFRS account for the large-area averaging effects of time-varying wind pressures on the surface or surfaces of the building.

On a smaller scale, pressures are somewhat greater on localized surface areas of the building, particularly near abrupt changes in building geometry (e.g., eaves, ridges, and corners). These higher wind pressures occur on smaller areas, particularly affecting the loads borne by components and cladding (e.g., sheathing, windows, doors, purlins, studs). The components and cladding (C&C) transfer localized time-varying loads to the MWFRS, at which point the loads average out both spatially and temporally since, at a given time, some components may be at near peak loads while others are at substantially less than peak (Department of Housing and Urban Development, 2015).

2.4.3. b Dead Loads:

Dead loads consist of the permanent construction material loads comprising the roof, floor, wall, and foundation systems, including claddings, finishes, and fixed equipment. The values for dead loads in Table 2.1 are for commonly used materials and constructions of public buildings. Table 3.3 provides values for common material densities and may be useful in calculating dead loads more accurately.

Table 2. 1: Dead Loads for Common Public Buildings Construction

Roof Construction			
Light-frame wood roof with wood structural panel sheathing and 1/2-inch gypsum board ceiling (2 psf) with asphalt shingle roofing (3 psf)		15 psf	
- with conventional clay/tile roofing		27 psf	
- with light-weight tile		21 psf	
- with metal roofing		14 psf	
- with wood shakes		15 psf	
- with tar and gravel		18 psf	
Floor Construction			
Light-frame 2x12 wood floor with 3/4-inch wood structural panel sheathing and 1/2-inch gypsum board ceiling (without 1/2-inch gypsum board, subtract 2 psf from all values) with carpet, vinyl, or similar floor covering		10 psf ^a	
- with wood flooring		12 psf	
- with ceramic tile		15 psf	
- with slate		19 psf	
Wall Construction			
Light-frame 2x4 wood wall with 1/2-inch wood structural panel sheathing and 1/2-inch gypsum board finish (for 2x6, add 1 psf to all values)		6 psf	
- with vinyl or aluminum siding		7 psf	
- with lap wood siding		8 psf	
- with 7/8-inch portland cement stucco siding		15 psf	
- with thin-coat-stucco on insulation board		9 psf	
- with 3-1/2-inch brick veneer		45 psf	
Interior partition walls (2x4 with 1/2-inch gypsum board applied to both sides)		6 psf	
Foundation Construction			
	Masonry ^b	Concrete	
	Hollow	Solid or Full Grout	
6-inch-thick wall	28 psf	60 psf	75 psf
8-inch-thick wall	36 psf	80 psf	100 psf
10-inch-thick wall	44 psf	100 psf	123 psf
12-inch-thick wall	50 psf	125 psf	145 psf
6-inch x 12-inch concrete footing			73 plf
6-inch x 16-inch concrete footing			97 plf
8-inch x 24-inch concrete footing			193 plf

Source: Residential Structural Design Guide. Downloaded on 5th of June, 2018 at exactly 11:20am

2.4.3. c Live Loads

Live loads are produced by the use and occupancy of a building. Loads include those from human occupants, furnishings, non-fixed equipment, storage, and construction and maintenance activities. Table 2.2 provides recommended design live loads for residential buildings. As required to adequately define the loading condition, loads are presented in terms of uniform area loads (psf), concentrated loads (lbs), and uniform line loads (plf). The uniform and concentrated live loads should not be applied simultaneously in a structural evaluation. Concentrated loads should be applied to a small area or surface consistent with the application and should be located or directed to give the maximum load effect possible in end-use

Table 2. 2: Live Loads for Common Public Buildings Construction

Application	Uniform Load	Concentrated Load
Roof ²		
Slope ≥ 4:12	15 psf	250 lbs
Flat to 4:12 slope	20 psf	250 lbs
Attic ³		
With limited storage	10 psf	250 lbs
With storage	20 psf	250 lbs
Floors		
Bedroom areas ^{3,4}	30 psf	300 lbs
Other areas	40 psf	300 lbs
Garages	50 psf	2,000 lbs (vans, light trucks) 1,500 lbs (passenger cars)
Decks	40 psf	300 lbs
Balconies	60 psf	300 lbs
Stairs	40 psf	300 lbs
Guards and handrails	20 plf	200 lbs
Grab bars	N/A	250 lbs

Source: Residential Structural Design Guide. Downloaded on 5th of June, 2018 at exactly 11:32am conditions. For example, the stair concentrated load of 136 kilograms (300 pounds) should be applied to the center of the stair tread between supports. The concentrated wheel load of a vehicle on a garage slab or floor should be applied to all areas or members subject to a wheel or jack load, typically using a loaded area of about 0.0129032 square meters (20 square inches).

2.4.4 Support Systems (Floor and Roof support systems)

2.4.4. a Floor support systems

Precast concrete double tee joists are one of the most popular precast concrete floor framing systems. However, compared with open steel joists, standard concrete joists are heavy and do not allow mechanical and electrical equipment (i.e., HVAC systems, electrical wiring, plumbing, and the like) to pass through them. Placing web openings in these joists to allow equipment to pass through them is a significant improvement, reducing the floor-to-floor height and overall building height.

This reduced building height can result in significant economy in the cost of the building and in the mechanical and electrical systems installed therein. A further benefit of using joists with web openings is weight reduction. This weight reduction also results in reduced vertical gravity loads and horizontal seismic forces in the supporting beams, columns, and foundation. The inventors contend that their new method is not only superior to steel in many respects, including corrosion resistance, but also easy to produce. The precast, pre-stressed concrete joist has integral web openings through which mechanical and electrical equipment may pass. The joist consists of two horizontal concrete members; the top member is in compression, the bottom in tension. The horizontal members connect via two vertical concrete members, creating two horizontal, prismatic segments and a web design for equipment installation.

The top surface of the joist has a flat upper face to support concrete slab flooring. Shear keys and U-shaped ties are cast into the top member to secure concrete flooring. The walls which may be precast or cast-in-place concrete, have indentations or notches to mate with the joists supporting the floor, ceiling, or roof. The joist may have prestressing strand throughout its horizontal members for reinforcement. Additionally, steel reinforcement bars may extend vertically from the top member through the web and into the bottom member to provide added strength. Preferably, the legs of the U-shaped ties extend into the top member of the joist along

either side of the pre-stressing strands. The whole assembly locks together, making the floor less subject to vibrations typical of steel construction buildings (Hanley-Wood, LLC, 2000).

2.4.4. b Roof Support Systems

The term roof system refers to the air barrier or vapor retarder (if present), roof insulation (if present), and the roof membrane, flashing, and accessories. The following roof systems were considered to be employed in the scheme.

1. Low-slope Roof Coverings (slope less than or equal to 3:12);
2. Built-up Roofs (BUR);
3. Mesh Reinforced Elastomeric Coatings (MREC);
4. Modified Bitumen (MB) which include, Atactic Polypropylene (APP), Styrene-Butadiene-Styrene (SBS) and Styrene-Ethylene-Styrene (SEBS);
5. Single-ply roof systems;
6. Thermoplastic Single-Plies which include Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC), Thermoplastic Polyolefin (TPO) and Ketone Ethylene Ester (KEE);
7. Thermoset Single-Plies which include Ethylene Polypropylene Diene Monomer (EPDM), Sprayed Polyurethane Foam (SPF), Metal Panels and Hot and Cold fluid-applied roofing membranes and
8. Steep-slope Roof Coverings (slope greater than 3:12) include Metal Panels/Shingles, Asphalt, Wood/Synthetic Shingles, Wood Shakes and Clay/Concrete Tiles.

2.4.4. c Roof Decks

Commercial and institutional buildings typically have steel or concrete roof decks, although plywood or Oriented Strand Board (OSB) decks are also used on smaller buildings. The deck can have significant influence on the roof system.

Of the deck types used today, steel is the most common. Although prime-painted steel decks with welded connections are commonly specified, it is recommended that galvanized decks

be specified in order to obtain greater corrosion protection in the event of roof leakage. It is also recommended that screw, pneumatic, or powder actuated-attachment be specified in lieu of welding, because screws provide more reliable attachment.

2.4.4. d Air barriers

If the roof membrane is monolithic (i.e., a membrane roof) it serves as an air retarder. However, separate air barriers are sometimes incorporated into roof systems. When air barriers are incorporated into wall systems, they are normally included to control air movement, control moisture and/or reduce energy consumption, or to prevent pumping due to wind, which can cause uplift with mechanically fastened membranes. When an air barrier other than the roof membrane is incorporated into a roof system, it is normally included to address wind performance issues or to address a building code requirement. To reduce the potential of interior air being pumped into the roofing system an air barrier should be located at the roof deck level under the roof insulation, sealing all roof deck voids.

The deck itself can be a barrier if it is monolithic, such as cast-in-place concrete. When the deck is used as an air barrier, deck penetrations such as plumbing vents should be sealed, and the deck should be sealed at parapets. However, a separate sheet material such as 6-mil polyethylene, approved house-wrap, a two-ply built-up membrane or a one-ply modified bitumen sheet is typically used to create an air barrier. Membranes used as air barriers, must be made airtight at all penetrations.

2.4.4. e Vapour Retarders

Vapour retarders are materials with a perm rating of 0.1 or less and are typically sheet materials such as 6-mil polyethylene, a two-ply built-up membrane or a one-ply modified bitumen sheet. House-wrap should not be used for a vapor retarder because it has inadequate vapor flow resistance.

The presence of a vapor retarder can make it difficult to find leaks, as they can carry water great distances from the source of the leak. However, as discussed above under Roof Decks, vapor retarders must be used on all new concrete decks and on steel decks wherever there is a high humidity occupancy below, especially in cold climates. To be effective, vapor retarders must be airtight at all penetrations. Vapor retarders may also be required to prevent condensation under white or light-colored membranes (cool roofs) in cold climates because the temperatures of such membranes may be so low that even occupancies with low or average interior humidity can cause condensation in such circumstances.

As noted above, if the deck is a new concrete deck, a vapor retarder must be provided on top of the deck, to keep moisture inherent in new concrete decks from migrating into the roof system. This is true, regardless of the building occupancy's interior relative humidity.

2.4.4. f Insulation

There are three categories of roof insulation: rigid board, non-rigid (batt, blanket, or loose fiber) and sprayed polyurethane foam. Rigid boards are typically used in low-slope assemblies. They may be polyisocyanurate (most common), extruded polystyrene, or mineral wool. Non-rigid insulations are typically used in attic spaces and in pre-engineered buildings. See the section on Sprayed Polyurethane Foam for more information on this type.

2.4.4. g Cover Boards

A cover board is a thin layer of insulation (such as perlite or wood fiberboard or dense polyisocyanurate) or glass mat gypsum roof board, preferably pre-primed. Plywood and oriented strand board are occasionally used if required for high-wind speed uplift warranties. Cover boards should be placed over the primary thermal insulation (typically one of the plastic foam insulations) in order to provide enhanced physical characteristics, such as improved fire and compressive resistance, prevention of delamination of facers due to traffic on the roof,

provision of improved wind uplift resistance, and to avoid blistering or avoid a compatibility problem.

Cover boards are also commonly used in re-covering to improve the application surface; to cover joints between insulation boards; and to provide a separation layer between the existing and new roof membranes. When used in this application they are often referred-to as "recovery board."

Cover boards in commercial construction are typically glass mat gypsum roof board (preferably pre-primed) or perlite. Some materials used for cover boards are sometimes specified for use as an underlayment board directly over steel roof decks in order to provide a thermal barrier to provide fire protection between steel decks and certain types of plastic foam insulation (the IBC specifies thermal barrier requirements) or to provide a smooth surface for a vapor retarder. Note that perlite will absorb water more readily than glass mat gypsum board; this may be a consideration if there is a leak.

2.4.4. h Rigid Insulation Boards

Rigid, or Board-stock insulation, typically has sufficient compressive strength to support the roof membrane and the loads placed upon it. In addition to supporting the roof membrane, rigid insulation can provide other functions for the roof system such as a uniform surface for membrane application and improved hail resistance. Rigid insulation is commonly used to achieve slope in low-slope applications where the deck does not provide the necessary slope. Tapered insulation typically provides 0.00635 meter (1/4") to 0.0127meter (1/2") of slope. Insulation should typically be applied in two layers with offset joints to minimize thermal bridging.

The following common types of rigid insulation boards are available:

Perlite: This is an open-cell low R-value insulation that is commonly used as a cover board. It has good fire resistance, but when exposed to water, it loses compressive resistance, turns

to mush, and can be easily compressed. 0.0127meter thick boards have a greater percentage of organic material content than do 0.01905meter (3/4") or thicker boards. Hence, when hot asphalt is applied over 0.0127meter (1/2") boards, the potential for the development of blisters in built-up and hot-applied modified bitumen membranes is increased. For these reasons, perlite is generally not recommended.

Polyisocyanurate: There have historically been issues with aging of polyisocyanurate affecting R-value. Nevertheless, polyisocyanurate is a high R-value insulation (R-5.6 per inch thickness in cooling conditions and R-5.0 per inch thickness in heating conditions using NRCA's "in-service" recommendation, or approximately R-5.7 for 0.0254meter (one-inch) thickness using the Long-Term Thermal Resistance (LTTR) method for determining resistance).

Polyisocyanurate is one of the plastic foam insulations. It is widely used in low-slope roof systems. Polyisocyanurate insulation is inherently more fire-resistant than polystyrene insulation. It always comes with facers, which are thin sheets on both faces of the insulation, because facers are necessary in the production process. Note that the foam insulation can compress and facers can delaminate when subjected to heavy traffic, therefore a cover board is always recommended. Also, facers act as vapor retarders, which may or may not be desirable.

Consider using the 25 psi product instead of the standard 20 psi. If subjected to a leak condition, polyisocyanurate will absorb moisture, lose its insulating value, and will have to be replaced in correction, unlike polystyrene, which can often be reused. Although more fire-resistant than polystyrene, it should be verified with the manufacturer if a thermal barrier is required. Polyisocyanurate is less expensive than extruded polystyrene.

Polystyrene: There are two types of polystyrene insulation: expanded polystyrene (sometimes referred to as EPS or bead-board) and extruded polystyrene (sometimes referred to as XPS). The two types have distinctly different properties. Polystyrene is one of the plastic

foam insulations and should be used with caution where hot roofing materials are employed. The International Building Code requires a fire separation layer called a "thermal barrier" with polystyrene insulation used over a steel deck. This is usually a 0.0127meter (1/2") sheet of gypsum directly above the deck.

Polystyrene boards should not be in direct contact with PVC membranes, otherwise the polystyrene will leach plasticizers out of the PVC. A suitable separator needs to occur between polystyrene and PVC.

Expanded Polystyrene (EPS): EPS is sometimes referred to as "molded expanded polystyrene" or "bead-board." This is moderate R-value insulation (from slightly less to slightly more than R-4 per inch, depending upon density). The low-density product is relatively inexpensive. Solvent-based adhesive and hot asphalt disintegrate EPS. Hence, if either of these is used, a suitable cover board needs to be installed over the EPS. EPS can also be decomposed or melt at high temperatures. Therefore, EPS should not be used underneath a black membrane unless a suitable cover board is installed between the EPS and the membrane. The National Roofing Contractors Association (NRCA) recommends expanded polystyrene insulation intended for use as rigid board roof insulation have a minimum density of a nominal 0.5669905kilogram (1.25 pounds) per cubic foot, that complying with ASTM C578, type VIII, having a minimum density of 0.5216312 kilograms (1.15 pounds) per cubic foot. EPS cells are filled with air. Therefore, unlike the other plastic foam insulations, EPS does not thermally age (i.e., loose R-value over time). EPS is not very resistant to water vapor; when exposed to water vapor drive, EPS can absorb a considerable amount of moisture.

Extruded Polystyrene (XPS, sometimes EXPS or XEPS): This is a high R-value insulation (R-5 per inch for products with a minimum compressive resistance of 25 psi, R-4.6 per inch for products with a minimum compressive resistance of 15 psi). Generally, products with an

R-value of 5.0 per inch thickness are used in roof applications. Some manufacturers offer XPS made from recycled XPS.

A cover board is usually required with XPS, to provide a surface to adhere the

membrane (XPS is not available with facers).

Figure 2. 11: Protected Membrane Roof (PMR) has two layers of Extruded Polystyrene (XPS). The top board has a factory-applied mortar surface.

Source: <https://www.wbdg.org/guides-specifications/building-envelope-design-guide/roofing-systems>. Downloaded on 5th June, 2017 at exactly 12:29pm.

XPS is very resistant to water vapor drive.

However, as with EPS, XPS should not be

exposed to solvent, hot asphalt, or very high

temperature. But unlike EPS, in order to

avoid membrane splitting, XPS should not be used below a built-up or modified bitumen membrane (even if a cover board is installed over the XPS).

XPS is the only insulation suitable for use above the roof membrane in protected membrane roof (PMR) systems (see section on this topic). However, boards intended for PMRs need to be specifically manufactured for this application. Some minor water absorption may occur in boards located above the membrane during the roof's service life. To account for the R-value reduction due to the water absorption, it is recommended that the roof designer reduce the board's initial R-value by 10%.

XPS can often be re-used when re-roofing, because it does not absorb water when there are the inevitable leaks, distinguishing it from the more commonly used polyisocyanurate insulation. That, combined with the required use of a cover board with XPS, which increases

durability, is why the life-cycle cost of XPS insulation is often better than polyisocyanurate insulation.

XPS boards with extremely high compressive resistance are available for use in plaza decks where high compressive loads occur. 40 psi is recommended for light pedestrian loads, 60 psi is recommended for heavy pedestrian loads with light vehicular traffic, 100 psi is recommended for heavy vehicular traffic.

Mineral wool: R-4 (approximate) is not seen very often in low slope roofs, except as a replacement for fiberglass insulation between roof rafters in residential construction. Cover board or a rigid upper layer is required that is integral with the mineral wool (or sheathing in residential construction).

Composite boards: Composite boards typically consist of two layers of different types of insulation that are laminated together in a factory. The primary insulation is typically polyisocyanurate or EPS. The secondary layer is typically perlite, wood fiberboard, Oriented Strand Board (OSB), plywood, or gypsum board. Composite boards made with OSB or plywood are commonly referred to as "nail base." Some nail base products have a small ventilation cavity between the primary insulation and the OSB or plywood. OSB and fiberboard composites are not recommended, as they do not withstand incidental wetting.

A nail-base insulation product should be checked to make sure it possesses adequate compressive strength and shear strength to withstand the loads expected for the roof system. For vented nail-base insulation, the product should be checked to make sure the spacer material and distance between spacer blocks provides adequate compressive strength, and the bearing surface of spacers provides adequate shear strength.

With some composite boards, the secondary layer (which is typically the top surface) is superficially adhered to the primary layer. With these boards, it is important to mechanically attach the composite board rather than adhere it. Otherwise the secondary layer could easily detach. The designer should understand that joints between the boards and the fasteners will

represent a path for thermal bridging, therefore composite insulation is recommended to be installed over an underlying layer of non-composite insulation. The top layer composite insulation may be used in lieu of a separate insulation cover board.

For all types of insulation, is recommended to use multiple layers, with staggered joints. Joints over 0.003175meter (1/8") wide are usually filled with spray foam insulation, especially if there is only one layer of insulation. Consider using maximum 1.2 meters X 1.2 meters (4 by 4 foot) boards to reduce the gaps caused by shrinkage of the insulation.

2.4.4. i Low-slope roof coverings

The following membranes are typically used on low-slope roofs, but may also be used on steep-slope roofs. When used on steep-slopes, the system's fire resistance may be reduced and/or special precautions may be needed when used on steep-slopes.

2.4.4. j Plaza decks and vegetated roofs

Low slope roofing is sometimes accomplished by using a Plaza Deck or an Extensive Vegetative Roofs.

Figure 2. 12: Bitumen is poured and aggregate surfacing is shoveled onto a built-up roof.

Source: <https://www.wbdg.org/guides-specifications/building-envelope-design-guide/roofing-systems>. Downloaded on 5th June, 2017 at exactly 12:40pm.

2.4.4. k Built-up Roofs (BUR)

Built-up roof membranes are composed of alternating layers of bitumen (either asphalt or rarely coal tar) and reinforcement sheets (felts). Fiberglass felts are typically used for asphalt BURs. Historically, ply sheets have been either fiberglass-mat or organic-mat reinforced. Currently organic-mat reinforced ply sheets have largely disappeared from the United States of America market. The asphalt is typically hot applied, however, cold-applied asphalt is available (cold-applied asphalt incorporates solvent). The membrane is either adhered to the substrate in bitumen or a base sheet (i.e., a heavy felt) is mechanically attached.

When a BUR is installed over polyisocyanurate, a suitable cover board should be installed over the polyisocyanurate. Four plies of felt are recommended (if a nailed base sheet is installed, four plies are recommended in addition to the base sheet). "Heavy duty" fiberglass felts are available (ASTM E2178 Type VI), but because of their stiffness, it is easier to construct unwanted voids in the membrane. Therefore, Type IV felts are recommended. Polyisocyanurate is by far the most common insulation used under built-up roof assemblies. Occasionally, mineral wool will be used.

The bitumen provides the waterproofing characteristics; the felts provide improvements to physical characteristics. Complete and full embedment of the felts into the bitumen is crucial. Exposed asphalt is susceptible to ultra-violet degradation. Therefore, BURs are surfaced with aggregate, a field-applied coating or a mineral surface cap sheet. If aggregate is specified, wind blow-off should be considered. Coatings include aluminum-pigmented asphalt, asphalt emulsion (reflective or non-reflective), urethane, and acrylic. Coatings can enhance fire resistance. However, if coatings are specified, periodic recoating will be required. Because of future maintenance demands, coatings are not recommended. If a cap sheet is specified, it should be in addition to the 4 plies of felt.

Asphalt tends to get brittle with age, making it unable to accommodate normal building movements. And, application of hot asphalt requires open flames and working with extremely

hot liquids. Some clients and designers do not use BUR roofs to avoid these safety issues. Fumes are particularly noxious to many people and should be avoided on occupied buildings. ASTM standard D312 is the product standard for asphalt used in roofing. There are four types of asphalt. Type I is much more susceptible to flow than Type IV. ASTM D6510 provides guidance for selection of asphalt Type in BURs. Caution should be used when heating asphalt to prevent changing its physical properties and thereby making it unsuitable for roofing. Base flashings of BURs are typically constructed with modified bitumen sheets (National Institute of Building Sciences, 2017).

2.5 BUILDING SERVICES RELEVANT TO THE BUILDING TYPE

Building services are the systems installed in buildings to make them comfortable, functional, efficient and safe.

2.5.1 Fire

Most fire detection and alarm systems operate on the same basic principles. If a fire is detected, then an alarm is triggered. This warns building managers and occupants that there may be a fire and that evacuation may be necessary. Some systems include remote **signaling** equipment which can alert the fire brigade or a remote monitoring **center**.

Fire can be detected by; heat detectors, flame detectors, smoke detectors, carbon monoxide detectors and multi sensor detectors, or an alarm can be triggered at manual call points. Alarms may consist of bells, sirens, horns, lights or a combination these. Two power supplies are required, generally a mains supply and batteries providing 24 hours back up.

It is important that a thorough assessment of need is undertaken before a fire detection and alarm system is designed or purchased.

Fire alarm systems are categorized as:

1. L, (L1 to L5): automatic systems intended for the protection of life;
2. M: manual systems, fitted with sounders and call points and
3. P, (P1 and P2): automatic systems intended for the protection of property.

Fire detection and alarm systems can be divided into a number of general types:

1. Conventional systems;
2. Addressable systems;
3. Analogue addressable systems;
4. Wireless systems and
5. Self-contained units.

Conventional systems generally consist of a series of detectors and call points wired to a control panel which drives the detectors and a minimum of two sounder circuits, includes LED indicators and allows de-activation and resetting. Typically, separate circuits will be provided for each fire 'zone' (usually a floor of a building or a fire compartment). This separation into zones means that the approximate location of the fire is known and so the appropriate response can be instigated. It also allows for easier diagnosis of faults.

Addressable systems are similar to conventional systems, but the central control panel can identify exactly which detector or call point triggered the alarm (rather than just a zone), or whether communication has been lost with a detector. In this system the circuit is wired in a loop, with a number of detectors or call points on each loop. The loop can be powered from both ends, so that it continues to function even if there is a break in the loop (separate loops may still be provided for each zone).

The control panel can be programmed to show specific information, or trigger specific responses for different detectors within the system. Addressable systems are generally used

for larger or more complex installations because of the benefits of more accurate detection, and so fault finding, and the reduced wiring requirement.

Analogue addressable systems, or intelligent systems can include an analytical capability in each detector which can assess local parameters to determine whether there is a fire, a fault or a maintenance requirement. This can be useful in preventing the occurrence of false alarms. A pre-alarm warning may be indicated if a detector is approaching a trigger condition.

Wireless fire alarm systems connect detectors and call-points to the control panel using wireless signals.

Self-contained fire alarm units are generally only suitable for small installations. They consist of a single unit, including break glass contact, sounder, power supply, battery and charger.

It is important that fire alarm and detection systems are regularly inspected, serviced and tested, and fire drills may be held to ensure occupants are familiar with fire and evacuation procedures (Designing Buildings Wiki, 2018).

2.5.2 Water Supply

Water supply is the provision of water by utilities organizations, typically using a pump and pipe system.

Typically, the first stage of the water supply process is the collection of rainwater in reservoirs, either from rivers or streams or from groundwater. This is pumped to water treatment works where it undergoes a number of processes, the first of which is screening which ensures the removal of large elements such as branches and vegetation. Following this, flocculation takes place – the adding of a solution which makes particles larger and easier to remove. Additional filters are subsequently used, such as:

1. Rapid gravity filter: Water is passed through a tank of coarse sand which traps particles and
2. Slow sand filter: Water is slowly filtered through large beds of fine sand.

Testing of the water's purity is carried out several times before a tiny amount (less than one milligram per liter) of chlorine is added to kill any organisms or bacteria which may remain.

Once treatment is complete, the water is stored in covered reservoirs before being pumped out via a distribution network of pipes and pumping stations making sure that the pH (Designing Buildings Wiki, 2018).

2.5.3 Heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC)

'HVAC' refers to Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning, which can be used in buildings to:

1. Maintain internal air quality;
2. Regulate internal temperatures and
3. Regulate internal humidity.

It is sometimes extended to include refrigeration (HVACR).

Internal air quality can be maintained by a combination of introducing 'fresh' air into the building, extracting 'stale air' and by filtration. Ventilation may be natural, mechanical, or mixed mode (a hybrid system). See Ventilation for more information.

Internal temperatures can be regulated by heating and cooling. Typically this is achieved by heated water (or sometimes steam) and chilled water that is generated by boilers and chiller-
sand then used in heating coils and cooling coils as part of the ventilation system. Alternatively, hot water may be used to supply radiators.

Humidity can be regulated by ventilation, dehumidification and humidification. Dehumidification is often provided alongside cooling as cooling air reduces the amount of moisture it is able to 'hold', resulting in condensation and so dehumidification. 'Close' humidity control (to within 10%) can involve cooling and dehumidification, then re-heating and re-humidification.

Refrigeration as 'the process of removing heat' and heat rejection as 'the discharge of heat to waste or atmosphere or to a system permitting reclaim or recovery' (Designing Buildings Wiki, 2018).

Very broadly, HVAC systems can be centralized in a building, or local to the space they are serving, or a combination of both (for example, local air handling units supplied by centrally-generated cooling). They may also be connected to a wider district heating or cooling network.

They may be integrated, with heating, ventilation and air conditioning provided by a single system, for example, air handling units connected to ductwork, or they may be a combination of separate systems, for example mechanical ventilation but with radiators for heating and local comfort cooling units.

They may also include passive or 'natural' systems such as natural ventilation.

In mechanically ventilated commercial developments HVAC is often provided by air handling units connected to ductwork that supplies air to and extracts air from internal spaces. Air handling units typically comprise an insulated box that might include some, or all of the following components; filter racks or chambers, a fan (or blower), heating elements, cooling elements, dehumidification, sound attenuators and dampers. Air handling units that consist of only a fan and a heating or cooling element,

located within the space they are serving, may be referred to as fan coil units (FCU). See Air handling units for more information.

HVAC can consume large amounts of energy, and where possible, demand should be reduced and passive systems adopted.

Extracting internal air and replacing it with outside air can increase the need for heating and cooling. This can be reduced by re-circulating a proportion of internal air, or by heat recovery ventilation (HRV) that recovers heat from extract air and to pre-heat incoming fresh air.

It is important that HVAC systems are considered together during the design process, even where they consist of independent systems. This is because of the interaction between heating, cooling, humidity control and ventilation. This is particularly complicated when other elements of environmental behavior are considered such as solar gain, natural ventilation, thermal mass, and so on.

The design of HVAC systems is generally a specialist task, undertaken by a building services engineer, and because of its interaction with other elements of the building it is important that it is considered from the outset, as a fundamental part of the design process, and not an 'add on' at the end.

HVAC may be controlled by a building management system to maximize occupant comfort and minimize energy consumption.

Regular inspection and maintenance is necessary to ensure that systems are operating optimally (Designing Buildings Wiki, 2018).

2.5.4 Sanitation

Every public building shall be provided with adequate sanitary toilet facilities for each of the sexes; and such facilities shall be convenient and accessible. Every public building which must provide adequate sanitary toilet facilities shall provide at least one free sanitary toilet facility for each of the sexes. Where toilet facilities are voluntarily provided by any store, market, supermarket, or other commercial establishment for use by customers of such establishment or the general public, there shall be at least one free sanitary toilet facility provided for each of the sexes. *One sanitary toilet and four (4) urinals should be provided for 5.0 male persons while one (1) sanitary toilet and eight (8) bidets must be provided for 2.5 female persons* (Cubicle center, 2018). It shall be the duty of the owner, manager, or other responsible person in charge to see that the toilet system is properly installed and maintained in a usable and sanitary condition at all times.

The method of sewage disposal for all public buildings shall comply with the rules and regulations of the state board of health.

All public buildings shall be kept at all times in a clean and sanitary condition and the cleaning shall be carried on under proper sanitary conditions. All rooms used for public meetings shall be cleaned after each meeting held in them, such cleaning to consist of thorough sweeping of the floors and wiping of the woodwork, together with proper airing of the rooms. No room shall be swept without the use of a proper dust-laying substance. Dry dusting is prohibited. In construing this regulation all meetings held during the course of a single day shall be regarded as one meeting (Washington State Legislature, 2003).

2.5.5 Lifts

A lift (or elevator) is a form of vertical transportation between building floors, levels or decks, commonly used in offices, public buildings and other types of multi-storey building. Lifts can be essential for providing vertical circulation, particularly in tall buildings,

for wheelchair and other non-ambulant building users and for the vertical transportation of goods. Some lifts may also be used for firefighting and evacuation purposes.

Lift installation and manufacture must comply with the Lifts Regulations 1997, as amended by the UK Supply of Machinery (Safety) Regulations 2008. Lifts that travel faster than 0.15 metre per second, and their safety components which permanently serve buildings and constructions, must be safe for use and meet health and safety requirements.

Safety components include:

1. Landing doors locking device;
2. Devices to prevent the lift falling or rising unchecked;
3. Devices to limit over-speed;
4. Energy-accumulating buffers;
5. Energy-dissipating buffers;
6. Safety devices fitted to jacks of hydraulic power circuits used to prevent falls and
7. Safety switches containing electronic components.

The Lifting Operations and Lifting Equipment Regulations (LOLER) provide guidance on lifts used by workers in workplaces. It requires lifts to be thoroughly examined by a competent person at least every six months or, in the case of goods-only lifts, every 12 months. Guidance for lift owners and other duty-holders is available in the HSE's 'Thorough examination and testing of lifts'.

BS EN 81-80 relates to the upgrading of existing lifts, to ensure they are safe for use. The aim is to meet the level of safety provided by a newly-installed lift.

2.6 STANDARD SPACES COMMON TO BUILDING TYPE

The theories and concepts as discussed in 2.8 above is used as benchmark in developing the architectural implication of the intended design. This is not really the design concept but it can serve as a take-off spring board in conceiving and developing the scheme.

There will be 5 major zones in the scheme. They are:

2.6.1 The Non-Laboratory Section

This will house most of the offices and administrative units including the Chief Executive Officer/Director General's Office, Executive Chambers, Archives, Conference Room, Open/General Offices, Board Room, Seminar rooms, Presentation Rooms, Lecture Halls, Equipment Room, Directors' Offices, Faculty Associates' Offices, Program Coordinators Offices, Rehearsal Rooms, Program Managers' Offices, Carbon Materials Office, Administrative Support Associate I Office, Principal Research Scientists' Offices, Assistant Director for Facilities and Operations Office, Communications Officer's office, Assistant Director for External Affairs and Development's Office, Program Administrator's Office, Multimedia Specialist's Office, GIS Coordinator's Office, Research Scientist Associates' Offices, Cost Engineering Scheduler's Office, and Research Engineer Seniors' Offices.

2.6.2 First Generation Biofuel Wing

This wing will house non-laboratory zones and laboratory zones. The laboratory zones will house fermentation and saccharification laboratories that conduct research into effective ways of producing bioethanol and transesterification laboratories that will

Figure 2. 13: Production process of denatured bio-butanol

Source:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/neuroscience/butanol>. Downloaded on 25th of March, 2018 at 7:27am.

handle all research into the production of bio-butanol.

This wing will be retrofitted with modular vivaria and orchards where crops to be used as feedstock will be cultivate.

2.6.3 Second Generation Biofuel Wing

This wing will house non-laboratory zones and laboratory zones. The laboratory zones will house lignocellulosic laboratories that conduct research into effective ways of producing methanol and anaerobic digestion laboratories that will handle all research into the production of biogas with appropriate digesters of minimum capacity.

This wing will be conjoined to dump sites where municipal wastes, animal residues and plant lignin will be stock-piled and used as feedstock for the digesters.

Figure 2. 14: Production process of biogas.

Source: https://www.americanbiogascouncil.org/biogas_what.asp. Downloaded on 25th of March, 2018 at 7:37am.

2.6.4 Third Generation Biofuel Wing

This wing will house non-laboratory zones and laboratory zones. The laboratory zones will house photo-bioreactor laboratories that conduct research into effective ways of producing non-degradable jet fuel and cell-disruption laboratories that will handle all research into the production of bioethanol.

This wing will be retrofitted with modular algae-cellular ponds and where microalgae are cultivated to be used as feedstock for the production of test samples of biofuel.

Figure 2. 15: Production process of bioethanol with algae.

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/. /260411416_An_overview_of_algae_bioethanol_prod. Downloaded on 26th of March, 2018 at 7:47am.

2.6.5 Fourth Generation Biofuel Wing

This wing will house non-laboratory zones and laboratory zones. The laboratory zones will house pre-combustion laboratories that conduct research

into effective ways of producing carbon-negative biogas and genetic-modification laboratories that will handle all research into the production of carbon-negative and 98 percent clean bio-butanol.

This wing will be retrofitted with vivaria where genetically modified crops are cultivated to be used as feedstock. There will also be geosequestration

Figure 2. 16: Production process of bio-methane and bio-hydrogen as fourth generation biofuels.

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/. /260411416_An_o_verview_of_algae_bioethanol_prod. Downloaded on 26th of March, 2018 at 8:23am.

stations where biogas is stored in underground reinforced concrete vats which will be in contact with the site's unmineable coal seams. These products will be kept there for long periods of time in order to make the biofuel carbon-negative. This will reduce, to infinitesimal levels, the pollutant effects of the products. Unmineable coal seams have been found to be present in Naze Industrial Clusters and this particular factor is one of the reasons why the site was chosen.

2.6.6 Architectural Implications

Shown below in Figure 2.17 are is the researcher's synergized criteria on the scheme as extrapolated from the discussed theories and concepts on Research/Laboratory schemes. This is not the design concept but it can serve as a veritable take-off platform to effectively consummate the design.

Figure 2. 17: Architectural implication of theories and concepts of related building type.

Source: Author's studio work as retrieved on 26th of March, 2018 at 8:23am.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

Research in common parlance refers to a search for knowledge. One can also define research as a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. In fact, research is an art of scientific investigation. The Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English describes research as "a careful investigation or inquiry especially through search for new facts in any branch of knowledge" (Hornby, 1968). Research can also be said to be a "systematized effort to gain new knowledge." Some people consider research as a movement, a movement from the known to the unknown. It is actually a voyage of discovery. We all possess the vital instinct of inquisitiveness for, when the unknown confronts us, we wonder and our inquisitiveness makes us probe and attain full and fuller understanding of the unknown. This inquisitiveness is the mother of all knowledge and the method, which man employs for obtaining the knowledge of whatever is the unknown, can be termed as research. Research is an academic activity and as such the term should be used in a technical sense. Research is, thus, an original contribution to the existing stock of knowledge making for its advancement. It is the pursuit of truth with the help of study, observation, comparison and experiment. In short, the search for knowledge through objective and systematic method of finding solution to a problem is research. The systematic approach concerning generalization and the formulation of a theory is also research. As such the term 'research' refers to the systematic method consisting of enunciating the problem, formulating a hypothesis, collecting the facts or data, analyzing the facts and reaching certain conclusions either in the form of solutions(s) towards the concerned problem or in certain generalizations for some theoretical formulation.

3.2 Research Design

The research design refers to the overall strategy that you choose to integrate the different components of the study in a coherent and logical way, thereby, ensuring you will effectively address the research problem; it constitutes the blueprint for the collection, measurement, and analysis of data. The research design method employed is descriptive. It is focused on Imo State as the base of study. For purposes of the research, data was obtained from primary and secondary sources using, personal interviews, physical observations and case studies.

3.3 Data

1. *Primary data*: These include all information extrapolated from six case studies conducted. They were organized to have in a glance the name of the facility visited, its brief history, the location with accompanying location maps, the year of commissioning of the facility, the objectives of the facility, features of the facility, the merits and demerits observed which are subjective. Interviews with relevant authorities/personnel and field observation also served to constitute the primary data. Others include pictures taken by the researcher, drawings/sketches and observations.

2. *Secondary data*: These included such information from books, journals and web sites that are relevant to the biofuel industry.

3.4 Method of data collection

Generally, data used in this research were collected through the following sources:

3.4.1. Oral Interviews:

This involves personal interview of all persons of relevance to the project based on their level of exposure to facilities of related scope and specification.

3.4.2. Internet Research:

This is another viable source used by the researcher to gather relevant information as several e-books were surfed via the internet for this research.

3.4.3. Review of existing publications:

A lot of information were obtained through effective use of the library materials including publications, journals, books, magazines, periodicals, related reports and gazetted documents on biofuels and biomass.

3.4.4. Case studies:

Case studies are a form of qualitative descriptive research that are used to look at individuals, a small group of participants, or a group as a whole. Researchers collect data about participants using participant and direct observations, interviews, protocols, tests, examinations of records, and collections of writing samples. Well documented case studies look at applications and methods including data collection and analysis. Ways to handle validity, reliability and generalizability are all geared towards ensuring that they remain viable to data analysis and result validity.

Here the researcher makes an intensive study of a unit or project to be investigated. It is the most preferred approach used in architectural projects since it gives room for proper assessment of existing but related schemes. Case studies conducted in this project include:

Table 3. 1: Analysis of case study types and their numbers

S/N	TYPE OF CASE STUDY	NUMBER	DESCRIPTION
1	Foreign case studies	4	These are related schemes located outside the boundaries of Nigeria.
2	Local case studies	2	These are related schemes located within the boundaries of Nigeria.

Source: Author submissions as at 12th day of March, 2018

3.5 Purpose of a case study

- ≠ The purpose of a case study is to provide a more thorough analysis of a situation or “case” which will reveal interesting information to the reader.
- ≠ Information generated and deduced from case studies help the researcher in making informed decisions towards achieving a unique design that offers solution to the problem statement.

Case studies were carried out in different institutes and treatment/biorefineries which include four (4) foreign and two (2) local case studies.

3.6 Case Study 1 (Foreign Case Study)

Riley-Robb Hall Biofuels Research Laboratory, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York, United States of America.

3.6.1 Brief History

The Riley Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory was the first campus renovation project to earn LEED Certification, and earned an innovation credit for utilizing Cradle to Cradle (C2C) certified materials. In addition to the building's green features, Riley Robb Hall is where much of Cornell's research into renewable energy solutions take place. The Riley Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory was established as a multidisciplinary and integrative research development laboratory where basic and applied researchers come together to cultivate scientific and technical solutions to biofuel and bio-product development. Bio-based industrial ecologies, such as biorefineries, must integrate a spectrum of biological and physical/chemical processes to develop desired products. Successful integration of technology into these industrial ecologies hinges on understanding how material, energy and monetary flows from one process influence the behavior of the next process, and any subsequent feedback loops. A quick review of what is involved in using plant-based resources to produce fuels, chemicals and materials would reveal complex and highly integrative activities/processes needed to yield the principal product and by-products.

3.6.2 Location

232 Riley-Robb Hall, Biological and Environmental Engineering Department, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York 14853, Ithaca, Latitude 42.446135 degrees East and Longitude-76.471536 degrees West, United State of America.

3.6.3 Year built

The Riley Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory was founded and built in 2008.

Figure 3. 1: Site Location of Riley-Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory at 232 Riley-Robb Hall, Biological and Environmental Engineering Department, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York 14853, Ithaca, Latitude 42.446135 degrees East and Longitude -76.471536 degrees West.

Source: http://events.cornell.edu/riley-robb_hall. Downloaded and re-drafted on 18th March, 2018 at 2:23pm.

3.6.4 Objectives of the Institute

The Riley Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory has the following objectives:

1. To examine industrial biotechnology solutions to agricultural, energy and environmental challenges.
2. To overcome the physical, chemical and biological barriers to liberating sugars from energy crops and converting them into biofuels including ethanol, biodiesel or hydrogen.

3.6.5 Features of the facility

- a. Bio-conversion processes laboratories
- b. Feedstock development laboratories
- c. Systems analysis units

Figure 3. 2: Ground Floor Plan of Riley-Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory at 232 Riley-Robb Hall, Biological and Environmental Engineering Department, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York 14853, Ithaca, Latitude 42.446135 degrees East and Longitude-76.471536 degrees West.

Source: http://events.cornell.edu/riley-robb_hall. Downloaded and re-draughted on 19th March, 2018 at 3:20pm. Scale: 1:250.

- d. Economics, environment and policy units
- e. Biomass separation laboratories
- f. Temperature-phased Anaerobic Digestion Process units
- g. Alternative Pretreatment Strategy units

Figure 3. 4: First Floor Plan of Riley-Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory at 232 Riley-Robb Hall, Biological and Environmental Engineering Department, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York 14853, Ithaca, Latitude 42.446135 degrees East and Longitude-76.471536 degrees West.

Source: http://events.cornell.edu/riley-robb_hall. Downloaded and re-draughted on 19th March, 2018 at 5:10pm.

Figure 3. 3: Three-dimensional view of Riley-Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory.

Source: http://events.cornell.edu/riley-robb_hall. Downloaded on 18th March, 2018 at 2:22pm.

Figure 3. 5: Location map of Riley-Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory at 232 Riley-Robb Hall, Biological and Environmental Engineering Department, Cornell University, Ithaca, New York 14853, Ithaca, Latitude 42.446135 degrees East and Longitude -76.471536 degrees West.

Source: http://events.cornell.edu/riley-robb_hall. Downloaded on 18th March, 2018 at 2:23pm.

- h. Enhanced Microbial Cellulose Degradation Laboratories
- i. Small Farm Integrated green houses
- j. Personal protective equipment stores
- k. Server/Network (Enterprise) rooms
- l. Material Handling Laboratories

3.6.6 Merits

- a. Multi-level laboratories
- b. Spacious 1,000 capacity seminar hall

Figure 3. 6: Instructional seminar halls of Riley-Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory.
Source: http://events.cornell.edu/riley-robb_hall. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:24pm.

- c. Sufficient parking lots.
- d. Wet-laboratories are zoned in to the rear of the facility.
- e. Clearance space for vertical-output machines is precise and efficient in the laboratories.
- f. Single corridor laboratory design with office clusters accessing main laboratories directly.

Figure 3. 7: Parking spaces for vehicles at Riley-Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory.
Source: http://events.cornell.edu/riley-robb_hall. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:25pm.

3.6.7 Demerits

1. Improper zoning of the mobile dump trailers. As seen on the site layout, the dump site, mostly non-degradable waste is an eyesore to the immediate environment of the facility.
2. Research and Development Centre has extensive plain glazing which pre-exposes the space to glare effect. This is evident of the fact that there are no shading devices in contact/close proximity to the space.

3. Wet laboratories are separated from the main facility by vehicular traffic. This minimizes the relationship between the dry laboratories and the wet laboratories.

Figure 3. 8: Sectional view of the multi-level laboratories at Riley-Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory.

Source: http://events.cornell.edu/riley-robb_hall. Downloaded on 21/03/2018 at 2:33pm.

4. Vehicular traffic within the site is not very coordinated as there are several points of egress and ingress.

5. Flat roof system, as adopted in most of the roof configuration, may allow solar insolation into the confines of the offices and storage spaces at the ground floor.

3.7 Case Study 2 (Foreign Case Study)

The European Bioenergy Research Institute, Aston Triangle, Birmingham B4 7ET, United Kingdom

3.7.1 Brief History

EBRI is an EU Centre of Excellence in applied bioenergy technology. It is a focus for pan-European activities on scientific and technological aspects of bioenergy production, conversion and utilization of waste products for renewable power, heat, transport fuels, hydrogen and chemicals.

Figure 3. 9: Site layout of European Bioenergy Research Institute, Aston Triangle, United Kingdom on latitude 52.487833 degrees East and longitude-1.888234 degrees West.

Source: Author's re-drafted sketch on 30th of May, 2018 at exactly 6:00pm.

EBRI performs research and knowledge transfer in all aspects of bioenergy. The EBRI building on the Aston University campus in Birmingham is a demonstrator of these technologies; its own bioenergy technologies provide the heat, electricity and cooling needed to power the building. EBRI provides collaboration opportunities for businesses to run trials and tests, evaluate waste sources and study combinations of bioenergy processes prior to investment.

The European Bioenergy Research Institute acts as a focus for worldwide activities on scientific and technological aspects of biomass production, conversion and utilization of products for renewable power, heat, transport fuels, hydrogen and chemicals. EBRI works to extract the maximum value from all types of biomass, including waste resources.

Figure 3. 10: Ground floor plan of European Bioenergy Research Institute, Aston Triangle, United Kingdom on latitude 52.487833 degrees East and longitude-1.888234 degrees West.

Source: Author's re-drafted sketch on 30th of May, 2018 at exactly 6:15pm. Scale 1:250.

3.7.2 Location

Aston University, Aston Triangle, Birmingham B4 7ET, United Kingdom on latitude 52.487833 degrees East and longitude-1.888234 degrees West.

Figure 3. 11: Satellite imagery of European Bioenergy Research Institute, Aston Triangle, United Kingdom on latitude 52.487833 degrees East and longitude-1.888234 degrees West.

Source: <http://www.aston.ac.uk/eas/research/groups/ebri>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:30pm. Scale: 1: 3,500.

3.7.3 Year built

European Bioenergy Research Institute (EBRI) was built and opened in 2013 on the Aston campus in Birmingham city center. The new building was officially opened in October 2013 by the Lord Mayor of Birmingham.

3.7.4 Objectives of the institute

The objectives of the institute, among many others, include:

- 1. *Pyrolysis*** - Research and technology demonstration for innovative pyrolysis processes.
- 2. *Biochar*** - Testing and analysis of biochar for enhancing poor and high-quality soils.
- 3. *Feedstock investigation*** - Testing and analysis of feedstocks for fuel production.
- 4. *Field tests*** - Experiments and testing undertaken by EBRI researchers and technicians.

5. **Combined heat and power (CHP) engines** - Optimizations of CHP engines for bioenergy provision.
6. **Gasification** - Research and technology demonstration for gasification applications.
7. **Green hydrogen production** - Low carbon production of H₂ for applications in the hydrogen economy.
8. **Bioenergy markets** - Optimizing the business strategy for the bioenergy sector.
9. **Algae cultivation** - Exploring the exploitation of microalgae for waste remediation and bioenergy production.

Figure 3. 12: Eyelevel perspective of the European Bioenergy Research Institute facility

Source:

<http://www.aston.ac.uk/eas/research/groups/ebri>.

Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:35pm.

3.7.5 Features of the facility

EBRI has seven laboratories all

multi-tiered including two industrial laboratories to allow EBRI to work with businesses in

order to tackle

industry issues.

Each laboratory is

dedicated to a

different area of

research and

includes: algae,

catalysis, high

Figure 3. 13: Aerial view of the European Bioenergy Research Institute facility

Source:

<http://www.aston.ac.uk/eas/research/groups/ebri>.

Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:38pm.

pressure processing and upgrading of fuels, thermal processing of biomass and waste materials, and the characterization of novel biofuels. These laboratories are available for feedstock, power and equipment tests. Others include: pyroformer intermediate pyrolysis unit; 400

Figure 3. 14: Aerial view of the European Bioenergy Research Institute facility.

Source:

<http://www.aston.ac.uk/eas/research/groups/ebri>.

Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:40pm.

kg/h fluid bed gasifier; 400 kWe CHP engine; a wide range of laboratory scale pyrolysis, gasification and hydrothermal processing reactors; catalyst design, production and characterization, and testing facilities; product upgrading facilities for biofuel production; extensive product analysis and characterization equipment; bio-refinery and biofuel synthesis and evaluation; algae production and biomass pretreatment and characterization; distributed energy technologies and electric vehicle-to-grid charging system.

3.7.6 Merit(s)

1. Spacious seminar room which is occupying a vantage position from the front façade.
2. Wet laboratories are detached from the main facility.
3. Flexible laboratories with mobile casework.

Figure 3. 15: Inside the presentation room

Source:

<http://www.aston.ac.uk/eas/research/groups/ebri>. *Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:42pm.*

4. Dry laboratories are multi-tiered with the Anaerobic Digestion laboratory and Biosynthesis laboratory occupying the ground floor plan.

5. There is a viable office for the Cost Engineering Scheduler. This officer is saddled with the responsibility of procuring plants and machines needed in the laboratories.

3.7.7 Demerit(s)

1. The site is seriously constrained and lies at the nerve center of a busy intersection of the Lister Street and Woodcock Street.

2. Existing circulation pattern makes it easy to access the laboratories. This is not allowed in sensitive facilities like laboratories and research outfits.

3. There is this sudden proximity between the facility and sports. A basketball court is located directly behind the research facility. The location of such sporting area will surely disturb the quiet zoning of laboratories of the research facility.

4. There are no identifiable spaces for technologists.

5. Parking spaces are a bit constrained as vehicles park directly behind each other.

6. The Arrival Architecture generally does not signify a research/laboratory building type. This is so evident as the structure was once a cinema.

3.8 Case Study 3 (Foreign Case Study)

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Denver, United States of America.

3.8.1 Brief History

Established in 1974, National Renewable Energy Laboratory began operating in 1977 as the Solar Energy Research Institute. Under the Jimmy Carter administration, its activities went beyond research and development in solar energy as it tried to popularize knowledge about already existing technologies, like passive solar. During the Ronald Reagan administration, the institute's budget was cut by nearly 90%; many employees were "reduced in force" and the laboratory's activities were reduced to R&D. In later years, renewed interest in the energy problem improved the institute's position, but funding has fluctuated. In 2011, anticipated congressional budget shortfalls led to a voluntary buyout program for 100 to 150

Figure 3. 16: National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 15013 Denver West Parkway, Golden, CO 80401, United States of America on latitude 39.740748 East, longitude:-105.170634 West.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-drafted on 1/06/2018 at 1:47am.

staff reductions. The budget for fiscal 2016 was \$427.4 million, down from a peak of \$536.5 million five years earlier. Changes in the budget have sometimes forced NREL to cut staffing. Since its inception in 1977 as the Solar Energy Research Institute, it has been operated under

Figure 3. 17: National Renewable Energy Laboratory (Bio-renewables), 15013 Denver West Parkway, Golden, CO 80401, United States of America on latitude 39.740748 East, longitude:-105.170634 West.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 1:52am. Scale: 1:3,000.

contract by MRI Global. In September 1991, the NREL was designated a national laboratory of the United States Department of Energy by President George H.W. Bush and its name was changed to NREL. Currently, NREL is managed for the Department of Energy by the Alliance for Sustainable Energy, LLC. The Alliance was formed in 2008 as a joint venture between MRI Global and Battelle. Dr. Martin Keller became NREL's ninth director in November 2015, and currently serves as both the director of the lab and the president of the Alliance. He succeeded Dan Arvizu, who retired in September 2015 after 10 years in those roles.

Figure 3. 18: Ground floor plan of National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 15013 Denver West Parkway, United States of America.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-drafted on 1/06/2018 at 1:57am. Scale: 1: 300.

Figure 3. 19: Aerial view of National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 15013 Denver West Parkway, United States of America.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 1/06/2018 at 2:06am.

3.8.2 Location

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory is located at 15013 Denver West Parkway,

Figure 3. 20: Satellite imagery of National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 15013 Denver West Parkway, Golden, CO 80401, United States of America on latitude 39.740748 East, longitude:-105.170634 West.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:45pm.

Golden, Colorado 80401, United States of America on latitude 39.740748 degrees East and longitude-105.170634 degrees West.

3.8.3 Year built

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory was built and established in 1974 and began operating in 1977 as the Solar Energy Research Institute.

3.8.4 Objectives of the institute

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) advances the science and engineering of energy efficiency, sustainable transportation, and renewable power technologies and

Figure 3. 21: Welcome plaque at National Renewable Energy Laboratory.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:48pm

provides the knowledge to integrate and optimize energy systems. NREL is the only federal laboratory dedicated to the research, development, commercialization, and deployment of renewable energy and energy efficiency technologies.

Figure 3. 22: Solar research laboratory

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:49pm.

The Bioenergy Program supports NREL research and development that focuses on biomass characterization, thermochemical and biochemical biomass conversion technologies, bio-based products development, and biomass process engineering and analysis. NREL also works to develop cost-effective, environmentally friendly biomass conversion technologies to reduce our nation's dependence on foreign oil, improve our air quality, and support rural economies.

Figure 3. 23: Open office work spaces

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 2:54pm.

The Buildings Research Program supports NREL research and development that focuses on improvements in residential buildings, in commercial buildings, in building equipment and

Figure 3. 24: The National Renewable Energy Laboratory.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 3:00pm.

components, building energy analysis tools, manufacturing, and in lighting and appliance standards. NREL is a nationally recognized leader in

energy with innovative technologies to significantly reduce energy consumption in buildings.

3.8.5 Features of the facility

National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)'s 327-acre South Table Mountain campus

Figure 3. 25: The Ethanol production hall

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 3:20pm.

currently includes 17 buildings, which house offices, laboratories, test facilities, and more than 2,447 workers. The vision for the sustainable campus is documented in their master plan and implemented through utilizing high performance

sustainable building requirements. In addition to open office, semi-private and some private

offices, the facility includes a library, data center, employee lunch room, lobby, conference, and support spaces.

3.8.6 Merit(s)

1. All of the buildings are sited with their long axes east-to-west so that they can take

Figure 3. 26: The biochemical conversion laboratory
Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 3:10pm.

advantage of passive solar energy along their long north and south walls.

2. The south-facing windows are all shielded with some sort

of bonnet or giant blinds to bounce the natural light

inside while keeping the summer heat out.

3. There are shaded balconies at the ends of each floor.
4. The roofs were angled up so that heat can rise and escape out the upper windows.

Figure 3. 27: Exquisite open office design spaces
Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 3:25pm.

5. There were also “huddle rooms” for small meetings, phone rooms for private conversations, and quiet rooms for

people to take health-related breaks (such as for migraines) or for nursing mothers to

Figure 3. 28: Perfect harmony with the outdoors
Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 3:30pm.

pump milk.

6. Buildings were planned with expansion in mind so that equipment can be added if new projects are authorized.

7. The whole facility has been

mapped out so that the sites of future buildings have already been designated.

3.8.7 Demerit(s)

1. The Laboratory's small (6,000-square foot) visitor center built and donated by

Figure 3. 29: NREL's South Table Mountain campus in the Denver metropolitan area
Source: *NREL Ten-Year Site Plan FY2007 – FY2018 (December 31, 2006)*. Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 3:40pm.

Midwest Research Institute in 1994, can no longer meet the demand of an increasing numbers of people who want to visit the lab and/or learn about renewable energy.

2. A conference facility would be highly beneficial to NREL's research and to the interests of many energy stakeholders.
3. NREL currently processes its visitors (checks identification, issues badges) in a guardhouse of less than a thousand square feet.

Figure 3. 30: NREL's Grand Build-out Vision for the South Table Mountain Campus – Planned to enhance the interfaces between basic and applied science, and engineering and the marketplace

Source: NREL Ten-Year Site Plan FY2007 – FY2018 (December 31, 2006).

Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 3:50pm

4. The small buildings results in groups of visitors, including high-level executives, foreign energy ministers and delegations, and similar guests, to sometimes by forced to wait outside in bad weather, sometimes for an extended period of time.
5. NREL has a strong education program for K-12, but no onsite classroom space for demonstrating key scientific principles about energy to students, science teachers, and others. This lack of conference and classroom space results in lost opportunities to further science

and technical education for many students, teachers, and school systems interested in renewable energy.

Figure 3. 31: Second floor plan of NREL

Source: NREL Ten-Year Site Plan FY2007 – FY2018 (December 31, 2006). Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 3:55pm. Scale: 1:250.

Figure 3. 32: Integrated Biorefinery Research Facility Expansion. (Proposed expansion indicated by blue arrows).

Source: NREL Ten-Year Site Plan FY2007 – FY2018 (December 31, 2006). Downloaded on 18/03/2018 at 4:00pm.

3.9 Case Study 4 (Foreign Case Study)

The University of Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research, Lexington, KY, 40511 United States of America.

3.9.1 Brief History

Founded over thirty years ago, the University of Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research (CAER) exists to provide research into important state industries – in this case, bioenergy and its environmental impact. The center is embarking on a program to address the critical national need for low-cost, reliable and abundant energy, and expanded laboratory facilities were needed to enable the research. Hastings+Chivetta, in association with Murphy+Graves were chosen to design the new building.

Figure 3. 33: Overview of the University of Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research.

Source: <http://www.caer.uky.edu/labs/labs.shtml#pet>.

Downloaded on 19/03/2018 at 4:15pm.

The two-storey multi-science facility will provide space for the disciplines of fuel chemistry, catalysis, environmental and geochemistry, electrochemistry, biomass conversion, and carbon materials. Lab spaces are designed with an open layout

to promote collaboration.

Laboratories include wet and dry labs, special process development, prototype manufacturing, and testing labs requiring production and manufacturing floor space. Portions of the facility

Figure 3. 34: Location map of Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research.

Source: <http://www.caer.uky.edu/labs/labs.shtml#pet>. Downloaded on 19/03/2018 at 4:25pm.

will be specially equipped to accommodate capacitor and battery manufacturing research and development, including facilities for battery pack testing and development as well as cell and module development, such as cyclers, test chambers, thermal chambers, and a device teardown area.

The new research space also incorporates labs and testing areas for prototyping, characterization, evaluation and lifecycle testing of new photovoltaic and solar materials. The core of the first floor will house the analytical instrumentation for bioenergy and biofuels. This project is LEED Gold Certified.

3.9.2 Location

2582 Research Park Drive (3rd building on the right) Lexington, 40511 United States of America on latitude 38.136549 degrees East and longitude -84.511415 degrees West.

3.9.3 Year built

Construction of the Kentucky Center for Energy Research Laboratory was completed in 1977.

3.9.4 Objectives of the Institute

1. Performing sound fundamental and applied research to develop industrially relevant technologies.
2. Collaborating with stakeholders to implement novel technologies.
3. Providing technologies to improve the environment.
4. Contributing to the formulation of technically sound policies related to energy and the environment.
5. Developing the capabilities of our colleagues while fostering a mutually supportive work environment with respect for individuals.
6. Contributing to the teaching and instruction aim of United Kingdom by educating students from pre-college to postgraduate levels and being involved in labor force development for Kentucky.
7. Collaborating with colleagues of United Kingdom to promote United Kingdom's and CAER's objectives.

Figure 3. 35: Views of the lobby spaces and stairwell

Source:

<http://www.caer.uky.edu/labs/labs.shtml#pet>. Downloaded on 19/03/2018 at 4:30pm.

Figure 3.36: Zoning pattern at Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research.

Source: <http://www.caer.uky.edu/labs/labs.shtml#pet>. Downloaded on 19/03/2018 at 4:35pm.

8. Promoting United Kingdom's objective of developing and benefiting from its Intellectual Property with a balance between the publication of scientific results and patenting
9. Providing public service in the areas of scientific education and our energy related competencies.

3.9.5 Features of the facility

1. **Ground Floor:** Biofuels and Environmental Catalysis Research Group focus is two-fold: to reduce the environmental impacts of fuel use and to develop renewable fuel sources

Figure 3. 37: Interior of the laboratories at Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research.

Source: <http://www.caer.uky.edu/labs/labs.shtml#pet>. Downloaded on 19/03/2018 at 4:40pm.

(biomass and biofuels). Also includes the UK Renewables Fuels Lab.

2. **First Floor:** Electrochemical Power Sources Research Group provides implementation of innovative energy-storage devices into a practical future use; emphasis is on renewable energy and the promise it holds - like capacitors and batteries.

Figure 3. 38: Interior of the lobby space at Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research.

Source: <http://www.caer.uky.edu/labs/labs.shtml#pet>. Downloaded on 19/03/2018 at 4:45pm

3. **Second Floor:** The entire second floor is devoted to State-of-the-

art Solar Research performed by United Kingdom Department of Chemistry Professor John Anthony's Research Group, whose work includes organic thin-film transistors (for flexible flat-panel displays), organic solar cells (for low-cost electricity generation) and organic light-emitting diodes (for high-efficiency lighting), and distributed solar energy technologies.

Figure 3. 39: Interior of the visitor's center at Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research.

Source: <http://www.caer.uky.edu/labs/labs.shtml#pet>.
Downloaded on 19/03/2018 at 4:48pm

In addition to housing non-fossil fuel research, the building is home

to the Kentucky-Argonne Battery Manufacturing Research & Development Center laboratories, jointly affiliated with the Commonwealth of Kentucky, the Argonne National Laboratory in Chicago, the University of Kentucky, and the University of Louisville. This is a shared-use facility, with portions of the laboratory purposely designed and specially equipped to accommodate capacitor and battery manufacturing research and development. For example, Center for Applied Energy Research. (CAER) Laboratory number 2 houses a 2,000 square foot dry lab, which remains at a relative humidity of 0.5%.

The fan in the lobby is the 10 foot Isis model from Big Ass Fans. The lobby was designed as an open area for gathering groups to introduce the building and research before embarking on tours of the facility.

Another view of the lobby features six touch screens. The Energy Efficiency Education Dashboard (EEED) system demonstrates the green features of the facility, the LEED Checklist and a graphical representation of the electrical, water, chilled water, geothermal, system efficiencies and renewable energy systems for the facility. The Energy

Efficiency Education Dashboard (EEED) provides

Figure 3. 40: Interior of the laboratory at Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research.

Source: <http://www.caer.uky.edu/labs/labs.shtml#pet>.
Downloaded on 19/03/2018 at 5:00pm.

instantaneous comparisons between electricity consumption for the research groups housed there. It also demonstrates a comparison between electrical consumption for the 1970's-era original Center for Applied Energy Research. (CAER Building number 1 and Center for Applied Energy Research Building number 2.

Three energy recovery wheels' recapture energy contained in hood exhaust and supply air. It is estimated that the amount in one year of energy savings will pay back the initial installation and purchase costs. This type of technology is not very well incorporated into most current university settings because there is a potential problem of cross-contamination between labs. Therefore, an Airtuity System was installed to make sure that staff safety is ensured. This system continually pulls samples from all the labs. If it senses any problems with the rankle of any of the air samples, it will vent the air from the lab immediately.

Two roof-top solar panels heat water that is used for all the domestic water in the building. A

Figure 3. 41: Interior of the laboratory at Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research.

Source: <http://www.caer.uky.edu/labs/labs.shtml#pet>.
Downloaded on 19/03/2018 at 5:10pm.

process cooling loop was incorporated into the facility, off of the geothermal system, to reduce once pass through water when used for cooling laboratory equipment.

3.9.6 Merit(s)

1. Deep overhangs that offer a whole lot of protection against driving rain and solar insolation.
2. Casework is flexible and easy to move around.

3.9.7 Demerit(s)

1. Extensive glazing that will surely cause glare if glazed members are not well treated.
2. Visitor's center is restrictive and cannot contain large volumes of visitors at peak hours.

3.10 Case Study 5 (Local Case Study)

The Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant, Umaru Musa Ya'adua Way, Lugbe, Airport Road, Abuja.

3.10.1 Brief History

The Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant Abuja is the activated sludge system type. It is an aerobic process. It draws sewage from the Federal Capital Territory population of over 649, 100 people on a land area of 7,315km². The plant capacity is of 700,000 population equivalent. For Average Dry Weather Flow (ADWF), the design flow is 131,250 cubic meters per day and present flow is 40,000 cubic meters of sewage per day. The plant has six aerobic bioreactors of 27,000 cubic meters' capacity each, making a total of 156,200 cubic meters' reactor capacities. The Solid Retention Time (SRT) is 20 days and the pH for the inlet and outlet of the wastewater is 7.2 and 7.4 – 6.9 respectively on the average.

In this plant, sewage is treated and remaining residue (sludge), which has high volume of Total Solids (TS) and Volatile Solids (VS), is thickened in a thickener and brought out and used as organic fertilizer without achieving gas production because the system is aerobic. The plant was designed to treat waste generated from Abuja city. It has three operating units with one -unit being under operation while the remaining two units are standby in the event of failure of one unit. The plants were designed for a full capacity operation of 131,250 cubic meters of waste per day, though at the moment, it is operating below designed capacity.

3.10.2 Location

The Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant, Abuja is located very close to the Wupa River along Umaru Musa Ya'adua Way, Lugbe, Airport Road, Abuja- Nigeria. The Wupa Waste Water Treatment Plant Abuja It is located upstream to the river Wupa. It lies between latitude 70.201 and 90.201 North and longitude 60 451 and 70 391East.

Figure 3. 42: The Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant, Wupa, Abuja

Source: <https://www.google.com.ng/maps/@9.0747558,7.5052082>. Downloaded on 27/03/2018 at 9:32am.

3.10.3 Year Built and Year Commissioned

Construction works on the Wupa Waste Water Treatment Plant Abuja started in 2001. It was commissioned in March, 2007.

3.10.4 Objectives of the Agency

The Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant Abuja is an environmentally friendly project which has been designed to ensure that the ambience in the city remains clean and pleasant.

It also ensures that the quality of the underground water is improved upon and the streams remain clean as only treated water is discharged back into its natural flow. The concept of the

aeration basin sewage treatment plant has been lauded the world-over for its immense health and environmental benefits.

It tremendously reduces the risk of epidemics associated with human waste disposal which might be traceable to the release of untreated water back to the stream and rivers.

Figure 3. 43: Floor Plan of the Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant Abuja.
Source: Author's field work on 27/03/2018 at 10:00am. Scale is not available.

3.10.5 Features of the facility

The Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant Abuja has facilities that aid in its sewage treatment and re-circulation back into the natural river. They include:

- a. 3 Archimedes pumps
- b. Coarse screens
- c. Fine screens
- d. Grit removal stations
- e. Oxidation ditches with 72 mammoth rotor aerators of 3,500 Kilowatts
- f. Final clarifiers
- g. Ultraviolet. disinfection stations

Figure 3. 44: Schematics for WUPA Sewage Treatment Plant Abuja.
 Source: Author's field work on 27/03/2018 at 10:12am.

Figure 3. 46: Aeration tanks at the Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant Abuja. Source: Author's field work with digital camera *on 27/03/2018 at 10:13am.*

Figure 3. 45: Gravity Thickener station at the Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant, Abuja. Source: Author's field work with digital camera *on 27/03/2018 at 10:20am.*

Figure 3. 47: Sludge dewatering tanks at the Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant, Abuja. Source: Author's field work with digital camera *on 27/03/2018 at 10:25am.*

3.10.6 Merit(s)

1. Its state of the art, high technology and computerized accessories rank this treatment plant at par with the most modern treatment plants in the world.
2. Sludge which is produced as a solid-by product of the sewage treatment process is of agricultural benefit as it could be collected and used as natural fertilizers to boost the growth and production of cash and food crops by the local farmers.
3. The entire treatment process can be divided into mechanical and biological phases. At no stage of the process is the addition of chemicals required.
4. The sewer pipelines are laid conduit and flow due to gravity.
5. In order to provide maximum aeration of the sewage in the system, the pipes were designed to flow half-full. It should be noted that this procedure will allow a slight safety factor for actual flows.

6. The minimum pipe size (used for house connections and regardless of the level of services) is 10centimeters, manholes have been provided at all junctions as well as at intervals of 90 meters maximum.
7. Approximately 3,000,000 meters of sewer pipes were used for the preliminary layout of the sewerage systems serving the capital city of Abuja, Nigeria.
8. A total of about 2, 500,000 meters of 10centimeter pipes were used for building connections from sewer laterals in the streets, the remaining pipe inventories required consist of 150millimeters to 1,850millimeters diameter pipes.

3.10.7 Demerit(s)

1. The treatment plant is being operated by power generating plants which the researcher conclude that the cost incurred in running the plant is exorbitant in relation to being powered by the Abuja Electricity Distribution Company.
2. The sludge being generated is not used for the generation of biogas. It is dumped at offsite random evacuation points.
3. The whole process is aerobic in nature just for the treatment of sewage.

4.8 Case Study 6 (Local Case Study)

The National Biotechnology Development Agency, Umaru Musa Ya'adua Way, Lugbe, Airport Road, Abuja.

3.11.1 Brief History

In recognition of the importance of biotechnology to national development, the Federal Executive Council on 23rd of April 2001 approved the National Biotechnology Policy, which led to the establishment of the National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA) in November 2001. The Agency was established under the aegis of the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology to implement the policy that is aimed at promoting, coordinating, and setting research and development priority in biotechnology for Nigeria. Based on this premise, the programmes of the agency are structured in line with the international standard bearing in mind the development of local technological contents (National Biotechnology Development Agency, 2018).

Figure 3. 48: Insignia of the National Biotechnology Development Agency.

Source:

<http://www.nabda.gov.ng/index>.

Downloaded on 27th of March, 2018 at exactly 8:21pm/

3.11.2 Location

The National Biotechnology Development Agency is located along Umaru Musa Ya'adua Way, Lugbe, Airport Road, Abuja on latitude 9.044058 east and longitude 7.502388 west.

3.11.3 Year Built

The National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA) was established in November 2001.

Figure 3. 49: The National Biotechnology Development Agency, Umaru Musa Yar'Adua way, Lugbe, Abuja. Source: <https://www.google.com.ng/maps/place/National+Biotechnology+Development+Agency+-+NABDA/@9.0439699,7.5002052,17z/data=!3m1!1s0x104e0b952807ef3f:0x98a28ef26c773921!8m2!3d9.0439699!4d7.5023939>. Downloaded on 27th of March, 2018 at exactly 8:26pm.

3.11.4 Objectives of the Agency

The National Biotechnology Development Agency was established to meet the following objectives:

1. Harness the potentials modern biotechnology has to offer under a legal regulatory regime.

Plate 3. 1: Major entrance to the National Biotechnology Development Agency. Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:00am.

2. Ensure environmental, human and socio-economic safety while harnessing the benefits associated with the practice of modern biotechnology and its outputs,
3. Exercise the sovereign right over all the nation's natural resources and authority to regulate access to such resources.
4. Allay the fear of the populace on the socio-economic consequences of modern biotechnology, especially among the small scale farming systems that are prevalent in Nigeria.
5. Reaffirm Nigeria's commitment to the principles of the World Trade Organization and to reaffirm Nigeria's commitment to the goals and objectives of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), and the Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety, which Nigeria has signed and ratified.
6. Safe use of modern biotechnology and provide holistic approach to the regulation of modified organisms in Nigeria.
7. Safeguard human health and the environment from any potential; adverse effect of genetically modified organism including food safety.
8. Provide measures for the assessment of genetically modified organism and management of risk in order to ensure safety in the use of genetically modified organisms to human health and the environment.
9. Ensure that the use of the genetically modified organism does not have undesired impact on socio – economic and cultural interest either at the community or National level.

10. Ensure the Law makes provision for the establishment of a competent agency which would work in line with existing institutional bodies to prevent unsafe use of

Figure 3. 50: The part-floor plan of the National Biotechnology Development Agency.
Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:20am.

genetically modified organisms as well as develop risk managements plan and strategy for protecting human health, biology diversity, and the environment from potentials risks associated with genetically modified organisms.

11. Ensure that Nigeria will have the opportunity to harness the potentials modern technology has to offer in the field of improved food production, medicine/health, Industrial growth and environmental sustainability, generation of Employment and wealth creation through the Modern Biotechnology industry.
12. Bring about responsible Research and Development in Modern Biotechnology,
13. Ensure that Nigeria will be able to guarantee the purity of its agricultural products for the international market, there by gaining international partners and also foreign earning.

14. Ensure that Nigeria will not serve as a dumping ground for unregulated Genetically Modified Organisms which may have impact on the environment and human health.

3.11.5 Features of the Agency

There are six departments, six units, nine Bio-resource centers and seven zonal centers of excellence. The departments include:

1. Administration and Finance:

This department handles all personnel matters, salaries, and welfare of staff in the agency.

2. Agricultural Biotechnology:

Dr. Nasiru Ibrahim is the Acting Director. The activities of the Department are geared towards

Plate 3. 3: The Tissue-culture Laboratory.

Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:25am.

Plate 3. 2: Acclimatization of plants in the screen house.

Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:30am.

the use of biotechnology to meet the National Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA) targets on agriculture and food security. Focal areas of this department include:

Acquisition and domestication of innovative and emerging biotechnologies for sustainable agriculture based on established ethical/biosafety protocols

Plate 3. 7: Off-loading of the raw material (Cassava) for bioethanol Production at National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA). *Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:35am.*

Plate 3. 4: The Fermentation Tank Hall at National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA). *Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:40am.*

Plate 3. 6: Distillation Unit at National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA). *Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:50am.*

Plate 3. 5: Shredding of the raw material at National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA). *Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:50am.*

Improvement and development of higher yielding crop varieties that are resistant/ tolerant to prevailing abiotic (drought, flooding, salinity etc.) & biotic (e.g. pest & diseases) stresses, bio-fortification and value chain development aimed at linking farmers with emerging technologies & markets

Development & provision of genetic modification approach for increased efficiency of high quality food & animal production

Education, public awareness & sensitization on genetically improved crops varieties developed and made available for sustainable food production.

3. *Bio-entrepreneurship and Extension Services:*

Lawan Danjuma Suleiman is the Acting Director/Head of Department. The Department of Bio-entrepreneurship and Extension Services (BED) is one of the technical departments at the National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA), under the Federal Ministry of Science and Technology, (FMST). The emergence of the department is to promote efficiency for Biotechnology Product delivery through bridging of research outputs with the market place. Biotechnology as a cutting-edge science can only make positive impact when results are processed through skills of entrepreneurship. The department is divided into two divisions namely Product Development and Industrialization & Bio-entrepreneurship.

The department is critical to the “*Acquisition of the relevant Biotechnologies for indigenous and self-reliant development for the national growth and accelerated socio-economic well-being firstly to Nigerians and also Africans*”.

Central focus of the department is to:

Ensure that Nigerians have access to safe and profitable use of Biotech-based products and services.

Promote the attainment of self-reliance in the Nigerian biotech industry

Ensure acquisition of manufacturing capability and attainment of high levels of expertise in all aspects of biotechnology for both value-added and basic components through continuous Research and Development.

Resolve both ethical issues and environmental concerns as we acquire and develop the Biotech industry in Nigeria.

4. *Environmental Biotechnology and Bio-conservation:*

Dr Gloria Imoh Bassey Obioh (nee Ahuama) is the Acting Director. The Department has the responsibility to coordinate the development and safe deployment of appropriate biotechnologies for the management and conservation of Nigeria's environment and bioresources. The functions of the department are aimed at improving the integrity of our environment and bioresources.

Divisions:

A. CLEAN TECHNOLOGY

B. BIO-CONSERVATION

3.11.5. A CLEAN TECHNOLOGY

Branches of the Division

- i. Biosafety (Cartagena Protocol) and Laboratory Safety
- ii. Waste and sustainable land management

Functions of the Division

1. Development of research agenda in the area of environmental management and clean technology;
2. Development of proposals in the relevant areas of responsibilities for fund sourcing, locally and internationally;
3. Development of guidelines and framework for ensuring compliance with Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety;
4. Establishment of containment facility for transgenic crops to ensure the integrity of Nigeria's biodiversity and environmental sustainability;
5. Establishment of guidelines for Scientists on safe handling of microorganisms and other biotechnology products and toxins; and

6. Development of biotechnological approaches for the management of lands in areas with drought, desertification and erosion.

3.11.5. B BIO-CONSERVATION

Branches of the Division

- i. Biodiversity
- ii. Genetic resources /conservation and management

Functions of the Division

1. Nigeria's ecosystem/biodiversity for the development of nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals;
2. Development and promotion of biotechnologies for the implementation of the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM);
3. Development of bio-products for the remediation of polluted environmental media;
4. Establishment and maintenance of biodiversity and bioinformatics databases;
5. Development of biotechnologies for the conservation and protection of Nigeria's biodiversity and endangered;
6. Development of Nigeria's bio-security programme in line with the Bacteriological Weapons Convention (BWC);
7. Establishment and maintenance of Microbial Resource Centre and Type Culture Collection for Nigeria;
8. Development of techniques for rapid identification and authentication of micro-organisms; and
9. Development of Bio-banking facilities, culture maintenance, quality control and assurance for Nigeria in consonance with ISO 9000.

5. *Genetics, Genomics and Bio-informatics:*

Professor Oyekanmi Nash is the Acting Director/ Head of Department. The Genetics, Genomics & Bioinformatics Department (GBBD) at National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA) is unique, encompassing all facets of modern genetics and bioinformatics research. Trans-disciplinary research being conducted in the laboratories would lead to cures for human diseases; improvements to crop and livestock quality and yield; creation of new technologies with applications to medicine; agriculture; environment; and industry.

Plate 3. 9: Inside the *Molecular Biotechnology Center (wet labs)*. Source: *Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 10:00am.*

Plate 3. 8: Bioinformatics center (dry lab). Source: *Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 10:20am.*

6. *Medical Biotechnology:*

Dr. Ibeh Bartholomew Okechukwu is the Director/H.O.D. Medical biotechnology seeks novel ways to improving health care delivery. Its primary tool is the understanding at a molecular level of man and the diseases that afflict him. The results range from quicker diagnostic tests, novel medicaments and vaccines, novel surgical tools and therapies etc.

KEY UNITS:

Infectious Diseases Research/ Medical Diagnostics Laboratory

Vaccinology Laboratory

Stem Cell / Bone Marrow Transplantation/Cord Blood Banking Laboratory

Medicinal Plants/ Extraction and Characterization of Active Components Laboratory

Nanotechnology /Radiation Biology and Human Health Laboratory

Biopharmaceuticals Laboratory

DNA Fingerprinting Laboratory

Plate 3. 11: The Biosafety Laboratory.

Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 10:27am.

Plate 3. 10: The Algae-culture tanks at National Biotechnology Development Agency (NABDA).

Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 10:33am.

The units housed in the facility include:

1. Audit
2. Communication and Protocol
3. Information and Communications Technology
4. Legal
5. Physical Planning

6. Servicom (National Biotechnology Development Agency, 2018).

Plate 3. 12: Accompanying catfish tanks in pavilion wet laboratories.

Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:33am.

The bioresources centers supported by the agency include:

1. Abuja Bioresource Center
2. Arochukwu Bioresource Center
3. Isanlu Bioresource Center
4. Kano Bioresource Center
5. Odi Bioresource Center
6. Ogbomosho Bioresource Center
7. Owode Bioresource Center

Zonal centers of the agency are located in tertiary institutions spread across the geographical confines of the country. They include:

1. Ahmadu Bello University (North-West Nigeria).

2. University of Ibadan (South-West Nigeria).

3. University of Jos (North-Central Nigeria).

4. University of Maidugri (North-East Nigeria).

5. University of Nigeria, Nsukka (South-East Nigeria).

Plate 3. 13: Immunovirology and Vaccine Department Laboratory under renovation as at the time of this case study.

Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:43am.

Plate 3. 14: The full view of National Biotechnology Development Agency.

Source: Researcher's fieldwork with digital camera on 28th of March, 2018 at 9:50am.

6. University of Port Harcourt (South-South Nigeria).

3.11.6 Merit(s)

Good landscaping with accompanying parking lots.

Softscaping elements are well positioned and were used to highlight the planning of the site.

All wet laboratories and centers are located at the rear of the administration block in close proximity to the dry laboratories.

The wet laboratories and accompanying offices are located on the ground floor, the dry laboratories on the first floor while the administrative offices and conference rooms are located on the second floor.

Location of exhibition grounds in close proximity to the entrance of the site. This will help control crowds during exhibitions and science fairs.

3.11.7 Demerit(s)

Internal conditions of the greenhouses are not exactly controlled.

As at the time of this case study, some of the laboratories were undergoing a lot of renovation works.

Areas earmarked for orchards and research farms are yet to fully take off.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 FINDINGS, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Presentation of Data

All case studies were properly documented in line with sixteen distinct variables which the researcher intends adopting as design considerations. The variables include:

- a. General landscaping.
- b. Efficiency of Parking Lots for automobiles
- c. Impediments/Restrictions on site.
- d. Synergy between laboratories and offices.
- e. Interspatial communication between the laboratory sections and public spaces
- f. Presence of public spaces including presentation rooms, conference room auditoria.
- g. Nominal operational space existing around laboratory equipment and casework.
- h. Presence of installed equipment including digesters, casework and related machinery with respect to space.
- i. Extensive glazing.
- j. Absence of sun-shading devices and thermal control features
- k. Effective management of ambient temperature through incorporated design features.
- l. Presence of auxiliary laboratories including vivaria, orchards, sequestration stations and dump sites.
- m. Presence of academic spaces including classrooms and demonstration spaces.
- n. Purpose-built integrity
- o. Arrival Architecture.
- p. Possibility for future expansion.

All six (6) case studies were duly compiled and given to each of six (6) assessors; four (4) professional architects of which three (3) are based in academic institutions while one (1)

is in the field but with clear disposition towards public buildings, a Fellow with the Nigeria Institute of Quantity Surveyors, and a Fellow with the Nigerian Institute of Town Planners. These assessors assigned weights to the variables of each of the case studies based on their own assessments. All scores assigned are to a maximum of ‘10’ and a minimum of ‘0’. When case studies have more frequency in exhibiting a particular pattern of response to a variable, the more they inform the researcher on whether that variable should be adopted or not. When more case studies score below “5” the more the researcher is informed to expunge the variable. When more case studies score above “5”, the more the researcher is informed to adopt the variable. However, this rule is not cast in concrete as the researcher could still be at liberty to improve upon a variable before adoption. This is seen when there is a tie in the number of case studies that respond to a particular variable during weighting.

Table 4. 1: Assignment of weights to variables deduced from case studies.

Serial number	Variables	Case Study 1 (Foreign Case Study) Riley- Robb Hall Biofuels Research Laboratory	Case Study 2 (Foreign Case Study) The European Bioenergy Research Institute	Case Study 3 (Foreign Case Study) The National Renewable Energy Laboratory	Case Study 4 (Foreign Case Study) The University of Kentucky Center for Applied Energy Research	Case Study 5 (Local Case Study) The Wupa Sewage Treatment Plant Abuja	Case Study 6 (Local Case Study) The National Biotechnology Development Agency
		RATING (10)					
SITE CONDITIONS							
1.	General landscaping	5	5	9	5	3	6
2.	Efficiency of parking lots for automobiles	7	3	9	4	1	7
3.	Impediments/Restrictions on site	1	8	1	5	3	2
ZONING							
4.	Synergy between laboratories and offices	4	3	9	5	2	7
5.	Interspatial communication between related spaces both in	4	4	8	5	2	3

	the laboratory sections and administration sections						
6.	Presence of public spaces including presentation rooms, conference rooms, auditoria.	3	7	4	6	1	5
EQUIPMENT\WORKSPACE							
7.	Nominal operational clearance for laboratory equipment and casework.	4	6	8	5	1	5
8.	Presence of installed equipment including digesters, casework and related machinery with respect to space.	2	8	7	3	1	3
DESIGN ISSUES/CHALLENGES							
9.	Extensive glazing	7	2	1	2	6	3
10.	Absence of sun-shading devices and thermal control features	1	4	9	7	1	2
11.	Effective management of ambient temperature through incorporated design features	1	3	10	4	4	4
AVAILABILITY OF SUPPORT SPACES/FACILITIES							
12.	Presence of auxiliary laboratories including vivaria, orchards, sequestration stations and dump sites.	1	1	7	1	7	8
13.	Presence of academic spaces including classrooms and demonstration spaces.	5	2	1	2	0	3
GENERAL ARCHITECTURE							
14.	Purpose-built integrity	1	8	9	8	9	9
15.	Arrival Architecture	4	2	9	5	9	5
FUTURE EXPANSION							
16.	Possibility for future expansion	2	1	9	5	8	7

Source: Author's fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 10:00am.

4.2 Interpretation of Data

There are six (6) documented case studies. For each variable, these case studies are weighted accordingly scored by informed assessors through their modules. The highest score is “10” while the lowest score is “0”. The more case studies score “5” and above the stronger the integrity of having *strong variables*. The more case studies score “4” and below the stronger

the probability of having *expendable variables*. However, when there is a tie, especially in a situation where the same number of case studies score above “5” and below “5”, the stronger the propensity of having a *weak variable*. All weak variables may be **positive or negative**. In this case, the researcher is at liberty to adopt a *positive weak variable* with little or no improvements. In the same vein, he can also adopt a *negative weak variable* after it has been fully revised.

4.2.1 General landscaping

For this variable, 5 case studies scored “5” and above with a total of 30 weights. $30/5 = 6$.

One (1) case study scored below “5” with a total of 3 weights. $3/1 = 3$. However, $6 > 3$; $6 > 5$.

This is a strong variable because most case studies visited exhibited propensity for good general landscaping. Full adoption is recommended.

Graph 4. 1: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for general landscaping.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 10:10am.

4.2.2 Efficiency of parking lots for automobiles

There is a tie. Three case studies scored below “5” while the same number scored above “5”.

Those that scored above “5” have a total of 23 weights. $23/3 = 7.6$. Those that scored below

“5” have a total of 8

weights. $8/3 = 2.6$.

Since $7.6 > 2.6$, such

variable is considered as

a positive weak

variable. The researcher

intends adopting it with

Graph 4. 2: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for *efficiency of parking lots for automobiles*

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 10:10am
minimal improvements.

4.2.3 Impediments/restrictions on site

For this variable, four (4) case studies scored below “5” with a total of 7 weights. $7/4 = 1.75$.

Two (2) case studies have

a total weight of 13. $13/2$

$= 6.5$. $1.75 < 6.5$; $1.75 < 5$.

This is an expendable

variable. Full expurgation

is recommended.

Graph 4. 3: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for *impediments/restrictions on site*.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 10:24am

4.2.4 Synergy between laboratories and offices

There is a tie. Three case studies scored below “5” while the same number scored above “5”.

Those that scored above “5” have a total of 21 weights. $\frac{21}{3}=7$. Those that scored below “5” have a total of 9 weights. $\frac{9}{3}=3$. Since $7 > 3$, such variable is considered as a positive weak

variable. The researcher intends adopting it with minimal improvements.

4.2.5 Interspatial

Graph 4. 4: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for synergy between laboratories and offices.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 10:34am

communication between the laboratory sections and public spaces

For this variable, four (4) case studies scored below “5” with a total of 13 weights. $\frac{13}{4}=$

3.25. Two (2) case studies scored above “5” with a total of 13 weights. $\frac{13}{2}=6.5$. $3.25 < 6.5$. This is an expendable variable. Full expurgation is

Graph 4. 5: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for interspatial communication between related spaces both in the laboratory sections and administration sections.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 10:40am

recommended.

4.2.6 Presence of public spaces including presentation rooms, conference rooms and auditoria.

There is a tie. Three case studies scored below “5” while the same number scored above “5”.

Graph 4. 6: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for efficiency of public spaces including presentation rooms, conference rooms.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 10:52am

Those that scored above “5” have a total of 18 weights. $18/3 = 6$. Those that scored below “5” have a total of 8 weights. $8/3 = 2.66$. Since $6 > 2.66$, such variable is considered as a **positive weak variable**.

The researcher intends

adopting it with minimal improvements.

4.2.7 Nominal operational space for laboratory equipment and casework.

For this variable, four (4) case studies scored above “5” with a total of 24 weights. $24/4 = 6$.

Graph 4. 7: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for clearance space for laboratory equipment and casework.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 11:02am

Two (2) case studies have a total weight of 5. $5/2 = 2.5$. $6 > 2.5$; $6 > 5$. This is a strong variable. Full adoption is recommended.

4.2.8 Presence of installed equipment including digesters, casework and related machinery with respect to available space

For this variable, four (4) case studies scored below “5” with a total of 9 weights. $\frac{9}{4} = 2.25$.

Two (2) case studies have a total weight of 15. $\frac{15}{2} = 7.5$. $2.25 < 7.5$; $2.25 < 5$. This is an expendable variable. Full expurgation is recommended.

Graph 4. 8: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for *efficiency of installed equipment including digesters, casework and related machinery with respect to space*.
 Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 11:10am

4.2.9 Extensive glazing

For this variable, four (4) case studies scored below “5” with a total of 8 weights. $\frac{8}{4} = 2$.

Two (2) case studies have a total weight of 13. $\frac{13}{2} = 6.5$. $2.0 < 6.5$; $2.0 < 5$. This is an expendable variable. Full expurgation is recommended.

Graph 4. 9: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for *extensive glazing*.
 Source: Author’s fieldwork. Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 11:25am

4.2.10 Absence of sun-shading devices and thermal control features

For this variable, four (4) case studies scored below “5” with a total of 8 weights. $\frac{8}{4} = 2$.

Two (2) case studies have a total weight of 16. $\frac{16}{2} = 8$. $2.0 < 8$; $2.0 < 5$. This is an expendable variable. Full expurgation is recommended while inclusion of sun-shading devices and thermal control features are advised.

4.2.11 Effective management of ambient temperature through incorporated design features

For this variable, five (5) case studies scored below

“5” with a total of 16 weights. $\frac{16}{4} = 4$. One (1) case studies has a total weight of 10. $\frac{10}{1} =$

10. $4.0 < 10$; $4.0 < 5$. This is an expendable variable. It should be noted that this assessment is correlating to tenth

variable/ As long as most of the case studies lack well-designed sun-shading devices, there is no way ambient temperature could be fully efficiently managed. The researcher is now better

Graph 4. 10: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for presence of sun-shading devices and thermal control features.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 11:30am

Graph 4. 11: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for effective management of ambient temperature through incorporated design features.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 12:10am

informed on the implication of not having sun-shading devices.

4.2.12 Presence of auxiliary laboratories including vivaria, orchards, sequestration stations and dump-sites

There is a tie. Three case studies scored below “5” while the same number scored above “5”.

Graph 4. 12: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for availability of auxiliary laboratories including vivaria, orchards, sequestration stations and dump-sites.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 12:21am.

Those that scored above “5” have a total of 22 weights. $22/3 = 7.3$. Those that scored below “5” have a total of 3 weights. $3/3 = 1.0$. Since $7.3 > 1.0$, such variable is considered as a **positive weak variable**.

The researcher intends

adopting it with minimal improvements

4.2.13 Presence of academic spaces including classrooms and demonstration spaces

Graph 4. 13: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for presence of academic spaces including classrooms and demonstration spaces.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 12:31am.

For this variable, five (5) case studies scored below “5” with a total of 8 weights. $8/4 = 2$. One (1) case studies has a total weight of 5. $5/1 = 5$. $2.0 < 5$;

$2.0 < 5$. This is an expendable variable.

4.2.14 Purpose-built structure

For this variable, 5 case studies scored “5” and above with a total of 43 weights. $43/5 = 8.6$.

One (1) case study scored below “5” with a total of 1 weight. $1/1 = 1$. However, $8.6 > 1$; $8.6 > 5$. This is a strong variable. Full adoption is recommended.

Graph 4. 14: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for *purpose-built structure*.
Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 12:41am.

4.2.15 Arrival Architecture

For this variable, 4 case studies scored “5” and above with a total of 28 weights. $28/4 = 7$.

Two (2) case studies scored below “5” with a total of 6 weights. $6/2 = 3$. However, $7 > 3$; $7 > 5$. This is a strong variable. Full adoption is recommended.

Graph 4. 15: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for *arrival architecture*.
Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 12:47am.

4.2.16 Possibility for future expansion

For this variable, four (4) case studies scored “5” and above with a total of 28 weights. $29/4=$

7.25. Two (2) case studies scored below “5” with a total of 3 weights. $3/2=$

1.5. However, $7.25 > 1.5; 7.25 > 5$. This is a strong variable. Full

Graph 4. 16: Distribution of numerical data of case studies for *possibility for future expansion*.

Source: Author’s fieldwork and collation of results of Independent Assessors Correlation Module on 1st April, 2018 at exactly 12:51am.

adoption is recommended.

4.3 Planning Considerations

This involves the technical studies which will help the researcher in achieving an efficient design in order to meet set standards as well as to achieve user satisfaction.

4.3.1 Activity Grouping/ Zoning (Lay- Out Hints)

In the layout planning of the Biofuel Research Institute, zoning of different activities are made distinct from each other but the different zones are effectively linked up together with walk ways and drive ways where necessary.

This is to ensure that the institute is fully pedestrianized with minimum use of automobiles plus reduction of its pollution, reduced fume effects from laboratories as well as reduced level of damage in cases of fire outbreak and enhanced security efficiency.

Effective zoning however, encourages contact between the zones, more especially the related facilities as the walk-ways would create better views, give quick access to the activity points

and also encourage foot exercise. A spilt over of excitement from one facility to another should be absorbed by means of unique landscape elements an example of which is the aquarium annex.

Activities that attract high public participation should be located closest to access points. Quiet zones like administrative building and other contemplative spaces like libraries and offices etc. should be zoned in the private areas while the noisy areas like the canteen, public exhibition/awareness and general parking etc. should be located off from private areas. However, in this design, planning considerations relating to zoning was based on security, privacy, supervision and access.

4.3.2 Circulation

Circulation is another basic planning consideration in the design of Biofuel Research Institute. It embraces all movement and communication basic to the process of spatial interaction. A well designed Research Institute will ensure activity units are easily accessible with vibrant environments. A research institute with a circulation layout that maximizes the user's access to variety of services and facilities yet minimizing the need for automobile movement.

In this design, much consideration will be given to vehicular and human circulation.

Circulation of visitors starts from the access point and goes through the public facilities of the Research Institute and back to the access point whereas the circulation of goods and fundamental services starts from the service entrance/exit to the specific area where the service is needed and back to service exit respectively.

To achieve maximum and functional circulation of human beings, goods and services in the Research Institute, adequate attention must be given to the drive/walk-ways that are going to run within the Institute as they would form the network through which the circulation of goods and services will be conveyed to their respective delivery points.

4.3.3 Building Materials

Building materials to be specified for construction are usually determined at the later stage of the design. However, the walls, ceilings and floors must be durable and appropriate for their functions. In line with set standards, the building materials specified for use in construction must meet the Building Construction Type 2B guidelines as the design falls under the Design Use Group J (Mixed use and Occupancy) as specified in (LexisNexis , 2006).

Their maintenance, cost, their appropriateness for security is checked acoustic properties and energy efficiency are duly considered.

4.3.4 Flexibility and adaptability

Flexibility is the ability of a building or space to accommodate different activities and over time respond to broader changes in use. Biofuel Research Institute buildings/layout is just like any other public/institutional establishment and is subject to expansion when the need arises. Therefore, one of the basic considerations to the planning of Biofuel Research Institute should be flexibility to cater for expansion factors in services as well as the incorporation of new sections, facilities and zones in the future.

4.3.5 Engineering Systems

This includes structural, electrical, mechanical and plumbing designs and installations.

The engineering systems are determined in the design stage of the project but great attention must be given to the design as well as the actualization of these systems as they are expected to stand the test of time in their stressful service to the public, in and out of season.

4.4 Design Considerations

From the technical data generated from the case studies, these design considerations suffice:

4.4.1 General Landscaping

Landscaping refers to any activity that modifies the visible features of an area of land, including:

1. living elements, such as flora or fauna; or what is commonly called gardening, the art and craft of growing plants with a goal of creating a beauty within the landscape.
2. natural elements such as landforms, terrain shape and elevation, or bodies of water; and
3. abstract elements such as the weather and lighting conditions.

Landscaping requires expertise in horticulture and artistic design.

Construction requires study and observation. It is not the same in different parts of the world. Landscaping varies according to different regions. Therefore, normally local natural experts are recommended if it is done for the first time. Understanding of the site is one of the chief essentials for successful landscaping. Different natural features like terrain, topography, soil qualities, prevailing winds and the system of native flora and fauna must be taken into account. Sometimes the land is not fit for landscaping. In order to landscape it, the land must be reshaped. This reshaping of land is called grading.

Removal of earth from the land is called cutting while when earth is added to the slope, it is called filling. Sometimes the grading process may involve removal of excessive waste (landfills), soil and rocks, so designers should take into account while in the planning stage.

4.4.2 Efficiency of parking lots

A **parking lot** (American English) or **car park** (British English), also known as a **car lot**, is a cleared area that is intended for parking vehicles. Usually, the term refers to a dedicated area that has been provided with a durable or semi-durable surface. In most countries where cars are the dominant mode of transportation, parking lots are a feature of every city

and suburban area. Shopping malls, sports stadiums, mega-churches and similar venues often feature parking lots of immense area.

Parking lots tend to be sources of water pollution because of their extensive impervious surfaces. Most existing lots have limited or no facilities to control runoff. Many areas today also require minimum landscaping in parking lots to provide shade and help mitigate the extent of which their paved surfaces contribute to heat islands..

4.4.3 Impediments/restrictions on site

This implies to the impact of the built-up environment to the overall movement of pedestrians and vehicles on site. As much as possible, there should be minimal obstruction caused by badly-positioned kerbs, signages, parking lots, outdoor relaxation paraphernalia and busy road networks and noisy junctions.

4.4.4 Synergy between laboratories and offices

The relationship of the labs, offices, and corridor will have a significant impact on the integrity and operations of the design. Do refer to **2.8.2** for more details.

4.4.5 Interspatial communication between related spaces both in the laboratory sections and administration sections

The relationship between the laboratory zones and the administrative section of the research institute must be complementary in order to forestall breakdown of communication among users. This is achieved through, apart from communication gadgets, proper zoning. Most times, appropriate signages help.

4.4.6 Efficiency of public spaces including presentation rooms, conference rooms

At this level, it is important to have a strategic development plan that incorporates a system of public spaces, especially for areas where a lot of people congregate. The plan should incorporate a variety of public spaces that respond to different needs (e.g. seminar halls,

meeting rooms, auditoria, markets) and take into account proximity, walkability, safety, and accessibility, as well as affordable transit options. At the project level, human-centric design that integrates different sectors can maximize the value of public space. Appropriate designs whose public spaces are scarce or commonly misused, can launch small pilot projects with inexpensive or temporary design interventions, which will then solicit public feedback and help scale up the successful projects.

4.4.7 The Laboratories, its equipment and casework.

4.4.7. a Walls/Doors/Security

1. The laboratory shall be completely separated from outside areas (i.e., must be bound by four walls). Having enclosed laboratories will help contain spills, keep unauthorized personnel from entering areas where hazardous operations are performed, etc.
2. The laboratory shall have means of securing specifically regulated materials such as DEA (Drug Enforcement Administration) controlled substances and CDC (Centers for Disease Control) select agents and radioactive materials (i.e., lockable doors, lockable cabinets, etc.). Having secured hazardous materials storage will keep unauthorized personnel from gaining access to them.

4.4.7. b Windows

3. If the laboratory has windows that open, they must be fitted with insect screens. Insects, particularly flies, are known to be a potential carrier of disease. To keep insects out of the lab, the doors must be closed while an experiment is in progress, and windows shall be screened if they are capable of being opened.

4.4.7. c Flooring

4. The floor must be non-pervious, one piece, and with covings to the wall. This can be achieved by use of glue, heat welded vinyl flooring, epoxy coated concrete slab, etc.

Floors should be covered up walls and cabinets to ensure spills cannot penetrate underneath floors/cabinets. Tiles and wooden planks are not appropriate because liquids can seep through the small gaps between them.

5. Floors in storage areas for corrosive liquids shall be of liquid tight construction.

4.4.7. d Sinks

6. Each laboratory must contain a sink for hand-washing. Exposure to hazardous materials and/or pathogenic organisms can occur by hand-to-mouth transmission. It is extremely important that hands are washed prior to leaving the laboratory. For this very reason, the sink should be located close to the egress.

7. Laboratory sinks shall have lips that protect sink drains from spills. Sink lips or berms should be $\geq 6.35\text{mm}$ and designed to completely separate the lab bench or fume hood work area from the sink drain.

4.4.7. e Chemical/Waste Storage

8. Chemical storage shelves shall not be placed above laboratory sinks.

9. Sufficient space or facilities (e.g., storage cabinets with partitions) shall be provided so that incompatible chemicals/gases (waste and non-waste) can be physically separated and stored. This will be based on the chemical inventory and use projection provided by the Principal Investigator to the project and EH&S. If the project scope cannot provide sufficient storage the user must develop a written management control plan to include as part of their local Chemical Hygiene Plan. Materials which in combination with other substances may cause a fire or explosion, or may liberate a flammable or poisonous gas, must be kept separate. When designing the shelves, it is important to factor in enough space for secondary containers.

Recommend that solvent storage not be located under the laboratory fume hood, as this is a location where fires are most likely to occur in laboratories.

All labs should be designed to conveniently and safely accommodate the temporary storage of biological, radiological, and chemicals (non-waste and waste) based on laboratory use projections. Wastes are generally stored in the lab in which they are generated, not in centralized accumulation areas.

4.4.7. f Furniture Design, Location, and Exit Paths

10. All furniture must be sturdy. All work surfaces (e.g., bench tops and counters) must be impervious to the chemicals used. The counter top should incorporate a lip to help prevent run-off onto the floor. For example, many microbiological manipulations involve concurrent use of chemical solvents such as formaldehyde, phenol, and ethanol as well as corrosives. The lab bench must be resistant to the chemical actions of these substances and disinfectants. Wooden bench tops are not appropriate because an unfinished wood surface can absorb liquids. Also, wood burns rapidly in the event of a fire. Fiberglass is inappropriate since it can degrade when strong disinfectants are applied. Fiberglass also releases toxic smoke when burned.

11. Vented cabinets with electrical receptacles and sound insulation should be provided for the placement of individual vacuum pumps where their use is anticipated. A 25.4mm to 50.8mm hole for the vacuum line hose from the cabinet to the bench top should be provided.

12. The lab shall have a minimum aisle clearance of at least 609.6mm. Main aisles used for emergency egress must have a clearance width of at least 914mm. Clear aisles and exits are necessary to facilitate departure in the event of an emergency. In practice, lab aisles must be designed wider than 609.6mm so that even with the presence of lab stools and other miscellaneous items, a clearance of 609.6mm is always maintained.

13. A pathway clearance of 914mm must be maintained at the face of the access/exit door. Lab benches must not impede emergency access to an exit. This is also applicable to placement of other furniture and appliances such as chairs, stools, refrigerators, etc.

14. Designated storage space should be provided for lab carts. Location must not reduce width of corridors or aisles to less than code-required widths. Lack of properly designed workstations can increase safety and ergonomic risks for occupants.

16. Laboratory shelving should NOT be installed at heights and distances which require workers to reach 30 centimeters above shoulder height and extend arms greater than 30 centimeters while holding objects 16 kg or less when standing on the floor or on a 304.8mm step stool. Installation of high shelving, above laboratory benches in particular, can create several potential hazards, including, but not limited to ergonomic issues (over-reaching above shoulders and across lab benches); spill and exposures to chemical, radiological or biological agents (e.g., dropping containers when accessing them at high levels). If high shelving were installed, administrative controls, which are often burdensome, would be required. A system for ensuring safe access would include prohibition on the materials stored on shelves, limitations on the frequency of use, availability of ladders or ladders stands, training on ladders, etc.

17. The space between adjacent workstations and laboratory benches should be 1524mm or greater to provide ease of access. In a teaching laboratory, the desired spacing is 1828.8mm. Bench spacing shall be considered and included in specifications and plans.

18. The laboratory doors shall be automatically self-closing. Such self-closing doors are to be able to be opened with a minimum of effort as to allow access and egress for physically challenged individuals.

19. Doors in H-occupancy laboratories shall have doors which swing in the direction of egress. Doors serving B-occupancy shall swing in the direction of egress if the occupant load is 50 or more. Where possible, all B-occupancy lab doors should swing out. Doors which swing in the direction of egress will facilitate occupant departures from laboratories during emergencies.

20. Lab desks should be located near exit ways and in the path of fresh make up air. This will ensure that, in the event of an emergency, employees working in “clean” areas (i.e., their desk) do not have to pass through more hazardous areas to exit the laboratory.

4.4.7. g Illumination

21. Laboratory areas shall be provided adequate natural or artificial illumination to ensure sufficient visibility for operational safety.

4.4.7. h Cleanability

22. The laboratory shall be designed so that it can be easily cleaned. Bench tops must be a seamless one-piece design to prevent contamination. Laminate bench tops are not suitable. Penetrations for electrical, plumbing, and other considerations must be completely and permanently sealed. If the bench abuts a wall, it must be coved or have a backsplash against the wall. Walls should be painted with washable, hard non-porous paints. Wooden and wood finish walls or floors are not appropriate because they can absorb hazardous and/or potentially infectious material, particularly liquids, making decontamination/remediation virtually impossible.

23. Spaces between benches, cabinets, and equipment must be accessible for cleaning and allow for servicing of equipment.

Laboratory furniture must have smooth, non-porous surfaces so as to resist the absorption of liquids and the harsh effects of disinfectants. Furniture must not be positioned in such a manner that makes it difficult to clean spilled liquids or conduct routine maintenance. For example, positioning a Class II biosafety cabinet in a limited concave space might not allow the biosafety cabinet certifier to remove panels of the cabinet when recertifying the unit.

4.4.7. i Breakrooms

24. The design of the laboratory building must incorporate adequate additional facilities for food storage/consumption and personal hygiene tasks.

4.4.8 Efficiency of installed equipment including digesters, casework and related machinery with respect to space.

Part of this consideration has already been discussed in **4.4.7 (a – i)** above.

4.4.9 Extensive glazing

Last year, a report by the National Environmental Engineering Institute NEERI said that the temperature around a glass-facade building can go up by 17 degrees Celsius (National Environmental Engineering Institute, 2017). "This is a concept borrowed from the temperate regions, where it works as those countries are cold. Nigeria is a warm country. Here, glass traps heat and throws it back to the immediate environment.

4.4.10 Presence of sun-shading devices and thermal control features

The use of sun control and shading devices is an important aspect of many energy-efficient building design strategies. In particular, buildings that employ passive solar heating or daylighting often depend on well-designed sun control and shading devices.

During cooling seasons, external window shading is an excellent way to prevent unwanted solar heat gain from entering a conditioned space. Shading can be provided by natural landscaping or by building elements such as awnings, overhangs, and trellises. Some shading

devices can also function as reflectors, called light shelves, which bounce natural light for daylighting deep into building interiors.

The design of effective shading devices will depend on the solar orientation of a particular building facade. For example, simple fixed overhangs are very effective at shading south-facing windows in the summer when sun angles are high. However, the same horizontal device is ineffective at blocking low afternoon sun from entering west-facing windows during peak heat gain periods in the summer.

Exterior shading devices are particularly effective in conjunction with clear glass facades. However, high-performance glazings are now available that have very low shading coefficients (SC). When specified, these new glass products reduce the need for exterior shading devices.

Thus, solar control and shading can be provided by a wide range of building components including:

- ≠ Landscape features such as mature trees or hedge rows;
- ≠ Exterior elements such as overhangs or vertical fins;
- ≠ Horizontal reflecting surfaces called light shelves;
- ≠ Low shading coefficient (SC) glass; and,
- ≠ Interior glare control devices such as Venetian blinds or adjustable louvers.

Fixed exterior shading devices such as overhangs are generally most practical for small commercial buildings. The optimal length of an overhang depends on the size of the window and the relative importance of heating and cooling in the building.

In the wet season, peak sun angles occur at the solstice on June 21, but peak temperature and humidity are more likely to occur in August. Remember that an overhang sized to fully shade a south-facing window in August will also shade the window in April when some solar heat may be desirable.

To properly design shading devices it is necessary to understand the position of the sun in the sky during the cooling season. The position of the sun is expressed in terms of altitude and azimuth angles.

- ≠ The altitude angle is the angle of the sun above the horizon, achieving its maximum on a given day at solar noon.
- ≠ The azimuth angle, also known as the bearing angle, is the angle of the sun's projection onto the ground plane relative to south.

Shading devices can have a dramatic impact on building appearance. This impact can be for the better or for the worse. The earlier in the design process that shading devices are considered they more likely they are to be attractive and well-integrated in the overall architecture of a project.

Both the projection factor (PF) for exterior shading and the shading coefficient (SC) of glass must be evaluated when using the Alternate Component Packages envelope design approach.

Designing shading systems

Given the wide variety of buildings and the range of climates in which they can be found, it is difficult to make sweeping generalizations about the design of shading devices. However, the following design recommendations generally hold true:

1. Use fixed overhangs on south-facing glass to control direct beam solar radiation. Indirect (diffuse) radiation should be controlled by other measures, such as low-e glazing.
2. To the greatest extent possible, limit the amount of east and west glass since it is harder to shade than south glass. Consider the use of landscaping to shade east and west exposures.
3. Do not worry about shading north-facing glass in the continental United States latitudes since it receives very little direct solar gain. In the tropics, disregard this rule-of-thumb since the north side of a building will receive more direct solar gain. Also, in the tropics consider shading the roof even if there are no skylights since the roof is a major source of transmitted solar gain into the building.
4. Remember that shading effects daylighting; consider both simultaneously. For example, a light shelf bounces natural light deeply into a room through high windows while shading lower windows.
5. Do not expect interior shading devices such as Venetian blinds or vertical louvers to reduce cooling loads since the solar gain has already been admitted into the work space. However, these interior devices do offer glare control and can contribute to visual acuity and visual comfort in the work place.
6. Study sun angles. An understanding of sun angles is critical to various aspects of design including determining basic building orientation, selecting shading devices, and placing Building Integrated Photovoltaic (BIPV) panels or solar collectors.

7. Carefully consider the durability of shading devices. Over time, operable shading devices can require a considerable amount of maintenance and repair.
8. When relying on landscape elements for shading, be sure to consider the cost of landscape maintenance and upkeep on life-cycle cost.
9. Shading strategies that work well at one latitude, may be completely inappropriate for other sites at different latitudes. Be careful when applying shading ideas from one project to another.

4.4.11 Effective management of ambient temperature through incorporated design features

Maintaining an appropriate ambient temperature is crucial to the proper functioning and longevity of users, equipment and machines. In general, a safe range is between 60 and 75 degrees Fahrenheit, although the cooler end of that range is better. Ambient temperatures above 80 degrees make it difficult for man and machines to keep a safe operating temperature.

4.4.12 Availability of auxiliary laboratories including vivaria, orchards, sequestration stations and dump-sites

Vivaria, orchards, fish tanks, and dump sites are part of the on-site open laboratories that form part of the 4-prong multi-faceted laboratory biofuel research institute. The vivaria and orchards will form part of the on-site open laboratories for the **saccharification, fermentation and transesterification labs**; the municipal dump site form the on-site stations for the **anaerobic digestion and lignocellulosic labs**; algae-culture ponds/tanks form the on-site open laboratories for the **cell disruption and photo-bioreactor labs** while the geosequestration station form the on-site facilities for the **pre-combustion and genetic modification labs**. A vivarium for genetically-modified crops is also billed to be provided.

4.4.13 Presence of learning spaces including classrooms and demonstration spaces

Classrooms include some version of a group gathering area, multiple seating options and a flex zone that can be adapted for unique learning activities. The layout should allow for a variety of grouping formats and lesson types that take into account students' widely varying learning styles. Twenty-first-century classrooms are driven by student's interests, and the open, flexible spaces allow students to come together to share, collaborate and create.

As already mentioned, to support flexibility institutions are getting rid of standard desks and replacing them with a variety of different seating options. To allow for maximum utility of the space, portable furniture is a must in 21st century classroom design. Common examples of workstation options include yoga mats, exercise balls, kidney tables, standing tables, sofas and floor tables. Giving students options that allow them to rock, bounce and rotate while they are sitting provides for enhanced circulation and concentration throughout the day—and all the learning benefits that come with. These classrooms also increase functionality for students by lowering whiteboards and making materials easily accessible.

Teachers and students are leveraging 21st century classroom design that utilizes these upgrades in new and different ways. These classrooms use technology as a tool to stimulate curiosity and inspire students' desire to learn. Technology, whether it is laptops, tablets, or mobile devices, puts information at students' fingertips and motivates them to research and make discoveries. In addition, technology integration supports inclusive classrooms, as it allows students to move at their own pace whether they are looking for opportunities for enrichment or need help to catch up. Plus, learning at the right level and pace helps keep students engaged, which dramatically reduces inappropriate classroom behavior.

Lighting is an important part of 21st-century classroom design. Bright fluorescent lighting is being replaced with more natural and incandescent light through the use of windows and

lamps. Not only does this make students more comfortable and reduce headaches, but studies have shown that student learning rates have improved between 7 and 26 percent in classrooms that are exposed to adequate natural lighting. Flexible lighting options are also beneficial as students use technology more frequently since dimmed lights make screens easier to see.

4.4.14 Purpose-built structure

There is always the better advantage of having schemes designed for a particular purpose. Building envelopes converted for use to functions not initially meant for them pose more problems as many of the facilities meant to support intended function of the building envelope are not available. As in the case of **The Riley Robb Biofuels Research Laboratory** which is not a custom-designed structure, it offered quite minimal facilities compared to other case studies. This lends credence to the fact that purpose-built case studies and schemes hold integrity than non-purpose-built structures.

4.4.15 Arrival Architecture

This is one of the variables helps to identify the functionality of the scheme at sight. One should be able identify the functionality of the scheme by mere appreciating its aura and massing. At no point should this consideration be in doubt as it gives credence to the class, nature and building type of the design scheme.

4.4.16 Possibility for future expansion

The scheme must be designed to grow. As designs are limitless in conception, they should also have limitless grow pattern. This fact is built into the fabric of the scheme by making sure that new facilities and laboratories could still be added even after the whole design has been fully consummated.

Other invaluable considerations include:

4.4.17 Thermal Comfort

Although the general climate is unalterable, the micro climate of the site can be modified through the adoption of planning and design systems such as ensuring that enclosed spaces are properly ventilated and the use of climate modifiers to ensure optimal airflow hence thermal comfort is achieved thereof.

4.4.18 Fenestration

Adequate Provision and positioning of fenestration means in the design will be used to admit appreciable natural lightening and ventilation and also limit the effects of glare and heat while allowing for rapid dissipation of infrared.

4.4.19 Fire Safety

Precautionary measures will be taken to curb possible and hazardous fire effects. Following this, fire prevention through effective design and fighting systems such as fire alarms, extinguishers and hydrants will be provided in the required positions. Also access pathways should be made sufficiently wide to offer easy movement of fire fighting vehicles. Some buildings will be individually planed in order to retard fire spread in case of occurrence.

Nevertheless, the design proposal would be made to meet the Building Construction Type 2B guidelines as specified in the National Building Code (LexisNexis , 2006).

4.4.20 Security

For the purpose of this design, security must be effective without becoming obstructive or unduly restrictive. Emphasis will be placed on security of lives and properties through the use of effective security devices. However, there will specifications for perimeter fencing round the site to curb possible attempts by invaders as well as the provision of security houses, doors and burglary proofs where necessary.

4.5 Site Selection and Analysis

4.5.1 Selection Criteria

Site selection is an important aspect of any project being that the site in question influences the design of the project either directly or indirectly. Since an architect is meant to design a

Figure 4. 1: Unmineable coal seams 500 meters below the sub-strata of Naze Industrial Clusters.

Source: <http://polarisdigitech.net/nazeindustrialclusters>.

project in relation to the site it becomes imperative that a site is stated as soon as the project is conceived. The selection criteria basically foster on the following factors.

A. Statutory need

Naze Industrial cluster is located directly above a small patch of unmineable coal seams which is very apt for the production of carbon-negative biogas. This will enable the adoption of geosequestration stations in the design of the Biofuel Research Institute. The geosequestration stations will be equipped with boreholes of up to 600meters depth where biogas is passed over the coal seams making it toxic-free with less emission depletion components.

B. Availability of Land

For a project of this scope, land availability is one useful criterion in site selection. Thus the choice of the proposed site with large expanse of land that will be appropriate should be a considerable factor as room must be given for future expansion.

C. Accessibility

Good access to and from the site is another important consideration in site selection criteria. The proposed site is strategically accessed from the Aba-Owerri road. It is pertinent to note that the Nekede-Ihiagwa road which is part of the Owerri ring road is the major road that links the two prominent federal institutions of higher learning in Imo State. This will ensure synergy between these institutions and the research institute.

D. Geographical Centrality

This implies centrality in aspect of proximity to users. A research institute of this standard should be located in a central place to attract national and international interns and researchers.

E. Availability of Services

The availability of services such as electricity, water supply (either from the public mains or easy access to underground water), Nearby accredited university for affiliation amongst others, are very vital keys to the functional selection of a site that would be suitable for a huge project as this.

4.6 Project Site

Imo is one of the 36 states of Nigeria and lies within the South East geopolitical zone of the country. Owerri is its capital and largest city. Its other major cities are Orlu and Okigwe. Located in the south-eastern region of Nigeria, it occupies the area between the lower River Niger and the upper and middle Imo River.

Imo State is bordered by Abia State on the East, River Niger and Delta State to the West, Anambra State on the North and Rivers State to the South. The state lies within latitudes 4°45'N and 7°15'N, and longitude 6°50'E and 7°25'E with an area of around 5,100 square kilometers.

Figure 4. 2: The proposed site as located at Naze on latitude 5.44 degrees and longitude 7.05 degrees.

Source(s): <https://www.google.com.ng/maps/search/NAZE/@5.4441397,7.0516333,2180m/data=!3m1!1e3> and author's field work.

Imo State consists of twenty-seven (27) Local Government Areas. They are Aboh Mbaise, Ahiazu Mbaise, Ehime Mbano, Ezinihitte Mbaise, Ideato North, Ideato South, Ihitte/Uboma, Ikeduru, Isiala Mbano, Isu, Mbaitoli, Ngor Okpala, Njaba, Nkwerre, Nwangele, Obowo, Oguta, Ohaji/Egbema, Okigwe, Onuimo, Orlu, Orsu, Oru East, Oru West, Owerri Municipal, Owerri North, Owerri West and Nwangele.

The proposed Biofuel Research Institute is to be sited at Naze, Owerri-North local government area of Imo State.

Naze is part of Alaenyi cluster which comprises of five towns: Ihitte-Ogada, Awaka, Egbu, Naze and Owerri-nchi-ise. Naze is made up of six villages: Umuorie, Ezeakiri, Umuosu, Umuezuo, Okpuala, and Umuakali. The resident market is Nkwo Naze, hitherto known as Amara – Isu where traders from hinterlands (Isomas) came to see civil society. Today Naze is regarded for its farmers markets, vegetable stands, and large churches. (Wikipedia, 2018)

The proposed site lies within Umuorie and Ezeakiri districts and is accessible from the Aba-Owerri expressway. The southwest part of the site is the Naze Industrial Clusters while on its northwest is a sprawling motorpark which will soon be dismantled in line with the Rescue Mission government of the Owelle Rochas administration.

The site covers an area of exactly 121, 560.88 square meters with a perimeter (fence) distance of 1.47 kilometers. This area is expected to house the design envelope, associated structures, vivaria, orchards and wet laboratory.

4.7 Site Analysis

This is aimed at highlighting all the characteristics of the site. It is essential for architects to understand the unique situation of the area concerned and have deep insight in not only the physical elements such as climate environment but also geographical features readily available. However, these qualities determine the layout and orientation of the buildings to be placed on the site.

4.7.1 Climatic Factors

For any design proposal to meet up with the required standard and functionality, climate as a principal element must be considered. However, this section analyses the climatic features of the proposed site thus;

4.7.1. a Rainfall

Many variations in rainfall have occurred for different climatic regions and individual locations in Nigeria with associated disasters. Every rainy season in Nigeria, wind gusts arising from tropical storms claim lives and properties worth millions of naira across the country. Flash floods from torrential rains wash away thousands of hectares of farmland. Dam bursts are common following such floods. Rainfall is one of the atmospheric driving forces responsible for climate variation and its effects in Imo state of Nigeria as in other parts of the world. A study in 2009

indicated that about 16% of the erosion in Owerri Municipality of Imo State is caused by rainfall (Maduka, 2010).

Imo State is located between latitude $4^{\circ}45'N$ and $7^{\circ}15'N$ and longitude $6^{\circ}50'E$ and $7^{\circ}25'E$, with an area of

Figure 4. 3: Yearly rainfall distribution in Imo State.

Source: http://file.scirp.org/Html/4-2360234_54577.htm.

Downloaded on 30th of March, 2018 at exactly 8:30am.

about 5100 square kilometers. It lies within the humid tropics and is generally characterized by a high surface air temperature regime year-round. Mean minimum temperature is $23.5^{\circ}C$ and mean maximum temperature is $32.1^{\circ}C$. Two seasons, wet and dry, are observed in the year. The rainy seasons begin in April and lasts till October. The State experiences climate variations following rainfall variability. It is on this premise therefore, that this study focused on determination of the shifts in rainfall and the associated disasters as the evidence of climate variation in Imo State.

Intended Design Solution(s)

- i. Use of pitch roofs with minimum slopes of 15° for easy water run-off
- ii. Application of hedges, shrubs and paving around the buildings
- iii. Provision of proper drainage channel and use of sloping gradient during landscape in order to facilitate easy surface water run-off.
- iv. Proper choice of building materials that suits the environment.

4.7.1. b Solar radiation

With relation to true north and cardinal points, the sun rises from the east and sets in the west.

Maximum solar radiation is recorded during the dry seasons and lesser during the peak of the raining season. The average daily sunrise is about 12 hours with maximum values recorded between 12.00 noon and 4.00pm.

Figure 4. 4: Solar radiation distribution in Owerri, Imo State.

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Okey_Nwofor.
Downloaded on 30th of March, 2018 at exactly 8:30am.

Intended Design Solution(s)

- i. Because of the geographical location of the project site, the use of materials with low thermal absorbance capacity should be used.
- ii. Use of solar control elements such as sun-shading devices, deep overhang, fin walls, balcony, and landscape elements-trees

- iii. Proper orientation of building, having the longer axis of the building with largest number of openings to face the north and south axis respectively so as to reduce the amount of direct solar radiation from the East and west where the sun neither rises nor sets.

4.7.1. c Temperatures

Temperatures throughout the year are relatively constant in Imo State with little variation throughout the course of the seasons. The state falls within the tropical forest belt of Nigeria with average temperatures ranging between 25°C - 28°C.

Figure 4. 5: Annual Temperature distribution in Owerri, Imo State.

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Okey_Nwofor.
Downloaded on 30th of March, 2018 at exactly 8:30am.

With the recent changes in atmospheric temperature as a result of global warming, cases of maximum daily temperature of 36°C where recorded in the year 2007. However, the mean annual temperature is about 25° – 28° Celsius with monthly readings as shown in Figure 4.4 on page 188.

Intended Design Solution(s)

- i. Proper orientation of the building on site.

Figure 4. 6: Author's intended design solution to be adopted in the scheme.

Source: Author's sketch.

- ii. Use of light reflective materials that reflects heat radiation.
- iii. Introduction of courtyards in the east – west elongations.
- iv. Use of soft landscape elements such as water bodies, green areas, shrubs, trees etc.

4.7.1. d Prevailing winds

Wind direction in Imo State is predominantly South-West trade winds and the North-East trade winds as shown in fig. 4.28. The South-West trade winds also known as the Tropical Maritime Air Mass blows across the Atlantic oceans and is moisture laden. It heralds the rainy or wet season from April to October. On the other hand, the North-East trade wind known as the sub-tropical continental anticyclone air mass which blows across the Sahara Desert carrying dry air and dust particles. It heralds the harmattan season from November to early February. An annual monthly mean wind speed of 73.3km/h per day is recorded throughout Owerri, with a slight difference in other parts of Imo State.

Intended Design Solution(s)

- i. Proper orientation of building in relation to wind direction
- ii. Use of natural shading devices to shade off unwanted and excess air movement.
- iii. Introduction of adequate fenestration.

4.7.1. e Relative humidity

Seasonal relative humidity variation corresponds with rainfall distribution. Generally, monthly relative humidity fluctuates between 80 and 90% and is recorded during raining season while relative humidity as low as 71% is recorded during dry season. The relative comfort zone for relative humidity is 40 – 55% (world weather online, 2018).

Figure 4. 7: Relative humidity distribution in Owerri, Imo State.

Source: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Okey_Nwofor. Downloaded on 30th of March, 2018 at exactly 8:30am.

Intended Design Solution(s)

- i. Use of properly seasoned timber materials in the construction
- ii. Cross ventilation is most viable to remove pockets of moist air.
- iii. Materials that are not prone to moisture absorption are to be used wherever possible.

4.7.2 Microclimate of the Site

Minimal temperature variation is observed in the site as a result of presence of averagely thick vegetation (especially within the Industrial Clusters) and trees within and around the site

which helps to absorb the amount of solar radiation reaching the site by absorbing some ultraviolet rays.

4.7.3 Geographic Features

This section analyses the geographic features of the proposed site.

4.7.3. a Vegetation

The site is located within the tropical rainforest zone, characterized with thick forest having tall trees which forms canopies over the forest and could grow as tall as 18-45 meters high. Although some portions within the site has been cleared by the Government and individuals for one purpose or the other at

Figure 4. 9: Showing the nature of vegetation in the proposed site.
Source: Authors Fieldwork, 2018.

Figure 4. 8: Showing access to the proposed site from Aba-Owerri road.
Source: Authors Fieldwork, 2018.

one time or the other, the site is currently bare at the approach but contains an average number of trees and ground vegetation.

4.7.3. b Geology and soil types

The site is situated very close to the Aba-Owerri road with the rich forest belt terrain. There were distinct macro-morphological properties of soil in the site. In the mixed forest the epipedon was darker (Dark brown 7.5 YR ^{3/2},) moist when compared to brown (7.5 YR ^{4/3}) moist, as observed in epipedon under some pine trees seen in the site. Peds in the epipedon under mixed vegetation were stronger and granular while soils under pine were weak and sub-angular. Friable consistence was reported in surface soils (0-10 cm) depth in epipedons under mixed forest unlike loose consistence exhibited by epipedons under pine forest. Roots were in abundance in epipedons in both soils but greater variety of roots in mixed vegetation.

4.7.3.c Topography

The land form of the site is characterized by relatively undulating terrain.

Figure 4. 10: The proposed site as located at Naze on latitude 5.44 degrees and longitude 7.05 degrees showing section X- X, index lines and contour intervals.
Source(s): <https://www.google.com.ng/maps/search/NAZE/@5.4441397,7.0516333,2180m/data=!3m1!1e3> and author's field work on 15th of June, 2018.

Figure 4. 11: The proposed site as located at Naze on latitude 5.44 degrees and longitude 7.05 degrees showing profile view of section X- X.

Source(s): <https://www.google.com.ng/maps/search/NAZE/@5.4441397,7.0516333,2180m/data=!3m1!1e3> and author's field work on 15th of June, 2018 at exactly 5:08pm.

4.7.4 Geographical Data

These include the geographical locations of the project site in relation to the geopolitical map of the country. These are illustrated diagrammatically below:

Figure 4. 12: Map of Nigeria showing the 36 states of the federation including Imo State.

Source: National Library, Owerri Branch.

Figure 4. 14: Map of Owerri North Local Government Area showing Naze, being the host community.

Source: National Library, Owerri Branch. Re-draughted by the author on 18th of June, 2018 at exactly 7:05pm.

Figure 4. 15: The proposed site as located at Naze on latitude 5.44 degrees and longitude 7.05 degrees.

Source(s): <https://www.google.com.ng/maps/search/NAZE/@5.4441397,7.0516333,2180m/data=!3m1!1e3> and author's field work.

4.8 Users' Analysis

This includes the analysis of the individual users of this project, identifying their possible attributes. However, for the context of this project the analysis of the user can be categorized into the following;

- i. Primary users
- ii. Secondary users
- iii. Passers-by

4.8.1 Primary Users

These are the direct users of the facilities in the Biofuel Research Institute which include the following:

4.8.1. a Administration Section

The administration section includes the following:

- i. The Director General
- ii. The Head(s) of Departments/Director
- iii. Researchers
- iv. Postdoctoral researchers
- v. Scientists
- vi. Principal Scientists
- vii. Senior Scientists
- viii. Contingent Workers
- ix. Center Director Bioenergy Sciences
- x. Research Technicians
- xi. Laboratory Directors
- xii. Associate Laboratory Directors
- xiii. Microbial Physiology & Engineering
- xiv. Process Research Engineers
- xv. Electrical Engineers
- xvi. Thermochemical Process/Control Engineers
- xvii. Electro/Mechanical Technicians
- xviii. Business Support III-Administrative Associates
- xix. Industrial Research Equipment Technicians
- xx. Molecular Microbiologists
- xxi. Staff Engineers
- xxii. Bio-process Engineers
- xxiii. Bioconversion Specialists

4.8.2 Indirect Users

The indirect users of the Biofuel Research Institute include:

- i. Biorefinery developers
- ii. Research Establishments
- iii. Government Agencies
- iv. Private and Contract-based Researchers

4.8.3 Passersby

This includes the admirers of this facility and every other person that do not contribute directly to the growth and upkeep of the Institute either by patronizing its products or by checking in or making commendations.

4.9 ACTIVITY AND SPACE ANALYSIS

4.9.1 Administration Section

The administration division in the proposed Institute will mostly take responsibility of all matters relating to the general administration in liaison with the Staff Officers, Research Instructors and other external but affiliated organizations/ Institutions and business associates operating at the Institute. The section would coordinate the activities of other sections in the Institute such as medical unit, research unit, IT and security, as well as all the zones and departments of the Institute that may seem to be independent.

4.9.2 Public Zones

Basically, the orchards and vivaria zones occupy the second largest area in the Research Institute. It is a section of the Institute where outdoor research wet labs and green houses are situated and maintained.

Other facilities to be featured in this section also include the Auditoriums, Lecture Halls, cafeteria and all others specified in the design brief whereas allowance would be given for future additions and expansion.

4.9.3 Commercial Zone

Business/Trade, being one of the sure activities that would run in the Institute to keep life in the Environment worthwhile would be provided to meet the day to day needs of the students, staff, Researchers and Visitors.

The commercial zone would be broken down into different business sections with respect to the kind of material in play. This would ease the search for materials and would contribute greatly to the free flow of traffic in and out of the site.

4.9.4 Gate Complex

The gate complex which would regulate the ingress and egress of persons and vehicles as well as goods through the Institute. It is a place where brief documentation, security procedures such as the inspection of vehicle, people and goods would occur.

4.10 Space Analysis

This section analyses the users of the proposed spaces in relation to their anthropometrics. It is indeed necessary as it helps in determining the actual space requirement per person, the total / average number of persons to occupy a provided space, the floor area required for the number of persons amongst other considerations. This will help in the space management and in determining the total floor area covered by the building(s).

Table 4. 2: Space Analysis showing spaces to be provided and capacity of usage.

SPACE	CAPACITY	SPACE PER PERSON (m ²)	NUMBER REQUIRED	TOTAL AREA (m ²)
Entrance porch	60	1.5	1	90
Waiting\Reception		0.90	-	120
Auditorium	1000	0.85	2	850
Library	100	1.2	-	120
IT Hall	50	1.2	2	120
Laboratories	25	0.90	6	18.0
Staff offices	1	1.35	3	40.5
General office	2	1.75	4	3.5
General offices	10	3.5	10	
Secretaries office	2	1.2	4	48.0
Conference hall	20	1.5	4	100
Cafeteria	150	2.5	3	300
Seminar Halls	1500	2.5	2	330
Other offices		1.8	6	-
Conveniences		1.35		
Kitchen	33	1.2	1	240

Source: Author's design programme.

4.11 Construction Materials and Finishes

4.11.1 Construction Materials

Construction in this context refers to the manner in which the structures are built. Hence, the building construction materials encompass different materials use in the construction of the buildings. The diverse effect of global warming in together with the problem of urbanization and the problems associated with the site region has constituted a great effect on the durability of materials as well as the thermal comfort of the occupants. This could be solved through the construction materials and the construction process employed in the execution of the Research Institute. Therefore the building materials for this project both interior and exterior will be influenced by income of the client(s), building codes and regulations, existing trends and availability of building material. Examples of material to be use in the construction of this project include;

- i. Wood (Seasoned and treated)
- ii. Cement
- iii. Sandcrete blocks
- iv. Steel bars
- v. Fine aggregate (Sand)
- vi. Coarse aggregate (Gravel stone)
- vii. Insulating materials (such as rock wool or fibre board)
- viii. Water proofing materials (such as Asphalt and Bitumen)
- ix. Plastic stoppers and sealants

4.11.2 Finishes

Finishes (External, internal and floor finishes) here were used considering not only their aesthetical functions but also their usage function, their structural, economic, stability, durability and the efficiency in the overall building envelop. The working consideration in the choice of finishes depends on functionality in terms of the finishes posing good weathering

properties and meeting satisfactory performance standards. Below are examples of finishes that could be used in the different structures in the Academy;

- i. Long span Aluminum
- ii. roofing sheet
- iii. Paint (Quality and type depending on the area of application)
- iv. Wall tiles for external walls (interior and part exterior)
- v. Ceramic tiles for floor
- vi. Stainless Steel hand rail

4.12 Design Scheme

4.12.1 Design Concept

The concept adopted by this researcher is one of the ways of responding to the current design

Figure 4. 16: The design concept as initiated for the Biofuel Research Institute.

Source: Researcher's conceptive studies.

situation. It is a way of translating the non-physical design problem into the physical building product. Every project will have critical issues, central themes or problem essences, and the general issues of designing a building can come under the following categories:

- ≠ functional zoning
- ≠ architectural space
- ≠ circulation and building form
- ≠ response to concept

≠ building envelope

Obviously many elements and factors fall under these categories, with much consideration required to the broader general issues, along with the technical details.

This researcher adopted the simple leaf as his concept based on the single fact that it is a natural element which is the basic component of a plant and from which much of our biofuels are produced.

The concept is derived from the combination of the leaf structure of the jatropha plant. The jatropha leaf is combined to form the spatial functioning zone of laboratories/laboratory offices and the administration section which the researcher intends to aggregate in a curvilinear form.

The Architectural space will resemble a leaf structure in elevation while the circulation and building form will flow with the curvilinear envelope.

Finally, the building envelope of the laboratories and its components will take a leaf-life ensemble in elevations while adopting a near pneumatic roof structure.

4.12.2 Bubble Diagram

Bubble diagrams depict the program in the form of circles and ovals shown in a floor plan format. Each circle, or bubble, represents the space needed to carry out a function, such as

Figure 4. 17: The bubble diagram.

Source: Researcher's preliminary sketches as at 14th of June, 2018.

dining, sleeping, and studying. The circles portray functional aspects of design, such as privacy, circulation, noise, daylight.

Bubble diagrams express not only the spaces within the building but also the relationships between spaces. They indicate what functions/spaces (circles) should be near each other in order for your building to offer functionality.

As shown above, the first purple form depicts the entrance lobby which empties into the larger second purple form – the circulation concourse. From the circulation concourse, circulation continues to the right wing – the offices and lecture hall. On the left wing are the auditorium, seminar halls and their support spaces.

After the circulation concourse, restrictive circulation pattern heralds the rear orange forms of the dry laboratories and their support spaces. From the dry laboratories, access to the wet laboratories commence through collapsible air-inflatable chutes. These are represented with light-blue forms.

4.12.3 Zoning Pattern

The site is zoned into the public zone, semi-private zone and the private zone. The public zone comprises of the administration block that houses the offices, lecture halls, auditorium, seminar halls and the dry laboratories. Others include the conference rooms, demonstration

Figure 4. 18: Zoning pattern of proposed site

Source: Researcher's preliminary sketches as at 15th of June, 2018.

halls and underground storage cisterns.

The public zone is in close proximity to the parking lot which lies within the high-decibel part of the site.

The semi-private zone comprises of the residencies of the staff, clinic, emergency bay and parking lots. This zone lies directly on the easterly and in close proximity to the Umuorie District. This zone is within the medium-decibel zone.

The private zone comprises of the geosequestration stations, orchards, vivarium and greenhouses. The private zone is situated thus in order to minimize as much as possible noise from the immediate environment. This zone, thus, was planned to be within the low-decibel zone.

Trees and horticultural plants were used to shield the public zone as much as possible. Also coupled with the fact that most activities going on in this zone are not so sensitive, this researcher found it apt to locate the zone there.

4.12.4 Conceptual sketch

The sketch as attached in Figure 4.19, page 209 is this author's intended solution to the requirements of the design scheme. It is still being developed as at the time of attachment.

Figure 4. 19: Preliminary design sketch of the ground floor plan
Source: Researcher's preliminary sketches as at 16th of June, 2018.

Kindly see 'APPENDIX C' for developed progress of the drawings of the proposed scheme. Therein as contained in 'APPENDIX C' are the cognitive base maps, the site plan, the floor plans, elevations and three-dimensional projections which are yet to be rendered. All such drawings are indicative of the fact that appreciable work has been done in making the scheme viable for the acceptance. However, final approval is yet to be given for presentation in the final jury.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 SUMMARY, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary

Biofuels are fuels made from cellulosic biomass resources, including ethanol, biodiesel and methanol. Those biomass processes can be designed to produce solid fuel, liquid fuel, gasses or electricity. Biofuels can have their sources from some crops, such as sugar cane, sugar beets, cassava etc., also from vegetable oils derived from plant seeds, such as sunflower, linseed and oilseed, as well as animal waste. It can be produced commercially through the thermo-chemical conversation and biochemical processes and also in the laboratory by simple chemical conversion. In meeting the Nigeria's energy needs, biofuels are very crucial ingredients for sustainable development and has always been a vital and indispensable input to the economic needs of our present civilization. It is obvious that there is need for Nigeria to have a purpose-built facility that is designed to explore alternative source of energy, more especially to reach out to the people that do not have access to electricity and other modern energy services. This will go a long way in cutting down the country's dependence on fossil fuels, improve its energy indices and overall Gross Domestic Product (Etim, 2012).

5.2 Recommendations

5.2.1 Infrastructure

There is the need for Nigeria to come up with institutional frameworks that will support and enhance the production of biofuel in a sustainable manner like in Brazil by way of providing a facility that is vested with the mandate to carry out research into biofuel production.

In line with the argument on the sustainable development of a viable Biofuels Research Institute, Nigeria must develop a strong, supportive policy, and a firm legal, regulatory and institutional framework to ensure that measures are put in place to harness the contribution of the sector to sustainable alternatives to energy.

Adequate laboratories that are designed to fully take up challenges of research and testing of feedstock from different relevant agencies and parastatals is advised.

Practical design tenets needed to make the laboratories conducive for different schedules must be put in place to enable researchers carry out informed research into the production of biofuel. These measures should include three-dimensional laboratory module system, race-track design pattern for laboratories and inclusion of underground cisterns for the warehousing of feedstock and biomass.

Wet laboratories, orchards, greenhouses and geosequestration stations are needed to make for a holistic and comprehensive research into the production of biofuels. Research should not and must not only stop at laboratories only. These support spaces are vital.

The country will go a step further by having biodegradable dump yards where Biofuel industries that have the capacity to produce ethanol, methanol and biodiesel in commercial quantities could source their raw materials at very little cost. This is already on-going in countries that have made a mark in biofuel production. The research institute develops samples of test products with accompanying efficient and economically viable production process which are patented and sold to commercial outfits.

5.2.2 Policy

Expansion of agricultural production, developing export markets for agricultural produce, ensuring competitive market prices for the national agricultural commodities and improving local market channels for efficient distribution and marketing of agricultural produce as well as proper dissemination and implementation of agricultural research information such as

newly available plant breeding techniques, technology and/or high-yielding and disease-resistant crop/seed varieties among others are highly recommended to foster an increase in agricultural production. This is because the increase in cultivated land area, agricultural labor force and even the maximum total gross margin obtainable from the entire enterprise signify an overall greater positive contribution to the national economy compared to the current (base year) production levels. Therefore, expanding agricultural crop demand should be the major focus and priority of the national government, Ministry of Agriculture and/or farmers in order to reap the desired positive outcomes.

Provision of annual short-term, medium and/or long-term credits (cash loans), with reduced interest rate (at least with a single-digit interest rate), to all farmers that are cultivating feedstock through commercial banks, agricultural banks and/or agricultural associations such as growers associations are essential to provide the necessary incentive required to boost agriculture, achieve optimum crop production in Nigeria and bridge the gap between food consumption and food production since they are required to fund all farm operations prior to harvesting and selling of farm produce. This might have been one of the major constraints to the Nigerian agricultural development and growth since the primary factors of production (land and labor) have been available in abundance before now. Therefore, the government could and should evolve an effective way of ensuring that the disbursed credits reach the targeted peasant farmers who are feeding the nation. The farmers should be monitored to ensure that the funds are invested in farming sector as planned to ensure repayment of loans immediately after harvest and sale of farm produce, as this will foster continuity and sustainability of such policy.

In order to ensure a successful and sustainable implementation of the ethanol policy with reduced impacts on food availability and food prices, a possible policy implementation strategy could be to create a government monitored Feedstock Growers Association that will ensure that farmers cultivate the same and other staple food crops for the purpose of domestic

consumption before they are allowed to enlist in the feedstock growers' association. This of course will require collaboration with the ethanol industry (where the farmers and/or the growers' association supply their feedstocks) in order to ensure that the ethanol industries do not buy from farmers who are not enlisted with the feedstock suppliers and that they report their feedstock supply sources on a quarterly basis for verification. For example, a farmer who wants to supply 20 metric tonnes of cassava per annum as feedstock could be mandated to have other inspected plots of land where he produces additional 20 metric tonnes of maize, 20 metric tonnes of cassava, 20 metric tonnes of yam and 20 metric tonnes of rice (depending on the regional food consumption and feedstock demands) without reducing any of the initial crops that s/he used to cultivate. In that case, domestic production and supply of all crops (food and cash) will be ensured while producing enough feedstocks for ethanol production since farmers who do not meet these criteria will be 'forced' to remain in the production of food crops where they will still receive the associated increase in their income in case of an increase in food-crop market prices. The above described policy procedure could help Nigeria maximize the identified positive benefits of ethanol production such as utilizing more of her productive agricultural resources (e.g., land and labor) that are currently lying idle or being under-utilized; creating more jobs; increasing farmers' income; boosting Nigerian motor fuel supply via the produced biofuel; and increasing the national Gross Domestic Product and national income thereby boosting the entire national economy while reducing the impact on food prices.

5.3 Conclusions

Globally, countries are adopting biofuel policies ostensibly to follow a cleaner path of development characterized by low carbon energy alternatives, achieve energy security and transform rural economies. Within this context, Nigeria's quest for biofuel arguably does not represent a misplaced priority. Nigeria even has high potentials for biofuel production due to

the level of water availability and the vast arable land available for the production of energy crops as identified by (Oshewolo, 2012)

The biofuels policy is the first of its kind established in Nigeria with the view of diversifying access to energy, job opportunities, sources of revenues and mitigating greenhouse gases emissions by linking agriculture with petroleum industry since the discovery of commercial fossil oil and gas reserves in 1956. 97.3% of the public responses consider this as a welcome development with strong potentials to yield good results, especially to the local inhabitants. However, some school of thought argued that, large scale biofuels production would seriously create imbalances such as sudden rise in food price and diversion of food land to cash crops production. Although the policy addressed issues such as the key feedstock, production structure, possible market demand, and investment incentives, careful planning is required otherwise the implementation may cause more problems than benefits. As the current study gave emphasis to the views of people in the academia, it is necessary to execute both short and long term research with farmers, academicians, oil companies, marketers and their respective associations to identify what works and what doesn't in terms of finance, source of manpower, most appropriate crops, fiscal system and end-product usage. Coupling the findings with lessons from countries like Brazil and India that have already gone a long way in biofuels production would be very important. To strike a balance between food and fuels production and the associated prices, emphasis should always be given to pre-exploited agricultural land and non-food crops. Crops such as jatropha and sugarcane could be good options. However, sorghum and cassava account for over 70% of food supply to the Nigerian people and therefore any commercial exploitation is associated with hunger threats and price hike. Currently, the country is more in tune with the production of first and second generation biofuels through transesterification and anaerobic digestion processes. Even at that, their level and scale of production is still minimal and through crude processes. The third and fourth generation biofuels are yet to be exploited. These processes generate better and more efficient

biofuels than the latter two processes and this is why countries like Brazil and India have long established marked expertise in their production.

To this end, the Biofuel Research Institute will go a long way in ensuring that the nation will build on its background knowledge of the earlier generations, train personnel on the production of biofuels from third and fourth generation platforms and use their wealth of experience and training to build on our capacity to effect production within our clime in the country.

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APPENDIX A

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University

P.O Box 02

Uli,

Anambra State.

22nd February, 2018.

Dear Sir/Madam,

REQUEST FOR ASSISTANCE IN THE ASSESSMENT OF CASE STUDIES AS PART OF THE INDEPENDENT ASSESSORS CORELATION MODULE

I most humbly wish to request your kind assistance in assigning weights to distinct variables as contained and accompanying the documented case study and its assessment sheet. You are at liberty to assign weights from zero (0) to ten (10) in response to your objective assessment of the documented case study. This will guide the researcher to either adopt or expunge variable(s) that meet up/fall below the score five (5) benchmark. All variables that score five (5) and above will be adopted as the design considerations.

This tool is devised in the course of this research as part of partial fulfillment for the award of Masters of Science in the Department of Architecture, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Uli, Anambra State.

I most humbly pledge that any information supplied by your person will be treated with utmost and strict confidence as this exercise will only be used for this research work.

Your objective response to this assessment is highly solicited.

Thanks for your anticipated cooperation.

Yours faithfully,

Onwukwe, Chukwuemeka Ozioma Stanislaus

Department of Architecture,

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Uli, Anambra State.

08037635722

APPENDIX B

Personal data:

Name of Institution/Office:	-----		
Designation/Rank:	-----		
Years of Experience in Practice:	-----		
Sex: (tick as appropriate)	Male: <input type="checkbox"/>	Female: <input type="checkbox"/>	
Membership to Professional Body: (tick as appropriate)	Nigeria Institute of Architects: <input type="checkbox"/>	Nigeria Institute of Quantity Surveyors: <input type="checkbox"/>	Nigeria Institute of Town Planners: <input type="checkbox"/>
Number of Years of Membership:	-----		

Documented Case Study:

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Denver, United States of America.

Brief History

Established in 1974, National Renewable Energy Laboratory began operating in 1977 as the Solar Energy Research Institute. Under the Jimmy Carter administration, its activities

Figure B- 1: National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 15013 Denver West Parkway, Golden, CO 80401, United States of America on latitude 39.740748 East, longitude: -105.170634 West.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 1:47am.

went beyond research and development in solar energy as it tried to popularize knowledge about already existing technologies, like passive solar. During the Ronald Reagan administration, the institute's budget was cut by nearly 90%; many employees were "reduced in force" and the laboratory's activities were reduced to R&D. In later years, renewed interest in the energy problem improved the institute's position, but funding has fluctuated. In 2011, anticipated congressional budget shortfalls led to a voluntary buyout program for 100 to 150 staff reductions. The budget for fiscal 2016 was \$427.4 million, down from a peak of \$536.5 million five years earlier. Changes in the budget have sometimes forced NREL to cut staffing. Since its inception in 1977 as the Solar Energy Research Institute, it has been operated under

Figure B- 2: National Renewable Energy Laboratory (Bio-renewables), 15013 Denver West Parkway, Golden, CO 80401, United States of America on latitude 39.740748 East, longitude: -105.170634 West.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 1:52am.

contract by MRI Global. In September 1991, the NREL was designated a national laboratory of the United States Department of Energy by President George H.W. Bush and its name was changed to NREL. Currently, NREL is managed for the Department of Energy by the Alliance for Sustainable Energy, LLC. The Alliance was formed in 2008 as a joint venture between MRI Global and Battelle. Dr. Martin Keller became NREL's ninth director in

November 2015, and currently serves as both the director of the lab and the president of the Alliance. He succeeded Dan Arvizu, who retired in September 2015 after 10 years in those

Figure B- 3: Ground floor plan of National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 15013 Denver West Parkway, United States of America.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 1:55am.

Figure B- 4: Aerial view of National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 15013 Denver West Parkway, United States of America.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 1:59am.

roles.

Location

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory is located at 15013 Denver West Parkway,

Figure B- 5: Satellite imagery of National Renewable Energy Laboratory, 15013 Denver West Parkway, Golden, CO 80401, United States of America on latitude 39.740748 East, longitude: -105.170634 West.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 2:06am.

Golden, Colorado 80401, United States of America on latitude 39.740748 degrees East and longitude-105.170634 degrees West.

Year built

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory was built and established in 1974 and began operating in 1977 as the Solar Energy Research Institute.

Objectives of the institute

The National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) advances the science and engineering of energy efficiency, sustainable transportation, and renewable power technologies and

provides the knowledge to integrate and optimize energy systems. NREL is the only federal laboratory dedicated to the research, development, commercialization, and deployment of renewable energy and energy efficiency technologies.

Figure B- 6: Inside the Solar research laboratory at The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Denver, United States of America.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 2:10am.

The Bioenergy Program supports NREL research and development that focuses on biomass characterization, thermochemical and biochemical biomass conversion technologies, bio-based products development, and biomass process engineering and analysis. NREL also works to develop cost-effective, environmentally friendly biomass conversion technologies to reduce our nation's dependence on foreign oil, improve our air quality, and support rural economies.

Figure B- 7: Open office work spaces at The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Denver, United States of America.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 2:15am.

The Buildings Research Program supports NREL research and development that focuses on improvements in residential buildings, in commercial buildings, in building equipment and components, building energy analysis tools, manufacturing, and in lighting

and appliance standards. NREL is a nationally recognized leader in buildings research combining renewable energy with innovative technologies to significantly reduce energy consumption in buildings.

Features of the facility

National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL)'s 327-acre South Table Mountain campus

Figure B- 9: The Aerial Perspective of the National Renewable Energy Laboratory.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-drafted on 1/06/2018 at 2:21am.

Figure B- 8: The Ethanol production hall at The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Denver, United States of America.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-drafted on 1/06/2018 at 2:25am.

center, employee lunch room, lobby, conference, and support spaces.

currently includes 17 buildings, which house offices, laboratories, test facilities, and more than 2,447 workers.

The vision for the sustainable campus is documented in their master plan and implemented through utilizing high performance sustainable building requirements. In addition to open office, semi-private and some private offices, the facility includes a library, data

Merit(s)

All of the buildings are sited with their long axes east-to-west so that they can take advantage of passive solar energy along their long north and south walls.

The south-facing windows are all shielded with some sort of bonnet or giant blinds to bounce the natural light inside while keeping the summer heat out.

Figure B- 10: The biochemical conversion laboratory at The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Denver, United States of America.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-drafted on 1/06/2018 at 2:29am.

Figure B- 11: Exquisite open office design spaces at The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Denver, United States of America.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-drafted on 1/06/2018 at 2:32am

There are shaded balconies at the ends of each floor. The roofs were angled up so that heat can rise and escape out the upper windows.

There were also “huddle rooms” for small meetings, phone rooms for private conversations, and quiet rooms for people to take health-related breaks (such as for migraines) or

for nursing mothers to pump milk.

Buildings were

planned with expansion in mind so that equipment can be added if new projects are authorized.

The whole facility has been mapped out so that the sites of future buildings have already been designated.

Demerit(s)

The Laboratory's small (6,000-square foot) visitor center built and donated by Midwest

Figure B- 12: Exotic horticulture at The National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Denver, United States of America. Perfect harmony with the outdoors.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 2:35am

Figure B- 13: The National Renewable Energy Laboratory's South Table Mountain campus in the Denver metropolitan area.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 2:41am

Research Institute in 1994, can no longer meet the demand of an increasing numbers of people who want to visit the lab and/or learn about renewable energy.

A conference facility would be highly beneficial to NREL's research and to the interests of many energy stakeholders. NREL currently processes its visitors (checks identification, issues badges) in a guardhouse of less than a thousand square feet.

The small buildings results in groups of visitors, including high-level executives, foreign energy ministers and delegations, and similar guests, to sometimes by forced to wait outside in bad weather, sometimes for an extended period of time.

NREL has a strong education program for K-12, but no onsite classroom space for demonstrating key scientific principles about energy to students, science teachers, and others. This lack of conference and classroom space results in lost opportunities to further science and technical education for many students, teachers, and school systems interested in renewable energy.

Figure B- 14: The National Renewable Energy Laboratory’s Grand Build-out Vision for the South Table Mountain Campus – Planned to enhance the interfaces between basic and applied science, and engineering and the marketplace.

Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-draughted on 1/06/2018 at 2:46am

Figure B- 15: Second floor plan of The National Renewable Energy Laboratory.
 Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-drafted on 1/06/2018 at 2:56am.

Figure B- 16: Integrated Biorefinery Research Facility Expansion at The National Renewable Energy Laboratory (Proposed expansion indicated by blue).
 Source: <https://www.nrel.gov/research>. Downloaded and re-drafted on 1/06/2018 at 3:06am.

Assessment Sheet (Weighting):

Serial number	Variables	Weighting (Maximum of 10 and minimum of 0)
SITE CONDITIONS		
1.	General landscaping	
2.	Efficiency of parking lots for automobiles	
3.	Impediments/Restrictions on site	
ZONING		
4.	Synergy between laboratories and offices	
5.	Interspatial communication between related spaces both in the laboratory sections and administration sections	
6.	Presence of public spaces including presentation rooms, conference rooms, auditoria.	
EQUIPMENT/WORKSPACE		
7.	Nominal operational clearance for laboratory equipment and casework.	
8.	Presence of installed equipment including digesters, casework and related machinery with respect to space.	
DESIGN ISSUES/CHALLENGES		
9.	Extensive glazing	
10.	Absence of sun-shading devices and thermal control features	
11.	Effective management of ambient temperature through incorporated design features	
AVAILABILITY OF SUPPORT SPACES\FACILITIES		
12.	Presence of auxiliary laboratories including vivaria, orchards, sequestration stations and dump sites.	
13.	Presence of academic spaces including classrooms and demonstration spaces.	
GENERAL ARCHITECTURE		

14.	Purpose-built integrity	
15.	Arrival Architecture	
FUTURE EXPANSION		
16.	Possibility for future expansion	

APPENDIX C

Figure C- 2: Proposed Site Layout of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 12:44am.

Figure C- 1: Proposed Site Layout: Topography of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 12:51am.

Figure C- 4: Proposed Site Layout: Climate of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 12:59am.

Figure C- 3: Proposed Site Zoning Pattern of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 1:02am.

Figure C- 8: Proposed Ground Floor Plan of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 1:31am.

Figure C- 7: Proposed First Floor Plan of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 1:34am.

Figure C- 9: Proposed Second Floor Plan of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 2:44am.

Figure C- 10: Proposed Third Floor Plan of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 2:45am.

Figure C- 12: Proposed Fourth Floor Plan of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 2:52am.

Figure C- 11: Proposed Fifth Floor Plan of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 2:53am.

Figure C- 14: Proposed Sixth Floor Plan of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 3:00am.

Figure C- 13: Three-dimensional views of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 3:04am.

Figure C- 17: Proposed North-East Elevation of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 3:26am.

Figure C- 18: Proposed South-East Elevation of The Biofuel Research Institute, Naze, Owerri-North, Imo State.

Source: Author's supervised scheme as at 11th of August, 2018 and attached at exactly 3:28am.

